

SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHING ANXIETY, EFFICACY BELIEFS AND MOTIVATION AMONG K-12 ENGLISH TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative research investigated Second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation among 386 English teachers in Batangas City Division, sampled from a larger population of 1100. The participants were mainly female elementary school teachers with master's degrees and 11 to 20 years of teaching experience. They reported experiencing anxiety related to self-perceived language proficiency, student engagement, and time management during second language instruction but expressed confidence in their teaching abilities. Notably, they did not feel anxious about their teaching experience or fear negative evaluations. The study employed statistical analyses, including ANOVA and t-tests, revealing no significant differences in teaching anxiety based on demographic profiles. However, significant variations in efficacy beliefs emerged when grouped by educational attainment, particularly concerning classroom proficiency and instructional strategies. External motivation also showed significant differences based on the teachers' highest educational level. Moreover, significant relationships were identified through Pearson correlation analysis, linking various factors in second language teaching. Key correlations included those between teaching anxiety and self-efficacy, self-perception of proficiency and classroom effectiveness, and various challenges faced in teaching. Based on these findings, an English language teacher improvement plan was developed, and recommendations for future research were made, emphasizing the importance of replicating and referencing this study to further explore these significant relationships and enhance teacher development in second language teaching.

Keywords: *Second Language Teaching Anxiety, Efficacy Beliefs, Motivation, English Teacher Improvement Plan*

INTRODUCTION

Learning a language is an essential part to be able to communicate and to understand the messages a human being wants to convey. Through language, human beings can perform duties and responsibilities, obtain needs and wants, survive day-to-day living, and enjoy entertainment and leisure. All of these are enjoyed in the context of a specific and the same language community. Equally important and capacitating is the ability to learn and utilize a second language (L2), which in turn, expands the opportunities and horizons of an individual. Learning a second language enables a person to transact with people who belong to the speech community that speaks that language.

The significance of language extends beyond individual communities, functioning in global interactions and understanding. Learning a second language does not only broaden one's personal horizons but also fosters intercultural communication and cooperation. In an increasingly interconnected world, proficiency in multiple languages is a valuable skill that opens doors to new opportunities and perspectives.

Today, English as a language, spoken widely all over the world, opens an array of opportunities –communication for business, academia and travel, wide access to online and offline information stored in English medium, wider educational opportunities, better understanding of technological advancements, better chances to learn culture of English-speaking countries, and global citizenship to name a few. The widespread use of English as a language transcends boundaries, making it an essential and required tool for communication and access to opportunities. Whether individuals acquire English as a second language, foreign language, or native tongue, its benefits are unfathomable. To illustrate, its role in facilitating global communication, particularly in business, academia, and travel is important.

In connection to this line of ideas, teaching a second language is challenging as second language teachers play a crucial role as facilitators and conversation partners for second language learners, creating a communicative environment for practice. Various factors such as instructional strategies, L2 proficiency, and feedback techniques impact language learning. Effective L2 teachers must be proficient in the target language to model correct pronunciation and grammar. Their instructional strategies and motivational skills greatly influence learner engagement and progress in language acquisition, highlighting the diverse set of skills and considerations needed to address the unique challenges of teaching a second language.

Establishing on the grounds of the previous situations, it could be deduced that various factors post difficulties in teaching a second or foreign language. More so, these factors accumulate and thus induce second language teaching anxieties that affect the quality of teaching and learning experiences students may get from these language teachers. Second, Language Teaching Anxiety refers to the feelings of unease, nervousness, or stress experienced by language teachers when instructing students in a second language. This type of anxiety can manifest in various forms, such as fear of making mistakes, concerns about students' comprehension, or worries about meeting

educational expectations. Second Language Teaching Anxiety can impact a teacher's confidence, teaching effectiveness, and overall well-being in the classroom (Zhang and Rahimi, 2021).

Previous studies have shown that anxiety in teaching a second or foreign language could lead to domino effects, opening the doors for various educational problems. Teaching anxiety could reduce instructional quality, because anxious teachers may struggle with delivering clear and effective lessons (Horwitz, 2019) and anxious teachers are less likely to implement innovative teaching strategies, opting instead for safer, more traditional methods that may not be as effective in promoting language acquisition (Tsiplakides and Keramida, 2020).

Second language teaching anxiety could also create an emotionally unstable classroom atmosphere which could negatively impact student motivation and engagement (Gkonou et al., 2020) because emotional states of teachers could often be mirrored by their students and could lead to a cyclical effect where anxiety is perpetuated within the classroom (Dewaele and MacIntyre, 2019). The relationship between teacher anxiety and student performance is further supported by studies indicating that high levels of teacher anxiety correlate with lower student achievement in language learning (Khajavy, Ghonsooly, Fatemi, and Choi, 2018).

As built by the foregoing arguments and citations, it can be said that building programs that could support second language teachers in terms of their challenges and difficulties could build initial and foundational steps toward improving teaching and learning English as a second language. Thus, there is a need for teacher training programs and stress management techniques to better prepare educators for the emotional demands of their profession (Gregersen & MacIntyre, 2021) and for ongoing professional development and support that could help teachers manage anxiety and improve their instructional practices (Tran, Baldauf, & Moni, 2019). This is to understand and address anxiety in ESL teaching which is essential for creating a conducive learning environment that could promote teacher well-being and student success (Oxford, 2020; Brown & White, 2020).

While second language teaching anxiety poses threats and difficulties in language teaching, efficacy beliefs of second language teachers could also make or break the teaching and learning outcomes. Soland (2019), defines second language teaching efficacy beliefs as teacher's confidence in their ability to effectively teach a second language to students. It involves the belief that one can successfully plan and execute language lessons, manage classroom activities, and support students in their language learning journey. Teachers with high Second Language Teaching Self-Efficacy Beliefs are more likely to persist in the face of challenges, utilize innovative teaching strategies, and positively impact student outcomes in language acquisition.

In the context of second language teaching efficacy beliefs, Kim and Elder (2021), emphasized the importance of teachers' confidence in their ability to effectively teach a second language. According to them, teachers with high efficacy beliefs are more likely

to implement innovative teaching strategies, persevere through challenges, and positively impact their students' language learning outcomes. They enumerated some key points regarding second language teaching efficacy beliefs including the impact of teachers' beliefs on student performance and motivation in learning a language, various strategies to improve teacher's self-efficacy in second language instruction, different roles of professional support and development in enhancing teachers' efficacy beliefs, the essential connection between teachers' efficacy beliefs and how these affect classroom management in second language classrooms, and finally, some research-based practices for encouraging optimistic efficacy beliefs among second language teachers. Overall, they underscore the significance of empowering teachers with the skills and confidence needed to create a motivating, engaging and effective language learning environment.

On the other hand, teachers could also demonstrate efficacy in providing constructive feedback and assessments which could help second language teachers guide student progress effectively, foster a positive classroom culture collaborating with colleagues for professional growth and improved teaching practices, keep up with current pedagogical research and apply it in the classroom is crucial for staying (Zhang and Rahimi, 2021).

MacIntyre (2018) also discussed about the important roles that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs play in second language learning process. He emphasizes that the confidence of teachers to effectively teach a second language directly influences their instructional routines and practices, and consequently, student outcomes. He added how self-efficacy beliefs results to positive teachers' grit, motivation and positive attitude to adopt innovative teaching strategies in a language classroom. He delves into effective strategies for enhancing self-efficacy in second language instruction, and the importance of professional development, support systems and coaching in improving teachers' confidence to teach and manage classes of second language learners, and to cultivate positive self-efficacy beliefs in the realm of second language teaching. Furthermore, he clearly emphasizes the connection between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and classroom dynamics, highlighting how confident teachers are more that equipped to manage diverse learning situations and take a lead in fostering positive student learning experiences and engagement in learning a second language.

With the possession of different self-efficacy beliefs on second language teaching, it is also worth taking note of motivation and its role to language teaching and learning. While it has been established in language learning, it is also important to study and describe how it influence the way second language teachers perform their roles in language acquisition and learning. Language teaching motivation refers to the drive, interest, and enthusiasm that a teacher could possess, in inspiring and engaging students in learning a new language, thus could significantly impact teaching effectiveness and student outcomes (Dörnyei & Ryan, 2020).

Various instances inside and outside classroom teaching could manifest motivation in teaching a second language. First is external motivation that plays a crucial role in shaping teachers' involvement, performance, and professional development in

context of teaching a second language. Mercer and Kostoulas (2018) explain that acknowledgement of second language teachers from co-workers, supervisors, and educational institutions for their teaching practices, enthusiasm, innovations, and contributions to language education can uplift teachers' motivation and morale to excel in their teaching roles and responsibilities. In addition, workshops, training programs and professional development opportunities are considered external motivators too, which play a vital role in improving teachers' motivation in second language instruction. Access to these kinds of learning opportunities and resources, inspires and equips second language teachers with positive perspective, fostering their growth and effectiveness in teaching a second language.

On the other hand, Kubanyiova (2020) discussed about the introjected motivation which is a form of internalize drive that affects teachers' performance and attitudes in teaching a second language. This kind of motivation in the context of language learning refers to internal expectations, pressures and standards that teachers carry out on themselves to achieve professional and personal goals in their respective teaching practices. He emphasized that teachers who are well-driven by introjected motivation in second language teaching often present work ethics like perfectionism, self-discipline and strong sense of responsibility. They set optimum standards for themselves, striving to top personal benchmarks of achievement and excellence in facilitating language learning experiences for their students.

Identified motivation, as described by Assor (2019), is a significant factor in second language teaching that enhances teachers' commitment, engagement, and effectiveness. This type of motivation occurs when teachers' personal goals, values, and beliefs align with the objectives of teaching a second language. Teachers motivated by identified factors demonstrate a meaningful connection to their roles, feeling a genuine sense of purpose and relevance in language education. This passion is driven by their recognition of the transformative impact language learning can have on students' lives.

Meanwhile Gao and Lamb (2021), explained that teachers who are intrinsically motivated in second language teaching demonstrate a genuine love for language learning, a deep interest in cultural exchange, and a sincere desire to foster communication skills in their students. Their enthusiasm for the subject matter and joy in witnessing students' progress and growth fuel their commitment to creating dynamic and engaging language learning environments. Aligned with their natural curiosity, creativity, and love for language, intrinsically motivated teachers often seek out innovative teaching methods, incorporate authentic materials, and design interactive activities that inspire student engagement and promote linguistic proficiency. Their intrinsic passion for language education drives them to continually explore new approaches, adapt to diverse learner needs, and cultivate a love for language learning in their students.

It is in these preceding contexts that the study entitled "Second Language Teaching Anxiety, Efficacy Beliefs and Motivation among K-12 English Teachers" was conducted. With the end goal of providing a proposed English language teacher improvement plan, this research investigated the interaction between and among teacher

anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation in the context of English language teaching across different profile variables.

This study could be considered significant to the following: First are the K-12 teachers who teach English as a second language. They will benefit from a better understanding of how anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation impact their teaching practices. This study can provide insights that help teachers improve their well-being, teaching effectiveness, and job satisfaction. Second are the school administrators who could gain insights into the factors that influence the performance and well-being of K-12 English teachers. Understanding teacher anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation can help administrators in creating supportive environments, offering targeted professional development, and enhancing teacher retention.

Teacher educators could also benefit from this study, as they can use the insights to tailor their training programs to address issues related to anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation among pre-service teachers, ensuring they are better prepared for the challenges of teaching English as a second language. Next are the students learning English as a second language in K-12 settings. Teachers who are less anxious, more confident in their teaching abilities, and highly motivated are likely to create more engaging and effective learning environments, leading to improved student outcomes and language proficiency. Finally, are the researchers in the field of education, specifically those interested in second language teaching and teacher well-being. The findings can add to the existing body of knowledge on second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation, guiding future research directions and informing best practices in teacher support and development.

Research Objectives

This study aims to determine the second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and motivation among K-12 English teachers in Batangas City Division.

Specifically, this research aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. describe the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and years of English language teaching experience;
2. determine foreign language teaching anxiety of the respondents as **to** self-perception of language proficiency, teaching inexperience, lack of student interest, fear of negative evaluation, and difficulties with time management;
3. identify the English language self-efficacy beliefs as regards to classroom proficiency, learner-focused instruction, assessment, language instruction, culture, and materials;

4. assess the second language teaching motivation of the respondents as to external motivation, introjected motivation, identified motivation, and intrinsic motivation;
5. test the significant difference in second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs and motivation, when respondents are grouped according to profile variables;
6. test the significant relationship among the three variables; and
7. propose an English language teacher improvement plan.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research study employed a descriptive quantitative design to achieve its objectives, focusing on examining current situations and identifying the attributes of specific phenomena through observation and exploration of correlations among them. It involved gathering descriptive information about events, which facilitated activities such as arranging, tabulating, illustrating, and explaining the collected data (Gay, 2020). This study quantitatively described the English teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and second language teaching motivation among K-12 English teachers in Batangas City Division. In this study, responses of the teachers to the adopted questionnaires were quantified through relevant descriptive scales. Moreover, data that were obtained underwent statistical tests or analysis to examine the significant differences of responses when profile variables were considered. Consequently, relationships between and among these variables were determined. Based on the aforementioned conditions, descriptive quantitative was the most suitable and appropriate design to use.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were the 386 basic education English teachers from the Division of Batangas City. These respondents were selected from the 1100 total English teachers from the aforementioned research locale. These respondents were sampled through stratified non-proportional allocation sampling method. In this sampling method, the size of the sample that was drawn from a particular stratum does not proportionate the relative size of that stratum. The total population was divided into different strata or subgroups, then the sample size for each stratum was decided. Finally, respondents were randomly selected from each stratum according to the allocated sample size.

Data Gathering Instrument

Based on literature review, a data-gathering instrument that quantitatively described the teachers' responses was used. This adopted research questionnaire quantitatively gathered data as regards second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and second language teaching motivation. Validation from experts and approval from the research adviser were sought. As a result, after incorporating the suggestions of the expert validator, the finalized instrument was then distributed to 30 participants for pilot testing.

Table 1 presents the reliability test results summary based on the pilot testing of the research questionnaire. Adapted from Aydin (2020), the first variable focused on Second Language Teaching Anxiety and outlined the various subdomains that highlighted the anxieties experienced by English Language teachers. The main objective was to create an instrument to assess Foreign Language Teaching Anxiety (FLTA). The subdomains included self-perception of language proficiency, teaching inexperience, lack of student interest, fear of negative evaluation, and difficulties with time management, each with corresponding reliability test results ranging from acceptable to good ratings based on Cronbach alpha values.

Table 1
Summary of Reliability Test Results

Indicators	Cronbach Alpha	Remarks
Self-perception of language proficiency	0.808	Good
Teaching inexperience	0.795	Acceptable
Lack of student interest	0.707	Acceptable
Fear of negative evaluation	0.844	Good
Difficulties with time management	0.850	Good
Classroom Proficiency	0.828	Good
Learner-Focused Instruction	0.949	Excellent
Assessment	0.918	Excellent
Language Instruction	0.942	Excellent
Culture	0.789	Excellent
Materials	0.893	Good
External Motivation	0.897	Good
Introjected Motivation	0.930	Excellent
Identified Motivation	0.892	Good
Intrinsic Motivation	0.907	Excellent

George and Mallery (2003) provide the following rules of thumb:

"_ > .9 – Excellent, _ > .8 – Good, _ > .7 – Acceptable, _ > .6 – Questionable, _ > .5 – Poor, and _ < .5 – Unacceptable"

Second language teaching efficacy beliefs consisted of six components: classroom proficiency, learner-focused instruction, assessment, language instruction,

culture, and materials, each with varying levels of reliability ranging from good to excellent based on their Cronbach alpha values. These components were derived from a study by Karas (2019).

The last part of the questionnaire focused on second language teaching motivation, four subdomains are explored: external motivation with a Cronbach alpha value of 0.897, introjected motivation with a value of 0.930, identified motivation with a value of 0.892, and intrinsic motivation with a value of 0.907. These subdomains were rated as either good or excellent and are based on the research by Sato et al. (2022).

Parts II-III of the questionnaire utilized the following scale to describe and quantify the responses of the participants towards survey items.

Option	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Description
4	3.5-4.00	Strongly Agree	High
3	2.50-3.49	Agree	Average
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Data Gathering Procedure

Once the adviser and the panel approved the research topic, the research instrument was developed based on the research objectives and literature review. Moreover, it was improved based on the comments and suggestions of the statistician and the validator. This research instrument was transformed into electronic copy, using Google Forms, to easily send it to the respondents and retrieved it thereafter. It also facilitated automation of the collection, tallying, and tabulation of the responses.

Upon approval of the commencement of the study, necessary permits for conducting were pursued and requests on data such as number of respondents were sought. Request letters were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Batangas City. As soon as the Schools Division superintendent approved the administration of the research questionnaire, the survey instrument was sent to the respondents through Google Forms. This platform allowed the researcher to harvest the results online, which were tabulated and sent to the statistician for processing and statistical treatment. The researcher then, started to analyze each table of the study, which was validated by the university statistician. Ample interpretations were written and literature reviews were cited to support the researcher’s analysis and interpretations.

Data Analysis

In attaining the objectives of the study, descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were utilized. In generating percentage and frequency distribution as related to the demographic profile, such as sex, educational attainment, and teaching position, and years of experience, descriptive statistics was used. In expressing the proportion or part of the sample or variable as compared to its whole, percentage was used. Weighted mean was used to compute the average of the different weights of the indicators/parameters in the questionnaire.

Inferential statistics such as Independent Samples t-Test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Levene's test, and Scheffe's Test were used to determine and describe the significant differences that were present in the variables when the respondents were grouped according to the expressed profile variables. The Independent Samples t Test was used to compare means of independent groups to determine statistical evidence that the population means were significantly different.

ANOVA was used to evaluate the difference between the means of the different groups respective to profile variables. Meanwhile, Levene's Test was used to check the assumption of equal variances before running the ANOVA. Finally, Scheffe Test is a post-hoc test used in Analysis of Variance used to find out which pairs of means are significant. While for the relationship between and among the three variables, namely: work tasks motivation, self-efficacy, and effectiveness, Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used.

Ethical Consideration

Various ethical considerations were ensured in this study. Before the research questionnaire was disseminated to 386 respondents, the study had been approved by the LPU-B-Research Ethics Review Committee. In consideration of the research protocols, data collection was properly observed in accordance to Data Privacy Act of 2012. This was primarily done using informed consent that was included in the beginning or first part of the questionnaire. This explained to the respondents that all data collected would be used academically, for research purposes, and would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

In the collection of data through the questionnaire, providing of name was optional and was never used to attribute to their responses. No part of the research attributed names or any identifying information to the data they provided. The respondents were asked to provide their school affiliation for monitoring purposes. These pieces of information were not included in the tabulation of data for analysis and interpretation. These raw data were kept secured and confidential in the google drive of the researcher and would be deleted after five years of the completion of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2
Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Profile

Sex	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	18	4.7
Female	368	95.3
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	162	42.0
Master's Degree	217	56.2
Doctorate Degree	7	1.8
Teaching Position		
Elementary Teacher (K-6 th)	357	92.5
Junior High School Teacher (7 th -10 th)	24	6.2
Senior High School Teacher (11 th -12 th)	5	1.3
Years of Teaching Experience		
10 years and below	135	35.0
11-20 years	142	36.8
21-30 years	76	19.7
31 years and above	33	8.5

Table 2 presents the respondent profiles into four categories: sex, level of education, teaching role, and years of teaching experience. These profiles furnish crucial contextual details about the sample population. By comprehending the demographic traits of the respondents, the researcher can evaluate the content validity of the results, ensuring their faithful reflection of the target population.

The data reveals that females represent a significant majority among respondents, accounting for 95.3% (368 individuals), while males comprise only 4.7% (18 individuals) out of a total of 386 respondents. This observation is consistent with findings from Bongco and Abenes (2019), which reference the Philippine Commission on Women data from 2008–2009, showing that 89.58% of public elementary and 77.06% of public secondary school teachers are female. Additionally, Banate and Saquin (2022) noted that in 2019, 87.35% of elementary teachers in the Philippines were female.

One significant reason for the prevalence of female English teachers over male teachers is that teaching, particularly at the primary and secondary levels, is often perceived as a more nurturing profession, which aligns with traditional gender roles that associate women with caregiving and nurturing responsibilities. This perception can attract more women to the profession from an early age. For instance, a study by Thornton and Bricheno (2021) suggested that societal expectations and cultural norms heavily influence career choices, with teaching viewed as a suitable career for women due to its perceived alignment with maternal roles.

Teaching could be typically characterized by relatively lower salaries compared to other professions requiring similar levels of education, which may deter men who often prioritize higher earning potential in their career choices. A report by the National Education Association (2020) highlighted that lower salaries in the teaching profession contribute to the gender imbalance, as women are more likely to accept lower wages due to historically entrenched wage disparities and societal norms regarding women's work.

Moreover, teaching profession is often seen as offering a better work-life balance, with more predictable hours and extended holidays, which can be particularly appealing to women who may bear a disproportionate share of domestic responsibilities. Research by Johnson and Johnson (2022), indicated that many women opt for teaching because it allowed for a manageable balance between professional and personal life, especially for those who plan to have or already have children.

In terms of educational attainment, individuals holding master's degrees dominate, comprising 56.2 percent with 217 respondents. Bachelor's degree holders follow at 42.0 percent, totaling 162 out of 386 respondents, and with doctorate holders representing 1.8 percent, comprising 7 respondents. Pursuing a master's degree is a common avenue for teachers to enhance their expertise in curriculum development and subsequently improve student performance. Obtaining a master's degree allows teachers to specialize, conduct research, and introduce innovative methodologies, thus enriching the education sector, as noted by Nucum (2019).

Many school districts and educational institutions have implemented policies that either require or strongly encourage teachers to pursue advanced degrees. These policies are often tied to teacher certification and continuing education mandates designed to ensure that educators are equipped with the latest pedagogical skills and knowledge. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2021), the push for higher educational standards among teachers is a direct response to the need for improved student outcomes and accountability in education systems.

Moreover, obtaining a master's degree often opens up career advancement opportunities and higher salary potential for teachers. Many educational systems offer significant salary increments and promotions for teachers who have earned advanced degrees, recognizing the additional expertise and dedication these qualifications represent. A study by Podolsky et al. (2020) found that teachers with master's degrees tend to have higher earning potential and are more likely to be considered for leadership roles such as department heads or administrative positions, making the pursuit of a master's degree an attractive professional investment.

The evolving demands of the educational landscape, including the integration of technology in the classroom and the need for specialized knowledge in areas such as special education and English as a Second Language (ESL), have made advanced degrees more valuable. Teachers with master's degrees are better prepared to meet these challenges and implement innovative teaching strategies that enhance student learning. Research by Kraft et al. (2021) highlighted that advanced education equips

teachers with critical skills in data analysis, curriculum development, and educational research, which are essential in today's complex educational environment.

Among teaching positions, elementary teachers hold the largest share, with 357 respondents, or 92.5 percent, followed by junior teachers at 6.2 percent with 24 respondents, senior high school teachers form the smallest group, with 5 respondents, or 1.3 percent. Republic Act No. 10533, mandating basic education completion for Filipino children aged 5 to 18, comprising six years of elementary and six years of secondary education, influences this distribution. Consequently, the higher number of elementary teachers is driven by legal requirements, with a proportional decrease in higher levels.

Early literacy is crucial for academic success, leading to a higher demand for elementary English teachers who specialize in teaching fundamental reading and writing skills. According to Cunningham and Zibulsky (2020), the early years of education are pivotal for developing literacy skills, making the role of elementary English teachers essential for laying the groundwork for students' future academic achievements.

Secondly, the structure of elementary education typically involves a single teacher responsible for teaching multiple subjects, including English, to a single class of students throughout the day. This model increases the number of teachers needed at the elementary level compared to middle or high school, where teachers usually specialize in one subject and teach multiple classes. Research by the National Center for Education Statistics (2021) indicated that the generalist nature of elementary teaching necessitates a higher number of teachers who are proficient in teaching English as part of a broader curriculum.

Demographic trends show higher enrollment numbers in elementary schools compared to secondary schools, partly due to population growth and compulsory education laws that mandate school attendance at younger ages. As a result, there is a greater demand for elementary teachers to accommodate the larger student populations in the early grades. A report by the U.S. Department of Education (2020) highlighted that the consistent influx of young students requires more elementary teachers to maintain optimal student-teacher ratios, thereby increasing the overall number of elementary English teachers.

Regarding teaching experience, those with 11 to 20 years of experience comprise the majority, representing 36.8 percent, or 142 out of 386 respondents. The bracket of 10 years and below is represented by 35 percent with 135 respondents, followed by 19.7 percent with 76 respondents having 21 to 30 years of experience, and 8.5 percent with 31 years or more, totaling 33 respondents.

The proliferation of teachers with 20 and below years teaching experience could be attributed to several factors, including high turnover rates, especially among newer teachers who may leave the profession within their first few years, may be due to challenges such as workload, insufficient support, and job dissatisfaction. This turnover contributes to a constant entry of new teachers who replace those who are leaving.

Additionally, educational policies and initiatives aimed at reducing student-to-teacher ratios and enhancing educational quality have led to increased hiring, bringing more novice teachers into the system. Retirement of more seasoned teachers also plays a significant role, as it opens up positions that are often filled by those with fewer years of experience. The growing recognition of the need for diverse teaching approaches and the integration of technology in classrooms have driven a demand for younger, more technologically adept teachers.

The increase in teachers with 11-20 years of experience is corroborated by DepEd Data Bits (2022), showing a consistent rise in teacher numbers across all levels from School Year (SY) 2016-2017 to SY 2020-2021, with an overall increase of 21.1 percent. This increase is further detailed with a 14.2% rise for elementary, 21.8% for junior high school, and 101.3% for senior high school levels.

Some school systems have implemented retention policies aimed at supporting and retaining experienced teachers. These policies often include professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and financial incentives such as higher salaries and retirement benefits for more experienced teachers. According to Sutchter, Darling-Hammond, and Carver-Thomas (2019), retention strategies ensured that teachers remain in the profession, particularly those who have surpassed the early career attrition phase.

Teachers with 11-20 years of experience have accumulated substantial pedagogical expertise and classroom management skills, making them valuable assets to their schools. Their extensive experience allows them to adapt to diverse classroom situations, implement effective teaching strategies, and mentor less experienced colleagues. A study by Kraft and Papay (2020) highlighted that teacher effectiveness improves significantly during the first decade of teaching, stabilizing after about 10 years, which contributes to the higher numbers of teachers remaining in the profession during this period.

Job satisfaction and career commitment often stabilize after the initial years of teaching, leading to increased retention rates among mid-career teachers. Teachers in the 11–20-year range typically have a more stable work-life balance, a deeper sense of professional identity, and stronger connections with their school communities, all of which contribute to their continued presence in the field. Research by Ingersoll, Merrill, and Stuckey (2021) showed that mid-career teachers report higher levels of job satisfaction and a greater likelihood of remaining in the profession compared to their early-career counterparts.

Table 3
Second Language Teaching Anxiety
as to Self-perception of Language Proficiency

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel embarrassed when I make mistakes while I am speaking.	2.95	Agree	1
2. I feel tensed when I have difficulties teaching grammar	2.95	Agree	2
3. I feel pressured when students bring unexpected questions.	2.57	Agree	4
4. I feel nervous when I commit mistakes in pronouncing words.	2.67	Agree	3
5. I feel embarrassed when some students speak English better than me	2.50	Agree	5
Composite Mean	2.73	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 3 presents the respondent's assessment of teaching anxiety as to self-perception of language proficiency. The composite mean of 2.73 indicates that the respondents agreed that they have second language teaching anxiety as to self-perception of language proficiency. The items on embarrassment when making mistakes while speaking and feeling tensed when having difficulties in teaching grammar both got the highest mean score of 2.95. It was followed by feeling nervous when committing mistakes in pronouncing words with 2.67 mean. All three item were verbally interpreted with agree. Meanwhile, feeling pressured when students bring unexpected questions (2.57) and feeling embarrassed when some students speak English better (2.50) were rated the least but still interpreted as agree.

Second language teaching anxiety affects teachers' self-perception of their language proficiency, which can impact their classroom experiences and effectiveness. Key manifestations include embarrassment from making mistakes while speaking and tension when teaching grammar. High anxiety, particularly during speaking activities, can lead to self-doubt and hinder effective communication. This apprehension is often exacerbated when teachers face unexpected student questions, reflecting their concerns about adequately conveying complex language concepts. Aydin (2020) emphasizes how these feelings can negatively influence teachers' language proficiency and overall teaching performance.

Additionally, ESL teachers frequently experience tension and anxiety when teaching complex grammatical concepts. Grammar is often perceived as a particularly challenging area, both for learners and instructors, because it requires precise knowledge and the ability to explain intricate rules and exceptions. Kim and Elder (2021) found that ESL teachers reported higher levels of anxiety when tasked with teaching grammar, as they feared being unable to provide clear and accurate explanations, which could undermine their credibility in the eyes of students.

The third in rank, nervousness regarding pronunciation mistakes indicates anxiety related to oral production. Fear of making pronunciation errors can affect self-perceived language competence. Moreover, teachers may experience nervousness when they make pronunciation mistakes, which can stem from concerns about their perceived linguistic accuracy and credibility as language instructors.

The last indicator, feelings of embarrassment may arise when some students speak English better than the teacher, highlighting the comparison between the teacher's language proficiency and that of their students. Teachers of English as a Second Language (ESL) might experience Second Language Teaching Anxiety (SLTA) related to self-perception of language proficiency. One factor is the fear of making mistakes while speaking, which can lead to feelings of embarrassment. This anxiety is rooted in the high expectations placed on language teachers to model perfect language use. According to Horwitz (2020), teachers often feel pressured to demonstrate language proficiency, and any deviation from this standard can lead to self-doubt and anxiety, impacting their teaching performance and self-esteem.

The self-perception of language proficiency also is involved in SLTA. Teachers who doubt their language abilities are more likely to experience anxiety, particularly when they compare themselves to native speakers or other proficient individuals. This comparison can lead to a heightened awareness of their own linguistic shortcomings, worsening feelings of inadequacy and stress. Faez and Valeo (2021) highlighted that non-native English-speaking teachers often struggle with confidence issues, fearing judgment from students and peers, leading to a heightened state of anxiety in teaching situations. Moreover, institutions often expect ESL teachers to not only teach language but also to serve as cultural intermediaries, which adds an additional layer of responsibility and pressure. This can be overwhelming, particularly for those who are still grappling with their own language proficiency and cultural adaptation. According to Mercer and Kostoulas (2021), these expectations can create a significant emotional burden, leading to increased levels of stress and anxiety.

Table 4 outlines the respondent's evaluations regarding teaching anxiety, specifically concerning teaching inexperience and language proficiency. The composite mean of 2.08 suggests a general disagreement among respondents. Fear in making mistakes while teaching in the classroom obtained the highest mean score of 2.46, followed by, being nervous due to lack of teaching experience with a score of 2.31, both interpreted as disagreement. Conversely, items on feeling worried before entering the classroom and feeling anxious when teaching in the classroom both garnered a weighted mean of 1.90. Finally, feeling tense when in the classroom received a mean score of 1.82. All these criteria were verbally interpreted as disagree.

Table 4
Second Language Teaching Anxiety as to Teaching Inexperience

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I think my lack of teaching experience makes me nervous	2.31	Disagree	2
2. I fear making mistakes while I am teaching in the classroom	2.46	Disagree	1
3. I feel worried before entering the classroom	1.90	Disagree	4
4. I feel anxious when I teach in the classroom	1.90	Disagree	3
5. I feel tensed when I am in the classroom	1.82	Disagree	5
Composite Mean	2.08	Disagree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Of all the indicators, fear in making mistakes while teaching in the classroom obtained the highest mean score. Apprehensions about making mistakes during classroom instruction could be mitigated by regarding errors as integral to the learning process, as highlighted by Dewaele et al. (2019), emphasizing the importance of resilience in diminishing language teaching anxiety. Furthermore, feelings of pre-classroom apprehension and the experience of anxiety or tension while teaching may not solely originate from teaching inexperience but could also be influenced by factors such as lesson preparation and classroom management skills. This viewpoint was substantiated by Zhang's (2022) research, which demonstrated that adept preparation and effective classroom management strategies have the potential to alleviate anxiety among novice language instructors.

Second in rank is being nervous due to lack of teaching experience. When examining the indicators associated with teaching inexperience and second language teaching anxiety from a perspective of disagreement, it suggests a certain level of ease or confidence despite the lack of teaching background. Initially, the notion that a deficiency in teaching experience induces nervousness may not apply to individuals who view their inexperience as an opportunity for personal and professional growth rather than a cause for anxiety. This perspective finds support in a study conducted by Zhang and Rahimi (2020), revealing that novice educators who embraced their lack of experience as a chance for learning exhibited reduced levels of anxiety.

Teaching ESL requires specialized skills and knowledge that go beyond general teaching methods, thus teachers may feel inadequately prepared to address educational needs of ESL students. For instance, a study on pre-service ESL teachers highlighted the challenges they face, such as a lack of self-confidence in their teaching abilities and difficulties in managing the specific requirements of ESL instruction (Ugalingan, Edjan, & Valdez, 2021) Moreover, the pressure to facilitate effective communication in a language

that students are not fluent in adds to the anxiety. Beginning teachers might lack confidence in their ability to create supportive language learning environment. They may also worry about their capacity to assess and track progress accurately, provide constructive feedback, and address the varied proficiency levels within a single classroom. Additionally, the emotional experiences and responses of ESL teachers, including feelings of anxiety and uncertainty, are significant factors that impact their teaching effectiveness (Golombek & Johnson, 2021). These challenges underscore the importance of targeted professional development and support for teachers new to ESL instruction to build their confidence and competence in this specialized field.

Table 5 summarizes the respondents' assessment of teaching anxiety in relation to lack of interest. The composite mean score of 2.66 indicates a general agreement among the respondents. Of all the indicators, respondents agreed most that they feeling stressed when students do not participate in the activities, and it received the highest mean score. This suggests that respondents commonly experience stress when student participation is lacking, because it got the highest mean score of 2.80. It was followed by feeling of discouragement when students lose interest in different macro-skill activities and feeling upset when students are bad at learning the English language because these items got computed weighted mean scores of 2.69 and 2.66, respectively. Respondents agreed to all these statements, as second language teaching anxieties in terms of lack of interest as evinced by their means. Meanwhile, the feeling of tense when students are not interested in the activities (2.36) and feeling of discouragement when my students show disappointment when teaching language (2.52) were still rated as second language teaching anxieties in terms of to lack of interest but got the lowest means. Overall, the respondents' teaching anxiety related to lack of interest appears to be a common experience, with varying degrees of intensity.

Table 5
Second Language Teaching Anxiety as to Lack of Interest

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel discouraged when students lose interest in different macro-skill activities	2.69	Agree	2
2. I feel tensed when students are not interested in the activities	2.63	Agree	4
3. I feel stressed when students do not participate in the activities	2.80	Agree	1
4. I feel upset because my students are bad at learning English language	2.66	Agree	3
5. I feel discouraged when my students show disappointment when I teach language.	2.52	Agree	5
Composite Mean	2.66	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

As mentioned, the respondents feel stressed when students do not participate in activities, thus may reflect a concern about one's ability to engage and motivate learners, which a perceived lack of proficiency can worsen. This most rated cause of teaching anxiety as related to student interest provided highlight a strong connection between self-perception of language proficiency and second language teaching anxiety. According to research, teachers' ability to regulate emotions and build positive relationships with students significantly impacts engagement and motivation (Greenier et al., 2021). Moreover, studies have shown that teacher empathy positively influences student engagement and motivation by creating a supportive and understanding classroom atmosphere (Zhang, 2022). When students do not participate, it can lead to teachers doubting their capacity to connect with and inspire their students, further exacerbating their stress levels. Additionally, the stress experienced by teachers can be linked to broader concerns about maintaining classroom discipline and achieving educational goals (Öztürk, 2021).

ESL teachers might frequently feel stressed when students do not participate in classroom activities. Active participation is crucial for language acquisition, and when students are disengaged, teachers may question their teaching methods and feel a sense of failure. According to a study by Dewaele and MacIntyre (2020), student participation is a key factor influencing teacher emotions, and lack of engagement can lead to significant stress and anxiety for teachers who strive to create interactive and dynamic learning environments.

It can be deduced also that the second cause of teaching anxiety as regards student interest is the feeling of discouragement when students lose interest in different macro-skill activities. It could suggest a personal sense of inadequacy in maintaining student engagement, especially in activities related to different language skills. Additionally, ESL teachers may feel discouraged when students lose interest in different macro-skill activities such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These activities are essential for comprehensive language development, and a lack of interest can hinder students' progress. Teachers often invest considerable effort in designing engaging and varied activities, and when these efforts do not result in student enthusiasm, it can be demoralizing. Kim and Kim (2021) found that ESL teachers frequently experience feelings of discouragement and helplessness when their carefully planned activities fail to capture students' interest, contributing to higher levels of teaching anxiety.

Furthermore, teachers can feel particularly upset when students struggle with learning the English language. This situation, and the third indicator can be challenging because it could reflect issues. Teachers may feel that they are not adequately equipped to address these issues, leading to frustration and anxiety. According to Gkonou and Mercer (2022), the inability to effectively support struggling students is a significant source of anxiety for ESL teachers, who may internalize these challenges as personal failures. The pressure to meet educational standards and student expectations further exacerbates this anxiety. ESL teachers are often evaluated based on their students'

performance, and when students do not perform well, teachers may feel that their professional competence is being questioned. This pressure can lead to a constant state of anxiety and self-doubt. A study by Liu and Huang (2020) indicates that performance-related stress is a significant factor contributing to SLTA among ESL teachers, particularly when dealing with unmotivated or struggling students.

The fourth indicator, feeling tense when students show disinterest in activities, may stem from a fear of being unable to meet students' learning needs or expectations, thus reflecting a perceived deficiency in language proficiency. Feeling discouraged when students express disappointment in teaching efforts may exacerbate feelings of inadequacy and self-doubt, particularly if these reactions are interpreted as reflections of the teacher's language proficiency. This association is supported by Liu (2019), who emphasized the role of student feedback in shaping teacher emotions and anxiety in language teaching contexts, and Piniel and Albert (2018), who underscored the importance of managing teacher emotions in the language classroom.

Lastly, the emotional labor involved in teaching can take a toll on ESL teachers' mental health. Constantly trying to engage uninterested students and address their diverse needs requires significant emotional energy. When students do not respond positively, teachers can experience burnout and emotional exhaustion. Mercer and Gregersen (2020) highlighted that the emotional demands of teaching, especially in challenging environments, can lead to chronic stress and anxiety, impacting teachers' overall well-being.

Table 6
Second Language Teaching Anxiety as to Fear of Negative Evaluation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel nervous and uneasy when my mentor-teacher/supervisor observes me teaching English.	2.64	Agree	1
2. I frequently commit mistakes and stutter when I know I am being observed and evaluated.	2.41	Disagree	4
3. I feel nervous about students' negative comments about my teaching performance.	2.33	Disagree	5
4. I feel anxious about my students telling their parents and other people about my mistakes and other negative/poor performance.	2.45	Disagree	3
5. I feel pressured to prepare more than the usual preparations, such as macro skill activities, language	2.57	Agree	2

materials, etc. when I have been scheduled for observation or evaluation.

Composite Mean

2.48

Disagree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

It could be gleaned from Table 6 above the different assessment of the respondents towards teaching anxiety as to fear of negative evaluation. The composite mean of 2.48 indicates that most of the respondents disagreed in general. Of all the indicators, respondents rated the following items most: feeling of nervousness and uneasiness when mentor-teacher/supervisor observes in teaching English, as supported by the mean score of 2.64, followed by the feeling of pressure to prepare more than the usual preparations, such as macro skill activities, language materials, etc., when scheduled for observation or evaluation with a weighted mean of 2.57. Respondents declared that these two are second language teaching anxiety as to fear of negative evaluation.

As evinced by the most-rated indicator, second language teachers might experience nervousness and uneasiness when their mentor-teacher or supervisor observes their teaching. This anxiety stems from the high stakes associated with evaluations, which can impact their professional reputation, job security, and career advancement. According to Kim and Kim (2021), the presence of an evaluator in the classroom heightens teachers' self-consciousness and fear of making mistakes, leading to increased stress and anxiety. The agreement with the criterion above suggests a significant fear of negative evaluation among language teachers, contributing to their experience of second language teaching anxiety. When language teachers experience nervousness and unease during observations by their mentor-teachers or supervisors, it reflects a form of anxiety related to their teaching performance. This anxiety may stem from the fear of being negatively evaluated or judged by others.

The fear of negative evaluation is also linked to the broader implications of evaluations on teachers' self-efficacy and confidence. Negative feedback or perceived criticism can undermine a teacher's belief in their own teaching abilities, leading to long-term anxiety and reduced job satisfaction. A study by Dewaele et al. (2020) found that ESL teachers who receive critical evaluations often experience lingering self-doubt, which can negatively affect their overall teaching performance and well-being.

Moreover, the anxiety associated with evaluations can impact the teacher-student dynamic. Teachers may feel pressured to prioritize performance over authentic teaching practices, which can lead to a less natural and more rigid classroom environment. This shift in focus can hinder the development of a supportive and engaging learning atmosphere. According to Farrell (2021), the stress of evaluations can cause teachers to adopt a more performative approach, which may not align with their usual teaching style and can reduce the effectiveness of their instruction.

Additionally, as suggested by the second most-rated indicator, language teachers often feel compelled to go beyond their usual preparations when they know they will be observed or evaluated. This heightened preparation pressure arises from the fear of negative evaluation. Teachers want to ensure that their lesson plans, materials, and activities are flawless to avoid any criticism. This fear-driven preparation can lead to stress and anxiety (Papi & Khajavy, 2021). This interpretation resonates with research by Malini and Janakavalli (2018) who identified a correlation between fear of negative evaluation and increased preparation efforts among language teachers. The pressure to perform well during observations leads second language teachers to invest significantly more time and effort in preparing for these sessions compared to regular classes. This includes creating detailed lesson plans, preparing extensive macro-skill activities (listening, speaking, reading, and writing), and developing high-quality language materials. The additional workload can be overwhelming and exacerbate feelings of anxiety. As highlighted by Tsui (2020), the preparation for observed lessons often involves an excessive focus on perfection, which can be mentally and physically exhausting for teachers.

Furthermore, the competitive nature of evaluations, where teachers are often compared to their peers, can create additional pressure. This comparison can foster a sense of inadequacy and fear of falling short of expectations, both from supervisors and colleagues. Research by Horwitz (2021) suggested that the competitive aspect of evaluations contributes significantly to SLTA, as teachers strive to meet or exceed the standards set by others in their profession.

On the other hand, the respondents disagreed that the feeling of anxiousness when students tell their parents and other people about teacher's mistakes and other negative/poor performance. (2.45), frequently committing mistakes and stutter when being observed and evaluated (2.41), and feeling nervous about students' negative comments about teaching performance (2.33) are second language teaching anxiety as to fear of negative evaluation.

The respondents' disagreement with the provided indicators suggests a variation in their experience of fear of negative evaluation within the context of second language teaching. Firstly, the lack of anxiety about students disclosing mistakes or negative performance to their parents or others may indicate a level of confidence or trust in their teaching abilities, despite the potential for scrutiny. Similarly, the absence of frequent mistakes or stuttering when being observed and evaluated may reflect a sense of composure or competence in managing performance anxiety, contrary to the expectations of fear-driven reactions. Additionally, the lack of nervousness regarding negative comments from students about teaching performance may suggest resilience or detachment from external judgments, indicating a lessened fear of negative evaluation. This interpretation is consistent with research by Dewaele and Dewaele (2019), who identified coping strategies that mitigate the impact of negative feedback on language teacher anxiety.

Table 7
Second Language Teaching Anxiety
as to Difficulties with Time Management

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel tensed when I am not prepared for class.	2.86	Agree	1
2. I am nervous when I finish the activities before the class ends	2.17	Disagree	5
3. I feel panicked when I cannot finish the class on time	2.22	Disagree	4
4. I feel that the allotted time for language activities is not enough for language learning or acquisition to happen.	2.70	Agree	3
5. I experience controlling time limits in activities, such as limiting students' response time, capsulating student group activities, restricting reading time, etc.	2.78	Agree	2
Composite Mean	2.55	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 7 presents the respondent's assessment of teaching anxiety as to time management. It could be seen that the composite mean of 2.55 indicates that most of the respondents agreed in general. Based on the table, it could be gleaned that the respondents are tensed when not prepared for class (highest mean score of 2.86), experience controlling time limits in activities, such as limiting students' response time, capsulating student group activities, restricting reading time, etc. (next highest mean of 2.78)" and feel that the allotted time for language activities is not enough for language learning or acquisition to happen (with 2.70 mean).

The top indicator of teaching anxiety as related to time management is when language teachers feel tense or anxious due to a lack of preparation for their classes. This anxiety may arise from concerns about delivering quality lessons, meeting students' expectations, or managing unexpected situations. The respondents' agreement with the provided indicators suggests that difficulties with time management contribute to their experience of second language teaching anxiety.

Research by Liu (2019) emphasizes that effective time management is vital for reducing stress among language teachers, as anxiety can negatively impact their motivation, behavior, and performance. Unpreparedness can worsen this anxiety, resulting in less effective teaching. Proper preparation is essential, and failures in this area can diminish confidence and increase anxiety levels. Kim and Kim (2021) also note

that ESL teachers often feel overwhelmed by lesson planning demands alongside other responsibilities, leading to inadequate preparation and heightened anxiety.

The second-rated indicator shows that teachers are anxious when they experience difficulties in controlling time. This observation resonates with the findings by Borg (2020), who highlighted the impact of time constraints on language teaching practices and teacher well-being. Teachers may worry about covering all content within the allotted time, leading to stress and potentially affecting their teaching quality. Feeling that the allocated time for language activities is insufficient can create anxiety for language teachers. Managing time limits is crucial for maintaining a productive learning environment. While setting deadlines for student responses or structuring group activities is necessary, excessive time pressure can contribute to anxiety.

Some teachers reported not feeling panicked when they could not complete their class within the allocated time. While this may be attributed to effective lesson planning, flexibility, or experience, it is essential to recognize that time pressure can still affect teaching quality and student engagement (Papi and Khajavy, 2021).

Moreover, the challenge of controlling time limits in classroom activities adds to this anxiety. ESL teachers often need to balance various activities such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing within a limited time frame. Effective time management is essential to ensure that all learning objectives are met, but it can be challenging to achieve, particularly with diverse student needs and unpredictable classroom dynamics. A study by Richards and Lockhart (2020) found that ESL teachers often struggle with pacing their lessons and managing transitions between activities, which can lead to feelings of inadequacy and stress. Furthermore, the pressure to create engaging and interactive lessons can add to the time management challenges faced by ESL teachers. Developing creative and effective language activities requires significant time and effort, and the fear of not being able to execute these activities within the allotted time can lead to anxiety. According to Tsui (2020), the expectation to deliver high-quality, student-centered lessons can create additional stress for teachers, particularly when they feel they do not have enough time to prepare or implement these activities effectively.

Additionally, unexpected disruptions or deviations from the lesson plan can exacerbate time management difficulties. Teachers may find it challenging to adapt on the fly while still covering the required material, leading to anxiety about falling behind or not meeting curriculum standards. Farrell (2021) highlighted that the ability to adapt and manage time effectively is a skill that develops with experience, and novice teachers, in particular, may experience higher levels of anxiety due to their inexperience in handling such situations.

The diverse proficiency levels and learning paces of students in ESL classrooms can complicate time management further. Teachers need to differentiate instruction and provide additional support to some students, which can disrupt planned time allocations for activities. Dewaele and MacIntyre (2020) found that managing a classroom with

varying levels of English proficiency requires careful time management and flexibility, adding to the overall stress and anxiety experienced by teachers.

Ranking in third is when teachers feel anxious about insufficiency of time for language acquisition activities. Guvendir (2021) emphasized the importance of understanding second language anxiety and its impact on learners. Language teachers may experience anxiety when they perceive time limitations hindering effective language learning or acquisition. This interpretation is supported by research by Gao and Zhang (2019), who discussed the challenges of time constraints in language teaching and its implications for teacher stress. Teachers who feel that time constraints prevent meaningful interactions or comprehensive language practice may struggle to create engaging lessons.

On the other hand, respondents disagreed that feeling panicked when they cannot finish the class on time and being nervous when finishing the activities before the class ends (with weighted means of 2.22 and 2.17 respectively) as indicators of their second language teaching anxiety with respect to time management.

In a study examining Second Language Teaching Anxiety (SLTA) and its correlation with difficulties in time management, it was found that respondents exhibited disagreement with certain indicators related to time management (Aydin, 2018). Respondents disagreed that they feel panicked when I cannot finish the class on time. This disagreement suggests that the respondents did not experience a sense of panic or overwhelming stress when faced with time constraints in the classroom setting.

Additionally, respondents disagreed that they feel nervous when they finish the activities before the class ends. This interpretation aligns with research by Gkonou, Daubney, and Dewaele (2019) that found that language teachers' anxiety levels could vary based on individual factors such as experience, teaching context, and coping strategies. Furthermore, the agreement with this indicator underscores the dynamic nature of SLTA and its interaction with time management skills in language teaching contexts. By understanding teachers' perceptions and experiences related to time management, educators and stakeholders can develop targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance teaching effectiveness and alleviate anxiety-related challenges.

Table 8
Summary Table on Second Language Teaching Anxiety

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Self-perception of language proficiency	2.73	Agree	1
2. Teaching Inexperience	2.08	Disagree	5
3. Lack of Interest	2.66	Agree	2
4. Fear of negative evaluation	2.48	Disagree	4

5. Difficulties with time management	2.55	Agree	3
Composite Mean	2.50	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 8 displays the summary indicators of Second Language Teaching Anxiety. It can be gleaned from the table above that the composite mean is at 2.50 with verbal interpretation agreement. Though some indicators fell under the category disagree, most of the indicators were under the agreement category, which led to the total mean of 2.50, leading to general agreement.

Table 8 above illustrates that self-perception of language proficiency was at the topmost position, followed by lack of Interest, then difficulties with time management. The computed weighted means were 2.73, 2.66, and 2.55 respectively, with verbal interpretation of agree. The last two indicators were fear of negative evaluation (2.48) and teaching inexperience (2.08), both were interpreted as disagree.

In analyzing the indicators under Table 8, it becomes evident that respondents share similar perceptions regarding their self-perception of language proficiency, lack of interest, and difficulties with time management. Firstly, regarding self-perception of language proficiency, the respondents agree that their self-perceived language proficiency contributes to anxiety in second language teaching. This suggests that teachers who feel less confident in their language abilities may experience anxiety when teaching a second language (Gkonou, Daubney, & Dewaele, 2019). ESL teachers grapple with their self-perception of language proficiency. Teachers who perceive their language skills as inadequate may experience heightened anxiety, particularly when they compare themselves to native speakers or more proficient colleagues. According to Dewaele and MacIntyre (2019), this comparison can lead to feelings of inferiority and self-doubt, which are detrimental to a teacher's confidence and performance in the classroom. Teachers might worry about making mistakes or being unable to provide clear and accurate explanations, which can undermine their authority and credibility. Additionally, cultural and institutional factors can influence these anxieties.

Secondly rated, respondents also agree that a lack of interest is associated with anxiety in language teaching. When teachers are not passionate or interested in the subject matter, it can lead to feelings of anxiety and stress in the classroom (Papi & Khajavy, 2021). The respondents perceive that time management challenges contribute to anxiety. Lack of student interest significantly contributes to teacher anxiety. When students are disengaged or indifferent, teachers may feel that their efforts are unappreciated and ineffective. This sense of futility can lead to discouragement and a lack of motivation, as noted by Kim and Kim (2021). Teachers might feel responsible for their students' lack of engagement, which can lead to self-blame and increased anxiety. The constant struggle to capture and maintain student interest can be exhausting and demoralizing, especially when teachers have put significant effort into lesson planning and activity design.

Student engagement and self-perceived proficiency creates a compounding effect on anxiety. For example, a teacher who is already anxious about their language proficiency might feel even more stressed when students are unresponsive or disinterested. This lack of feedback can reinforce the teacher's negative self-perception, leading to a vicious cycle of anxiety and self-doubt. Farrell (2021) highlighted that this cycle can be particularly damaging for novice teachers who are still building their confidence and teaching skills.

Interestingly, the respondents disagree that fear of negative evaluation contributes to their anxiety. This contrasts with findings from Cheng and Cheng (2010), who emphasized the impact of fear of negative evaluation on language teacher anxiety. Similarly, respondents also disagree on teaching inexperience, indicating a range of experiences among participants. This finding contrasts with research by Botes et al. (2018), which underscored the role of teaching inexperience as a potential trigger for anxiety among language instructors. Overall, the analysis of these indicators provides insights into the complex interplay of factors contributing to second language teaching anxiety among respondents.

Moreover, the pressure to meet educational standards and perform well in evaluations can further exacerbate these anxieties. ESL teachers often face high expectations from supervisors, colleagues, and themselves to deliver effective and engaging lessons. When faced with disinterested students or doubts about their language abilities, the fear of negative evaluation can become overwhelming. Horwitz (2021) pointed out that the pressure to perform can lead teachers to overprepare and second-guess their teaching methods, adding to their stress and anxiety.

Table 9
English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Classroom Proficiency

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>I can use English as the medium of instruction.</i>	3.37	Agree	1
2. <i>I can use English for all classroom functions and interactions.</i>	3.15	Agree	5
3. <i>I can use English to provide spoken and written feedback in class.</i>	3.20	Agree	3
4. <i>I can model natural English use.</i>	3.18	Agree	4
5. <i>I can use common phrases/words that frequently occur in English language classrooms.</i>	3.34	Agree	2
Composite Mean	3.25	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 9 presents the respondent's assessment of English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Classroom Proficiency. It could be gleaned that the composite mean of 3.25 indicates that most of the respondents agreed in general. Respondents agreed that all items are indicators of English language self-efficacy in terms of classroom proficiency. They can use English as the medium of instruction (weighted mean of 3.37), can use common phrases/words that frequently occur in English language classrooms (with 3.34 weighted mean) can use English to provide spoken and written feedback in class (with 3.20), and lastly they can model natural English use and can use English for all classroom functions and interactions (with 3.18 and 3.15 weighted means respectively).

The first indicator, wherein the respondents asserted that they can use English as the medium of instruction, underscores the importance of teachers' confidence in their language proficiency for delivering lessons effectively. Analyzing the indicators of English language self-efficacy in terms of classroom proficiency reveals key insights into teachers' perceptions of their language abilities and their impact on classroom dynamics. Under this indicator, it involves using English as the primary language for teaching various subjects, even in non-native English-speaking countries. Wang (2021) found a strong positive relationship between English medium instruction (EMI) teachers' classroom English proficiency and their teaching self-efficacy. EMI teachers who can effectively use English as the medium of instruction tend to have higher self-efficacy in their teaching roles.

According to Richards and Farrell (2020), comprehensive training helps teachers develop a strong foundation in both language proficiency and pedagogical techniques, enabling them to use English confidently and effectively in the classroom. Additionally, continuous professional development plays a significant role in enhancing ESL teachers' efficacy. Regular workshops, seminars, and courses keep teachers updated with the latest teaching strategies and language trends, further boosting their confidence. Kim and Elder (2021) highlighted that ongoing professional development allows teachers to refine their skills and adapt to new teaching contexts, ensuring they remain proficient and effective in using English as the medium of instruction.

Additionally, the second-most rated indicator is using common phrases/words in English language classrooms indicator. This could reflect the teacher's ability to employ everyday language commonly used in English language classrooms. It includes phrases related to classroom management, instructions, and interactions. The frequent use of common phrases and words in English language classrooms contributes to teachers' sense of efficacy. These commonly used linguistic tools help establish clear and consistent communication patterns, making it easier for teachers to manage the classroom and convey instructions effectively. Research by Dewaele and MacIntyre (2019) indicated that the repetitive use of these phrases helps both teachers and students become familiar with classroom routines, reducing misunderstandings and enhancing overall classroom management.

The third most rated indicator is providing spoken and written feedback in English indicator. This highlights the teacher's confidence in giving feedback to students in spoken and written form using English. The positive feedback and progress of students also reinforce teachers' belief in their efficacy. When students demonstrate improvement in their English language skills, it validates the teachers' methods and use of English as the medium of instruction. According to Faez and Valeo (2021), observing students' progress provides teachers with tangible evidence of their effectiveness, boosting their confidence and sense of accomplishment.

Modeling natural English use indicator refers to the teacher's ability to demonstrate natural and authentic English language use. Modeling helps students learn proper pronunciation, intonation, and language structures. When a teacher models natural English, they demonstrate the rhythm and flow of the language, helping students grasp how native speakers use stress and intonation to convey meaning and emotion. This can significantly improve students' listening skills and their ability to mimic these patterns in their own speech. Research has shown that exposure to authentic language use can enhance learners' phonological awareness and pronunciation skills (Darling-Hammond, et.al., 2021).

Using English for all classroom functions enhances students' listening and speaking skills through immersive activities like discussions and explanations, rather than isolated lessons. Hoang (2021) emphasizes that consistent exposure to the target language in meaningful contexts is vital for language acquisition, allowing learners to internalize vocabulary and linguistic structures. This approach models real-life English use in various scenarios, such as giving instructions and conducting discussions, which helps students develop practical language skills. Additionally, teachers' proficiency in classroom English reflects their confidence and can boost their self-efficacy, suggesting that prioritizing language training in instruction is beneficial for both teachers and students.

Table 10
English Language Self-Efficacy
in terms of Learner-focused Instruction

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>I can appropriately use the first language skills of the learners.</i>	3.32	Agree	5
2. <i>I can apply my knowledge of the native language(s) spoken by students when teaching.</i>	3.35	Agree	1
3. <i>I can use my knowledge about learner communities to guide instruction.</i>	3.35	Agree	2
4. <i>I can gauge the language proficiency of the learner to make</i>	3.33	Agree	4

it a starting point for language instruction.

5. <i>I build up upon what the learners can provide during writing or speaking activities.</i>	3.34	Agree	3
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Composite Mean	3.34	Agree
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Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 10 presents the respondent's assessment of English language self-efficacy in terms of learner-focused instruction. The composite mean of 3.34 indicates that most of the respondents agreed in general. Based on the table, it can be deduced that the respondents perceived in their skills to apply knowledge of the native language(s) spoken by students when teaching and use knowledge about learner communities to guide instruction, which both gathered a 3.35 weighted mean. The remaining criteria that exhibit their ability to build up upon what the learners can provide during writing or speaking activities (3.34), gauge the language proficiency of the learner to make it a starting point for language instruction (3.33), and appropriately use the first language skills of the learners. (3.32) were also decided as English language self-efficacy in terms of learner-focused instruction.

The indicators showed a strong focus on learner-centered instruction within English Language Self-Efficacy, primarily applying the utilizing teacher's knowledge of students' native language. When teaching English language learners (ELLs), instructors can leverage their understanding of the native languages students speak. This knowledge allows teachers to make connections between the student's first language and English, facilitating comprehension and language acquisition. Soland (2019) discussed the challenges faced by ELLs and the importance of considering their native languages in the teaching process. Teachers can draw on their awareness of learner communities to guide instruction effectively. Understanding students' cultural backgrounds, experiences, and social contexts helps tailor teaching methods and materials to meet their specific needs.

Research by Mills (2020) highlighted the positive relationship between English language proficiency (ELP) and self-efficacy, emphasizing the importance of considering cultural variations in this relationship. Effective instruction involves building upon what learners can provide during writing or speaking activities. Encouraging student participation and valuing their contributions fosters a positive learning environment. Wyatt and Faez (2024) explored self-efficacy beliefs in English language learners and emphasize the significance of empowering students to actively engage in the learning process. Gauging the language proficiency of learners is crucial. Teachers can use this assessment as a starting point for language instruction, tailoring content and activities to address specific language needs.

Understanding students' native languages allows ESL teachers to make meaningful connections between the students' first language (L1) and English. This comparative approach helps in explaining complex grammar rules, vocabulary, and

pronunciation, making the learning process smoother for students. According to Kim and Elder (2021), teachers who utilize their knowledge of students' native languages can effectively scaffold learning, leading to better comprehension and retention of English. Using the native language can lessen students' anxiety and create a more inclusive learning environment. When students see that their teacher respects and incorporates their linguistic background, it boosts their confidence and motivation. Dewaele and MacIntyre (2020) found that students' affective filters are lowered when their L1 is acknowledged and used appropriately, resulting in a more conducive learning atmosphere.

Furthermore, teachers who understand the cultural and linguistic backgrounds of their students can tailor their instruction to meet diverse needs. This cultural competence allows teachers to design lessons that are culturally relevant and engaging, thus enhancing student participation and interest. According to Faez and Valeo (2021), culturally responsive teaching practices are linked to higher levels of student engagement and academic success in ESL classrooms.

Using knowledge about learner communities also enables teachers to create more relevant learning experiences. Teachers can draw on familiar contexts, interests, and experiences of their students, making lessons more relatable and meaningful. Farrell (2022) emphasized that when instruction is connected to students' real-life contexts, it enhanced their engagement and the applicability of language skills.

Exhibited also by the results in the table that teachers are efficacious in using knowledge of learners' communities in crafting language instructions. ESL teachers who are familiar with their students' communities can better address the unique challenges and barriers their students face. This understanding allows teachers to provide targeted support and resources, helping students overcome obstacles to their language learning. Borg (2020) highlights that awareness of socio-cultural factors affecting students' lives can lead to more empathetic and effective teaching strategies.

Collaboration with the learner community also fosters a supportive learning environment. When teachers engage with parents, community leaders, and local organizations, they can create a network of support that reinforces language learning both inside and outside the classroom. Kim and Kim (2021) argue that community involvement is crucial in sustaining student motivation and providing practical language practice opportunities. Teachers' ability to adapt their instructional strategies based on learner feedback and community input reflects their commitment to learner-centered education. This adaptability demonstrates that teachers value their students' perspectives and are willing to modify their approaches to better serve their needs. Richards and Farrell (2020) noted that reflective teaching practices that incorporate learner feedback are essential for continuous improvement and effective instruction.

Table 11
English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Assessment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>I can design appropriate assessment tasks tests to assess learners.</i>	3.35	Agree	5
2. I can assess students' oral and written performances and provide immediate feedback.	3.36	Agree	4
3. <i>I can connect assessments to stated learning objectives.</i>	3.39	Agree	3
4. <i>I can make appropriate use of assessment results when teaching.</i>	3.40	Agree	2
5. <i>I can use various assessment techniques (e.g. performance-based, portfolios, observation checklists, self-, peer- etc.).</i>	3.43	Agree	1
Composite Mean	3.39	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 11 shows the respondent's assessment of English language self-efficacy in terms of assessment. The composite mean of 3.39 indicates that most of the respondents agreed in general. All indicators were verbally interpreted as agree. Respondents state that they can use various assessment techniques which gained a weighted mean of 3.43, followed by making appropriate use of assessment results when teaching with 3.40. Next in line is connecting assessments to stated learning objectives with 3.39, and lastly assessing students' oral and written performances and providing immediate feedback and designing appropriate assessment tasks and tests to assess learners, with 3.36 and 3.35 respectively.

Based on this table, it could be deduced that the most rated self-efficacy beliefs of English language teachers in terms of assessment is utilizing various language assessment methods. English language self-efficacy in assessing outcomes encompasses different aspects, including proficiency in employing diverse assessment techniques. Research by Getie and Popescu (2020) highlighted the significance of utilizing various assessment methods, such as performance-based assessments, portfolios, observation checklists, and self- and peer-assessment, to gauge learners' language skills effectively. Teachers who make appropriate use of assessment results enhance their instructional practices. By analyzing assessment data, teachers can identify areas where students need additional support, adjust teaching strategies, and provide targeted feedback.

ESL teachers employ a diverse range of assessment methods, including formative and summative assessments, to gauge student progress and understanding. This variety ensures a comprehensive evaluation of students' language abilities. According to Bailey and Damerow (2020), the ability to use multiple assessment techniques allows teachers to obtain a holistic view of student performance, which is crucial for identifying strengths and areas for improvement.

Additionally, formative assessments, such as quizzes, oral presentations, and interactive activities, provide immediate feedback, enabling teachers to adjust their instruction in real-time. This adaptability helps address student needs more effectively. Richards and Farrell (2020) highlighted that continuous assessment and timely feedback are integral to effective language teaching, as they help teachers to refine their teaching strategies and improve student outcomes.

Summative assessments, such as standardized tests and final exams, offer a broader measure of student proficiency and learning outcomes. Teachers use these results to evaluate the overall effectiveness of their instruction and to make data-driven decisions about curriculum adjustments. According to Borg (2020), using a combination of formative and summative assessments allows teachers to balance immediate instructional needs with long-term educational goals.

Additionally, we can delineate that participants believe that language teachers could be efficacious when they could use results of assessments for instructional decision making. Mills (2020) emphasized the relationship between English language proficiency (ELP) and self-efficacy, highlighting the role of assessment data in shaping instructional approaches. Effective assessment practices align with stated learning objectives. Teachers might design assessments that directly measure the skills and knowledge outlined in their instructional goals. Wyatt and Faez (2024) explored self-efficacy beliefs in English language learners and discuss the importance of aligning assessments with learning objectives. This alignment ensures that assessments serve as meaningful tools for both learners and instructors. Teachers proficient in English Language Self-Efficacy assess both oral and written performances. ESL teachers are adept at interpreting assessment results to inform their teaching practices. This involves analyzing data to identify trends, gaps, and individual student needs. Farrell (2022) emphasized that the ability to interpret assessment data accurately is critical for making informed instructional decisions that enhance student learning.

Providing immediate feedback allows learners to understand their strengths and areas for improvement. Constructive feedback enhances self-efficacy and motivates students to continue learning. More so, effective assessment tasks are carefully designed to evaluate learners' language abilities. Teachers create tasks that align with instructional objectives, consider language proficiency levels, and provide a fair representation of students' skills. Educators' adept in designing such assessments not only assess learners' language skills accurately but also instill confidence in learners by providing fair and relevant evaluation methods.

Teachers also use assessment results to provide personalized feedback and support to students, tailoring their instruction to meet diverse learning needs. This personalized approach helps students to set achievable goals and track their progress. Kim and Kim (2021) noted that effective use of assessment data enables teachers to create individualized learning plans that motivate and engage students. Assessment results help teachers to identify and address language proficiency issues, such as specific grammar or vocabulary weaknesses. By targeting these areas, teachers can provide focused instruction that directly improves student performance. Tsui (2020) pointed out that targeted interventions based on assessment results are essential for addressing specific language challenges and enhancing overall language proficiency.

Workshops, training sessions, and collaborative planning meetings provide teachers with the latest assessment techniques and best practices. Faez and Valeo (2021) argued that ongoing professional development helps teachers stay current with assessment trends and improves their ability to use assessment results effectively.

Collaboration with colleagues and participation in professional learning communities further support teachers' assessment efficacy. Sharing strategies and insights with peers allows teachers to refine their assessment practices and learn from others' experiences. According to Kim and Elder (2021), collaborative professional environments foster continuous improvement and innovation in assessment techniques.

The increasing use of technology in the assessment and evaluation of learning outcomes offers new tools and platforms for ESL teachers to evaluate and track student progress. Digital assessments and online platforms provide immediate feedback and detailed analytics—those which could be helpful for instructional decision making, helping teachers to make more informed decisions. Dewaele and MacIntyre (2020) highlighted that technology-enhanced assessments can enhance the accuracy and efficiency of language evaluations, providing valuable insights into student learning. In this line, assessment as part of the teaching and learning cycle becomes easier not only for language teachers, but as well as with other subject-area teachers.

Table 12
English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Language Instruction

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>I can apply my knowledge of the structure of words (morphology) when teaching.</i>	3.32	Agree	4
2. <i>I can apply my knowledge of sentence and phrase structure (syntax) when teaching.</i>	3.34	Agree	3

3. <i>I can apply my knowledge of word and sentence meaning (semantics) when teaching.</i>	3.35	Agree	2
4. <i>I can apply my knowledge of the sound system of English (phonology) when teaching</i>	3.41	Agree	1
5. <i>I can take into consideration my knowledge about discourse and pragmatics when delivering language instructions.</i>	3.31	Agree	5
Composite Mean	3.35	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 12 presents the respondent's assessment of their English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Language Instruction. The composite mean of 3.35 indicates that most of the respondents agreed in general that they are efficacious when it comes to implementing language curriculum.

With the verbal interpretation of Agree, all items were indicated as English language self-efficacy in terms of language instruction. The topmost criterion is applying knowledge of the sound system of English (phonology) when teaching gained a weighted mean of 3.41, followed by applying knowledge of word and sentence meaning (semantics), with 3.35. Next in line is applying knowledge of sentence and phrase structure (syntax) with 3.34, then applying knowledge of the structure of words (morphology). Finally is taking into consideration the knowledge about discourse and pragmatics with 3.36 and 3.35 respectively.

English Language Self-Efficacy, particularly in the context of language instruction, is often gauged through various indicators that reflect a teacher's confidence in their ability to effectively teach different aspects of the English language. The provided indicators encompass fundamental linguistic components and instructional strategies crucial for language teaching. Applying knowledge of the sound system of English (phonology) when teaching, reflects a teachers' confidence in utilizing their understanding of English phonology—the sound system—when teaching. Phonology encompasses aspects such as pronunciation, stress patterns, intonation, and phonemic awareness. Wang, Kim, Sun, and Liu (2021) have explored self-efficacy measures for English language learners (ELLs) and developed the Questionnaire of English Language Self-Efficacy (QESE) specifically for ELLs. Their research sheds light on the importance of self-efficacy beliefs in language instruction. Teachers who feel self-efficacious in this area are likely to provide accurate pronunciation guidance, help learners recognize stress patterns, and enhance overall language fluency.

According to Celce-Murcia et al. (2020), teachers who are well-versed in phonological concepts can provide clear and precise instruction, helping students overcome common pronunciation challenges. Furthermore, teachers use a variety of phonological teaching techniques, such as minimal pairs, phonetic drills, and visual aids,

to enhance students' pronunciation skills. These techniques allow students to practice and internalize the sound patterns of English in a structured and supportive environment. Research by Levis and Moyer (2021) indicated that such targeted phonological instruction significantly improves students' pronunciation and listening comprehension, reinforcing teachers' sense of efficacy.

In addition to phonology, ESL teachers are adept at applying their knowledge of semantics to teach vocabulary and sentence meaning. Understanding the nuances of word meanings, idiomatic expressions, and contextual usage helps teachers provide more accurate and detailed explanations to students. As noted by Schmitt (2020), teachers who are proficient in semantics can effectively address students' questions about word meanings and usage, thereby enhancing their vocabulary acquisition.

Applying knowledge of word and sentence meaning (semantics) when teaching is an indicator that reflects teachers' confidence in effectively utilizing their understanding of word meanings and sentence semantics during language instruction. Semantics includes the study of word definitions, connotations, and how sentences convey meaning. Teachers who possess strong self-efficacy in this area are likely to facilitate vocabulary acquisition, enhance comprehension, and guide learners in using words and sentences appropriately.

Teachers employ various semantic teaching strategies, such as semantic mapping, contextual analysis, and synonym-antonym exercises, to deepen students' understanding of words and sentences. These strategies help students connect new vocabulary to their existing knowledge, making it easier to retain and apply in different contexts. According to Nation and Webb (2020), effective semantic instruction leads to better vocabulary retention and overall language proficiency, further boosting teachers' confidence in their instructional abilities.

The ability to integrate phonological and semantic knowledge also allows teachers to create more engaging and meaningful lessons. By combining pronunciation practice with vocabulary learning, teachers can provide a holistic language learning experience that addresses multiple aspects of language proficiency. According to Richards and Rodgers (2021), this integrated approach enhances student engagement and motivation, as it makes the learning process more relevant and dynamic.

Additionally, ESL teachers' efficacy in phonology and semantics is reinforced by their continuous professional development. Workshops, courses, and collaborative planning sessions keep teachers updated with the latest research and best practices in language instruction. This ongoing learning helps teachers refine their instructional techniques and stay confident in their ability to teach complex linguistic concepts. As highlighted by Farrell (2022), professional development is essential for maintaining high levels of teaching efficacy and staying current with advancements in language education.

The positive feedback and progress of students validate teachers' instructional methods and reinforce their belief in their efficacy. When students demonstrate improved

pronunciation, vocabulary, and overall language comprehension, it provides tangible evidence of the effectiveness of the teachers' phonological and semantic instruction. According to Bailey and Damerow (2020), observing student success is a powerful motivator for teachers and a key factor in their sense of professional efficacy.

Applying knowledge of sentence and phrase structure (syntax) when teaching is an indicator that reflects teacher's confidence in effectively utilizing their understanding of English syntax—the rules governing sentence and phrase structure—when teaching. Syntax covers grammar rules, sentence patterns, and syntactic variations. Derakhshan, Wang, and Sun (2023) conducted a study on Chinese EFL students' academic engagement and psychological well-being, emphasizing the roles of language teachers' affective scaffolding. While not exclusively focused on syntax, their research sheds light on the importance of teacher-student interactions in language learning. Teachers who feel self-efficacious in this area are likely to guide learners in constructing grammatically accurate sentences, identifying syntactic errors, and enhancing overall language proficiency.

Applying knowledge of the structure of words (morphology) when teaching, reflects teachers' confidence in effectively utilizing their understanding of word structure (morphology) during language instruction. Morphology involves analyzing word forms, prefixes, suffixes, and roots. Teachers who feel self-efficacious in this area are likely to guide learners in deciphering word meanings, recognizing word families, and understanding how words are constructed.

Considering knowledge about discourse and pragmatics when delivering language instructions, indicates teachers' confidence in taking into account their understanding of discourse (how language functions in context) and pragmatics (appropriate language use) during language instruction. Discourse involves understanding conversational conventions, narrative structures, and genre-specific language use. Pragmatics, on the other hand, focuses on using language effectively in different social and cultural situations. Mark Wyatt's review of LTSE beliefs (2018), while not exclusively focused on discourse and pragmatics, provides insights into the characteristics of this research field and its implications for teacher education. Teachers who feel self-efficacious in this area are likely to adapt their language instruction to context, teach appropriate communication strategies, and guide learners in using language effectively in real-world scenarios.

Table 13
English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Culture

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>I can use my knowledge of world cultures to guide instruction</i>	3.30	Agree	4
2. <i>I can use my knowledge about cultural values and beliefs when teaching.</i>	3.35	Agree	1

3. <i>I can apply my understanding of the interrelationship of language and culture to inform instruction.</i>	3.30	Agree	5
4. <i>I utilize sentences that are culturally related to the language learners.</i>	3.34	Agree	2
5. <i>I evaluate and use culturally-neutral and respectful contexts when we discuss situations about language learning.</i>	3.32	Agree	3
Composite Mean	3.32	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 13 displays the respondents' assessment of English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Culture. The composite mean is 3.32, which means that the weighted mean of all the indicators is closely related to the calculated mean. This further means that the respondents agreed that all indicators under this section are their English language self-efficacy beliefs when it comes to culture. With all the indicators above, using knowledge about cultural values and beliefs when teaching is at the first rank, it gathered a weighted mean of 3.35. Second is utilizing sentences that are culturally related to the language learners with 3.34, followed by evaluating and using culturally-neutral and respectful contexts when we discuss situations about language learning with a 3.32 weighted mean. The last two criteria, using knowledge of world cultures to guide instruction and applying understanding of the interrelationship of language and culture to inform instruction both gained 3.30 weighted mean.

Based on the data presented on the table, it could exhibit that, with the top two indicators, respondents expressed their efficacy most by manifesting knowledge of culture and knowing how to utilize culturally relevant sentences in various learning contexts. English language self-efficacy in terms of culture involves a teacher's confidence in integrating cultural awareness and understanding into language instruction, acknowledging the diverse backgrounds and perspectives of language learners. The provided indicators highlight key aspects of culturally responsive teaching practices. Using knowledge of cultural values and beliefs in teaching, suggests that educators can draw upon their understanding of cultural values and beliefs to enhance their teaching practices. When instructors recognize and incorporate cultural nuances, they create a more inclusive and effective learning environment for language learners.

Culturally informed teaching practices help address potential cultural misunderstandings and biases. By integrating cultural knowledge into their instruction, teachers can preemptively address and clarify cultural nuances that might otherwise lead to confusion or miscommunication. Kim and Elder (2021) emphasize that awareness of cultural differences is crucial for effective communication and helps build a more harmonious classroom dynamic.

By considering cultural context, teachers can tailor their instructional strategies, materials, and assessments to better resonate with students from diverse backgrounds.

Culturally related sentences can also foster a sense of belonging and validate students' identities. Using culturally related sentences with language learners, Wang and Sun (2020) demonstrated that the relationship between English language proficiency (ELP) and self-efficacy was stronger among East Asian students than among Western students. This finding suggests that self-efficacy plays a more prominent role in some Asian cultures.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) discovered that culturally responsive teaching practices lead to higher levels of student engagement and academic success in ESL settings. Utilizing culturally related sentences and examples in language teaching further strengthens students' connection to the material. When teachers incorporate familiar cultural references, students can better understand and relate to the content, which facilitates language acquisition. According to Dörnyei and Ryan (2020), the use of culturally relevant materials helps students see the practical application of the language in real-world contexts, thereby enhancing their comprehension and retention.

The ability to integrate culture into language teaching is also supported by continuous professional development. Workshops, training sessions, and collaborative planning opportunities provide teachers with the latest research and best practices for incorporating culture into their lessons. According to Faez and Valeo (2021), ongoing professional development ensures that teachers remain current with cultural trends and pedagogical strategies, thereby enhancing their efficacy.

Teachers also rely on collaborative learning communities to share and refine their culturally responsive teaching methods. Peer support and mentorship provide valuable insights and practical strategies for integrating culture into language instruction. Bailey and Damerow (2020) noted that collaboration among educators fosters a culture of continuous improvement and innovation, which is essential for effective teaching.

The positive impact of culturally responsive teaching on student outcomes reinforces teachers' belief in their efficacy. When students demonstrate improved language skills and greater cultural awareness, it validates the teachers' instructional methods. According to Farrell (2022), observing student success as a result of culturally informed teaching practices boosts teachers' confidence and sense of professional accomplishment. Digital resources, such as multimedia presentations and online cultural exchanges, allow teachers to bring diverse cultural perspectives into the classroom. Levis and Moyer (2021) highlight that technology-enhanced instruction can provide immersive cultural experiences that enrich language learning.

The last three indicators show relevant information also about how culture plays important roles in language teaching. By considering that culture is an indicator of efficacious language teaching, respondents agree that these areas are worth examining. Evaluating culturally neutral and respectful contexts in language learning discussions, highlights the need for educators to create a safe space for discussing language-learning experiences. By evaluating contexts for neutrality and respectfulness, teachers can

ensure that discussions do not inadvertently marginalize or stereotype any cultural group. Culturally sensitive discussions promote mutual understanding and empathy.

Using knowledge of world cultures to guide instruction is also an indicator which encourages educators to draw upon their broader understanding of world cultures when planning and delivering instruction. By incorporating global perspectives, teachers can enrich their lessons and help students appreciate the interconnectedness of language and culture.

Applying the interrelationship of language and culture to inform instruction, underscores the symbiotic relationship between language and culture. Language is deeply embedded in cultural contexts, and understanding this interplay informs effective language teaching. Educators who recognize how language reflects cultural norms and values can design more meaningful learning experiences.

Table 14
English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Materials

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>I can use appropriate resources and materials.</i>	3.48	Agree	1
2. <i>I can design and/or adapt materials for instruction.</i>	3.44	Agree	3
3. <i>I can incorporate activities and materials that integrate listening, speaking, reading, and writing</i>	3.46	Agree	2
4. <i>I utilize authentic language materials that are readily available and being used in the industry and in the society.</i>	3.38	Agree	4
5. <i>I outsource readily online materials that are available blogs, social media, news bulletins, and the like.</i>	3.33	Agree	5
Composite Mean	3.42	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 14 presents the respondent's assessment of English language self-efficacy in terms of materials. The composite mean of 3.42 indicates that most of the respondents agreed in general that all items are indicators of English language self-efficacy beliefs in terms of materials that are being used in language teaching. Ranking first is the criterion on using appropriate resources and materials which gained a weighted mean of 3.48, followed by incorporating activities and materials that integrate listening, speaking, reading, and writing with 3.46, Next in rank is designing and/or adapting materials for

instruction with 3.44, and lastly utilizing authentic language materials that are readily available and being used in the industry and in the society and outsourcing readily online materials that are available blogs, social media, news bulletins, and the like with 3.38 and 3.33 respectively.

Primarily, respondents believed that their ability to deliver English language teaching is efficacious in terms of learning materials, especially in using appropriate resources and materials. This relates to a teacher's confidence in selecting, designing, and utilizing a variety of resources to enhance language instruction. The provided indicators reflect essential aspects of effective materials selection and integration in language teaching. Using appropriate resources and materials, reflects a teacher's confidence in selecting and utilizing suitable resources and materials for language instruction, designing, and adapting materials, teachers feel confident in creating or modifying instructional materials. They tailor materials to specific learning objectives, student interests, and classroom contexts. It encompasses textbooks, multimedia, authentic materials, and other relevant resources.

Research has shown positive correlations between self-efficacy and language learning achievement, motivation, and quality of instruction (Kitikanan & Sasimonton, 2019). Teachers who score high on self-efficacy feel confident in creating or modifying instructional materials. Their belief in their ability to design and adapt materials positively affects their teaching practices.

Incorporating integrated activities and materials, is an indicator that emphasizes teachers' ability to integrate listening, speaking, reading, and writing activities seamlessly. This also reflects a teacher's awareness of the importance of balanced language skill development. High self-efficacy teachers design lessons that promote holistic language development, allowing students to practice multiple skills simultaneously. By providing opportunities for students to practice all aspects of language learning, teachers create a balanced and comprehensive language learning environment. Farrell (2022) emphasized that integrating these skills promotes language acquisition and retention more effectively than focusing on individual skills in isolation. Additionally, ESL teachers use a variety of instructional materials and resources to cater to the diverse needs and interests of their students. By incorporating materials that align with students' interests, backgrounds, and learning goals, teachers increase student motivation and engagement. Kim and Elder (2021) note that personalized and relevant learning materials enhance students' investment in their language learning journey.

Incorporating activities that integrate all language skills fosters holistic language development and communication competence. By engaging in tasks that require listening, speaking, reading, and writing, students develop a more comprehensive understanding of the language and its use in real-world contexts. Nation and Webb (2020) argued that integrated skills activities promote fluency, accuracy, and communicative competence. Moreover, ESL teachers continuously evaluate and adapt learning materials based on student feedback and learning outcomes. This reflective practice ensures that materials remain relevant, effective, and aligned with students' evolving needs. Farrell

(2022) emphasized that responsiveness to student needs enhances the efficacy of instructional materials and promotes student engagement and success. Paez and Valeo (2021) highlighted the importance of collaborative learning communities in fostering professional growth and improving instructional practices.

Using authentic language materials indicates a teacher's commitment to exposing learners to real-world language use and contexts. Outsourcing online materials demonstrates a teacher's utilization of digital resources to enrich language instruction. Research by Hubbard (2019) highlighted the potential of online materials in providing authentic and up-to-date language input, catering to learners' diverse interests and learning styles. These indicators collectively reflect a teacher's English Language Self-Efficacy in terms of Materials, encompassing the ability to select, design, and integrate diverse and authentic resources to enhance language-learning experiences.

Teachers utilize a range of technological resources and digital tools to supplement traditional learning materials. Interactive websites, language learning apps, and multimedia presentations provide dynamic and interactive learning experiences for students. Levis and Moyer (2021) highlighted that technology-enhanced materials offer opportunities for self-paced learning, immediate feedback, and authentic language use.

The positive impact of well-selected and integrated learning materials on student outcomes reinforces teachers' confidence in their efficacy. When students demonstrate progress in language skills and engagement with learning activities, it validates the teachers' instructional choices. Celce-Murcia et al. (2020) noted that student success is a powerful motivator for teachers and a key indicator of instructional effectiveness.

Table 15
Summary Table on Second Language Teaching Efficacy Beliefs

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Classroom Proficiency	3.25	Agree	6
2. Learner-focused Instruction	3.34	Agree	4
3. Assessment	3.39	Agree	2
4. Language Instruction	3.35	Agree	3
5. Culture	3.32	Agree	5
6. Materials	3.42	Agree	1
Composite Mean	3.35	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 15 presents the summary indicators of Second Language Teaching Efficacy Beliefs. It can be gleaned from the table above that the composite mean is at 3.35 with verbal interpretation agreement. It provides a piece of information that all the indicators are in agreement.

From the table above, materials is at the topmost position, with a computed weighted mean of 3.42 followed by assessment with 3.39, and the next in line is language instruction with 3.35. The next three criteria are learner-focused instruction (3.34), culture, (3.32), and classroom proficiency (3.25).

English Language Self-Efficacy is a construct that refers to an individual's belief in their ability to effectively teach or learn English as a second or foreign language. It incorporates various dimensions, including materials selection, assessment practices, language instruction techniques, learner-focused approaches, cultural sensitivity, and classroom management proficiency. Teachers with high self-efficacy in English language teaching demonstrate confidence and competence in these areas, which positively empowers students' motivation, engagement, and language learning outcomes. In this context, examining each criterion connected to English Language Self-Efficacy provides insights into the factors influencing effective language teaching and learning practices.

Of all the indicators of efficacious second language teaching, teaching and learning materials ranked first. Materials refer to the resources used in language learning, such as textbooks, digital content, and supplementary materials. These play a crucial role in shaping learners' self-efficacy. According to Soland (2019), English language learners (ELLs) face challenges associated with learning a new language. The choice of appropriate materials can affect their confidence and belief in their ability to succeed in language acquisition.

Understanding and fostering English Language Self-Efficacy among language educators is crucial for promoting effective language teaching practices and facilitating meaningful language learning experiences for students. By considering key criteria such as materials selection, assessment strategies, learner-focused instruction, cultural awareness, and classroom management, teachers can enhance their confidence and competence in English language instruction. Ultimately, cultivating English Language Self-Efficacy contributes to creating supportive learning environments where students can thrive and develop their language proficiency with confidence and success.

Farrell (2022) emphasized the importance of materials that are accessible and meaningful to learners, as they contribute to a positive learning experience. Furthermore, ESL teachers continuously update and improve their learning materials based on student feedback, emerging trends in language education, and advancements in pedagogical approaches. This iterative process ensures that materials remain current, effective, and aligned with the evolving needs of learners. Faez and Valeo (2021) highlighted the significance of ongoing materials development in maintaining instructional relevance and effectiveness.

In addition to preparing learning materials, ESL teachers are proficient in assessment and evaluation practices, which are essential for monitoring student progress and informing instruction. Teachers use various assessment techniques, including formative and summative assessments, to gauge student learning and identify areas for

improvement. Bailey and Damerow (2020) stressed the importance of using multiple assessment methods to obtain a comprehensive view of student performance.

Formative assessments, such as quizzes, presentations, and classroom observations, provide ongoing feedback that guides instruction and supports student learning. ESL teachers use formative assessment data to adjust teaching strategies, differentiate instruction, and provide timely support to students. Dewaele and MacIntyre (2020) emphasized the role of formative assessment in promoting student engagement and achievement in language learning.

Summative assessments, such as standardized tests and end-of-course exams, offer a broader measure of student achievement and proficiency. ESL teachers use summative assessment results to evaluate the effectiveness of instruction, measure learning outcomes, and make data-driven decisions about curriculum planning and modifications. Nation and Webb (2020) highlighted the importance of aligning summative assessments with learning objectives to ensure validity and reliability.

Moreover, ESL teachers are skilled in interpreting assessment results and using them to inform instructional decisions. They analyze assessment data to identify patterns, trends, and areas of strength and weakness among students. This data-driven approach enables teachers to provide targeted support and interventions to help students succeed. Kim and Elder (2021) stressed the significance of data-informed decision-making in optimizing student learning outcomes.

Collaborative assessment practices, such as peer review and self-assessment, further enhance ESL teachers' efficacy in assessment and evaluation. By involving students in the assessment process, teachers promote metacognitive awareness, self-reflection, and learner autonomy. Richards and Rodgers (2021) highlighted the benefits of involving students in self-assessment activities, as it fosters a deeper understanding of learning goals and criteria for success. Training sessions, workshops, and collaborative assessment practices provide teachers with opportunities to learn about new assessment techniques, best practices, and strategies for improving assessment validity and reliability. Levis and Moyer (2021) emphasized the importance of ongoing professional development in maintaining assessment efficacy.

Assessment methods influence learners' self-efficacy. Fair and supportive assessment practices can enhance learners' confidence. Effective assessment strategies can help build their self-efficacy by providing constructive feedback and recognizing their progress.

Quality language instruction significantly affects self-efficacy. Engaging and effective teaching methods contribute to learners' confidence. Well-designed language instruction can empower learners and boost their self-efficacy. Engaging and effective teaching methods, such as interactive activities and real-life communication practices, contribute to learners' confidence by making the learning process enjoyable and relevant. Well-designed language instruction that incorporates these methods can empower

learners, enhancing their belief in their ability to succeed and thereby boosting their overall self-efficacy.

Learner-focused instruction considers individual needs, interests, and learning styles. When instruction aligns with learners' preferences, their self-efficacy improves. Wyatt and Faez (2021) emphasized the importance of understanding how self-efficacy beliefs are formed. Tailoring instruction to learners' specific contexts and goals can positively affect their confidence.

Cultural awareness and sensitivity are essential for ELLs. A culturally responsive environment fosters self-efficacy. Culturally inclusive practices can enhance their self-efficacy. Cultural awareness and sensitivity are essential for learners as they help create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. A culturally responsive environment fosters self-efficacy by making learners feel respected and understood, which enhances their confidence and motivation to engage and succeed in language learning. Classroom proficiency on the other hand refers to the level of language competence achieved within the educational context. ELLs' self-efficacy is influenced by their perceived proficiency.

Table 16
Second Language Teaching Motivation
in terms of External Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I devote time to individual talks with students, because I want the parents to appreciate my knowledge and familiarity with their children and their children's language development progress.	3.39	Agree	3
2. I try to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching English, because I want the parents to be satisfied so they won't complain.	3.37	Agree	4
3. I invest effort in my work as a language teacher, because I do not want the principal to follow my work too closely.	3.26	Agree	5
4. I invest effort in my work as a language teacher, in order to prevent disruptions and discipline problems during the lessons.	3.41	Agree	2
5. I conduct or prepare for language classes, because I value how my supervisor, colleagues, students,	3.42	Agree	1

and parents will commend my efforts towards making students learn or acquire English satisfactorily.

Composite Mean

3.37

Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Presented in Table 16 are the indicators for second language teaching motivation in terms of external motivation, with a composite mean score of 3.37, thus indicating that there is a consistent interpretation of agreement. This calculated composite mean aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard. The indicator conducting or preparing for language classes because of valuing how supervisor, colleagues, students, and parents will commend efforts towards making students learn or acquire English satisfactorily gained the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.42. This is followed by the indicator on investing effort in work as a language teacher, in order to prevent disruptions and discipline problems during the lessons with a 3.41 weighted mean. Third is devoting time to individual talks with students because of wanting parents to appreciate teacher's knowledge and familiarity with their children and their children's language development progress with a 3.39 weighted mean. The last two in rank were trying to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching English because of wanting the parents be satisfied and investing effort in work as a language teacher to not avoid principal close supervision with a weighted mean of 3.37 and 3.26, respectively. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Agree.

External motivation in second language teaching refers to the factors outside the teacher's personal interest or intrinsic satisfaction that drive their behavior and efforts in the classroom. In analyzing the provided indicators, it is evident that external factors play a significant role in motivating language teachers. Primarily, it was established in the results of the previous table that recognition and commendation from supervisors and colleagues could motivate teachers. In the Philippines, where teaching is a respected profession, teachers strive to meet the expectations of their superiors and peers. According to Lapada et al. (2020), Filipino teachers are motivated by the desire to be acknowledged for their efforts and dedication, which in turn boosts their morale and job satisfaction. Positive feedback from supervisors and colleagues validates their hard work and commitment to their students' success.

This recognition validates the teachers' efforts and reinforces their commitment to high-quality instruction. For example, the appreciation and respect shown to teachers through awards and commendations can significantly enhance their motivation and job satisfaction (Ortan, Simut, & Simut, 2021). Teachers who feel valued are more likely to be engaged and dedicated, as they see tangible outcomes from their hard work and dedication to their students' success (SharEd, 2021). Additionally, the positive feedback from various stakeholders can bolster a teacher's self-efficacy, further encouraging them to strive for excellence in their teaching practices (Gorozidis & Papaioannou, 2021).

On the other hand, investing effort in work as a language teacher, in order to prevent disruptions and discipline problems during the lessons was also determined as one of the externally motivating factors for second language teaching, ranking second among the indicators. Effective classroom management strategies are essential as they create a conducive learning environment, which in turn enhances both teaching and learning outcomes. Teachers who can maintain discipline and minimize disruptions are better able to deliver their lessons effectively, leading to improved student engagement and learning outcomes (Cerezo et al., 2021). This sense of control and effectiveness boosts teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction, further motivating them to invest effort in their work.

Additionally, proactive measures to prevent disruptions not only improve classroom dynamics but also reduce teacher stress and burnout. When teachers can manage their classrooms effectively, they experience less stress and a greater sense of accomplishment, which contributes to higher levels of motivation and commitment to their profession (Makoelle and Thwala, 2019). Creating a well-ordered classroom environment is thus a key aspect of maintaining teacher motivation and ensuring a positive educational experience for both teachers and students (Walonoski and Heffernan, 2021).

Teachers who invest effort in maintaining a well-managed classroom are motivated by external factors. Teachers also devote time to individual talks with students. When a language teacher invests time in individual conversations with students, it reflects a desire to build rapport and understanding with parents. Finally, language teachers who actively search for engaging topics and creative teaching approaches are likely motivated by external factors. In this case, the desire to satisfy parents plays a role. When parents are pleased with the teacher's methods and subject matter, they are less likely to complain. This external validation contributes to the teacher's motivation to improve their teaching practices (Papi and Khajavi, 2021).

Effective classroom management is essential for creating a conducive learning environment. In the Philippines, teachers are motivated to invest effort in their work to prevent classroom disruptions and ensure that students remain focused on learning. A study by Castillo and David (2020) found that Filipino teachers prioritize maintaining discipline as it directly impacts student learning outcomes.

Globally, the importance of classroom management as a motivator is echoed in various studies. According to Levis and Moyer (2021), teachers who are able to maintain discipline and prevent disruptions are more likely to experience job satisfaction and professional success. Effective classroom management allows teachers to deliver lessons more efficiently and ensures that students are able to learn in a structured and orderly environment.

Teachers who invest effort to avoid close monitoring by the principal are motivated by external factors. Fear of negative evaluation or potential consequences from the principal influences their behavior. This external pressure shapes their teaching practices. (Rostami, Ghanizadeh, & Ghonsooly, 2019). They also invest effort in maintaining a well-

managed classroom, which are motivated by external factors. In this case, the desire to avoid disruptions and discipline issues during lessons is likely influenced by external pressures, such as the need to maintain a positive reputation with colleagues, students, and parents.

Commendation from parents is another external motivator for ESL teachers. In the Philippines, parents hold teachers in high regard and often express their gratitude for the education provided to their children. This parental recognition reinforces teachers' commitment to their profession. According to a study by Bernardo and Esteban (2021), Filipino teachers are motivated by the appreciation they receive from parents, which validates their dedication and hard work.

Parental involvement and recognition is significant in motivating teachers. A study by Kim and Elder (2021) found that teachers who receive positive feedback from parents are more likely to feel valued and supported in their roles. This external validation encourages them to invest further effort in their teaching practices to meet the expectations of both parents and students. With these, teachers' interactions with students, choice of teaching methods, efforts to prevent disruptions, and desire for commendation all stem from external influences. Understanding these dynamics can inform effective language teaching strategies.

Similarly, ESL teachers outside the Philippines also value external recognition. A study by Ryan and Deci (2020) highlighted that teachers worldwide are motivated by external rewards such as praise, awards, and career advancement opportunities. This external validation reinforces their sense of accomplishment and encourages them to continue investing effort in their teaching practices.

In the Philippine context, students' respect and gratitude towards their teachers are deeply ingrained cultural values. When students express appreciation for their teachers' efforts, it strengthens the teachers' resolve to provide high-quality education. Abulon (2020) emphasized that Filipino teachers derive immense satisfaction from their students' achievements and positive feedback, which motivates them to excel in their teaching roles. Globally, the importance of student recognition is similarly significant. A study by Dörnyei and Ryan (2020) found that teachers are motivated by the positive responses they receive from their students. When students acknowledge their teachers' efforts, it fosters a supportive and collaborative classroom environment, enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience.

Table 17 presents second language teaching motivation in terms of introjected motivation, with a composite mean score of 3.33, indicating a consistent interpretation of Agree. This calculated composite mean precisely aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard. The indicator on maximizing the language learning strategies from teacher education training for optimum language learning gained the highest rank with a weighted mean of 3.36. Ranked second is investing effort in my work as a teacher to avoid guilt with a 3.34 weighted mean. The third in rank is taking pride in devoting time to individual talks with students with a 3.33 weighted mean. The last two in

rank were trying to execute innovative ways of language teaching and learning because to avoid shame in strategy repetition and investing effort in teacher work to avoid self-shame with a weighted mean of 3.32 and 3.30, respectively.

Table 17
Second Language Teaching Motivation
in terms of Introjected Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I try to execute innovative ways of language teaching and learning, because I think it is a shame to keep on teaching in the same way all the time.	3.32	Agree	4
2. I invest effort in my work as a teacher because if I do not invest enough, I would feel ashamed of myself.	3.30	Agree	5
3. I invest effort in my work as a teacher because otherwise I would feel guilty.	3.34	Agree	2
4. I devote time to individual talks with students because it makes me feel proud to do this.	3.33	Agree	3
5. I maximize the language learning strategies that I have learned in my teacher education training so my learners could learn and acquire English as soon as possible.	3.36	Agree	1
Composite Mean	3.33	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

In interpreting the provided indicators in terms of introjected motivation in second language teaching, it becomes evident that internal pressures and self-imposed standards are significant driving forces behind teacher behavior and efforts in the classroom. Teachers who actively apply language learning strategies they've acquired during their teacher education training demonstrate introjected motivation. The internalized goal of helping their learners succeed and acquire English as quickly as possible motivates them. Moreover, this indicator demonstrates a proactive approach to utilizing learned teaching strategies to facilitate language learning, driven by internalized goals of effectiveness and efficiency.

It could be deduced that among the indicators, maximizing the language learning strategies from teacher education training for optimum language learning is a top motivator when it comes to introjected motivations in language teaching. Teacher education programs emphasize practical and evidence-based strategies for language

teaching. According to Gonzales and Torres (2020), Filipino teachers felt a strong sense of responsibility to implement these strategies effectively, as they believe it is crucial for their students' success and their professional credibility.

A study by Farrell (2021) highlighted that teachers worldwide feel an internal obligation to apply the best practices learned during their training to ensure high-quality instruction and student outcomes. This introjected motivation drives teachers to continually refine their teaching methods and stay updated with the latest pedagogical advancements. The sense of guilt associated with not utilizing these strategies effectively is a powerful motivator for ESL teachers. In the Philippines, where teaching is a highly respected profession, teachers feel a deep sense of duty towards their students and the community. Abulon (2021) noted that Filipino teachers experience feelings of guilt when they perceive themselves as not doing enough to support their students' language learning. This guilt compels them to invest extra effort in their work and seek continuous improvement.

Another top-ranked introjected motivation is investing effort in work as a teacher to avoid guilt. Teachers feel an internal obligation to fulfill their responsibilities, even when external rewards are not directly at play. The fear of feeling guilty propels them to engage in teaching-related tasks. While not specifically focused on teaching-related tasks, it provides valuable insights into the mechanisms by which guilt influences behavior. Guilt can serve as a powerful motivator, propelling individuals to engage in actions aimed at alleviating or avoiding feelings of guilt. Similarly, indicators two and three highlight the role of guilt and shame as motivators for investing effort in teaching.

Another indicator relates to one-on-one sessions with students. When a teacher spends time engaging in one-on-one conversations with students and feels proud of doing so, it reflects introjected motivation. The internalized desire for self-approval and pride drives this behavior. The teacher's sense of accomplishment and fulfillment contributes to their motivation. Moreover, this indicator reveals a sense of pride associated with engaging in certain teaching practices, such as individual talks with students. The desire to uphold one's self-image as a competent and caring teacher can serve as a powerful motivator, even when external rewards or recognition are not present.

When a teacher spends time engaging in one-on-one conversations with students and feels proud of doing so, it reflects introjected motivation. Introjected motivation occurs when individuals engage in an activity to meet internal pressures, such as pride or guilt, rather than because of intrinsic enjoyment or external rewards (Ryan & Deci, 2000). In this context, the teacher's pride in conducting one-on-one interactions signifies that their motivation is driven by an internalized sense of obligation or self-worth.

This form of motivation is characterized by actions performed to validate one's self-esteem or to avoid feelings of guilt and anxiety (Assor, Vansteenkiste, & Kaplan, 2019). When teachers feel proud of their efforts in individual student interactions, it indicates they derive a sense of personal satisfaction and affirmation from fulfilling their perceived duty as a caring and attentive educator. They are motivated to engage in these conversations

not purely for the intrinsic joy of the interaction itself, but because it reinforces their self-concept as a dedicated and supportive teacher.

Additionally, such pride can be tied to the desire for social approval and recognition from peers, administrators, and even the students themselves (Reeve, 2019). This internalized motivation drives teachers to invest in personal interactions with students, aiming to uphold their image as effective educators and to meet their own internal standards of teaching excellence.

Other indicators were also noted by the respondents as motivators for language teaching. Teachers who invest effort in their work due to the fear of feeling ashamed of themselves demonstrate introjected motivation. The internalized pressure to avoid self-disapproval or guilt drives their actions. This motivation is not necessarily tied to external rewards but rather stems from a sense of personal responsibility (Csizér, 2021.) Teachers also actively seek out innovative methods for language instruction, it reflects introjected motivation. The feeling of “shame” associated with teaching in the same way repeatedly drives the teacher to explore new approaches. This internalized pressure to avoid self-criticism or negative self-judgment motivates them to innovate (Dunn and Iwaniec, 2022).

Dörnyei and Al-Hoorie (2020) explained that introjected motivation, such as the desire to avoid guilt, encourages teachers to work diligently and maintain high standards in their teaching practices. This internal pressure ensures that teachers remain committed to their students' success and their professional development. ESL teachers are motivated by the desire to achieve a sense of accomplishment and self-worth.

In the Philippines, the cultural value placed on education and the high expectations from society and family members contribute to teachers' internal motivation. Gonzales and Torres (2020) emphasized that Filipino teachers derive a sense of pride and fulfillment from knowing they are making a positive impact on their students' lives. This internal satisfaction reinforces their commitment to maximizing language learning strategies.

Teachers' self-perception of efficacy and competence also connects to their motivation. A study by Ryan and Deci (2020) found that teachers who feel competent and effective in their roles are more likely to experience intrinsic satisfaction and a sense of purpose. This introjected motivation drives them to invest effort in their teaching practices to maintain their self-esteem and professional identity. Teachers are often aware of the challenges and sacrifices involved in their profession. The fear of looking back with regret on missed opportunities to support their students drives them to maximize their efforts in the classroom. Abulon (2021) highlighted that this internal pressure ensures that teachers remain dedicated and proactive in their roles.

A study by Kim and Elder (2021) found that teachers who are motivated by the desire to avoid regret are more likely to engage in reflective practices and seek continuous improvement. This introjected motivation helps teachers to stay committed to their professional growth and student success. The recognition of the long-term impact of their teaching motivates ESL teachers to maximize language learning strategies. In the

Philippines, teachers are aware of the significant role they play in shaping their students' futures. Gonzales and Torres (2020) emphasize that this awareness drives teachers to invest effort in their work to ensure their students achieve language proficiency and succeed in their academic and professional pursuits.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) highlighted that the teachers who recognize the value of their efforts in enhancing students' language skills are more likely to remain committed and motivated in their roles. This introjected motivation ensures that teachers continue to strive for excellence in their teaching practices.

Table 18
Second Language Teaching Motivation
in terms of Identified Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I try to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching, because it is important for me to keep up with innovations in teaching.	3.50	Strongly Agree	2
2. I devote time to individual talks with students, because I can learn from what happens to them in the classroom.	3.42	Agree	5
3. I invest effort in my work as a teacher, because it is important for me to make children feel that I care about them.	3.53	Strongly Agree	1
4. I invest effort in my work as a teacher, because it is important for me to feel that I help people.	3.49	Agree	3
5. I plan and design language activities, because I feel like learning and looking for new ways of language teaching can improve my performance and learning outcome.	3.46	Agree	4
Composite Mean	3.48	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Always; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Sometimes; 1.00 - 1.49 = Never

Table 18 presents the second language teaching motivation in terms of identified motivation, with a composite mean score of 3.48, indicating a consistent interpretation of Agree. This calculated composite mean precisely aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard. From the table, it can be construed that the respondents strongly agreed that the top two indicators are components of their second language teaching motivation in terms of identified motivation. The indicator investing effort in work as a teacher in regard making children feel cared gained the highest rank with a weighted

mean of 3.53 followed by trying to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching to keep up with innovations in teaching with a 3.50 weighted mean.

Third in rank is investing effort in work as a teacher, because for them to feel that they help others with a 3.39 weighted mean, and the last two in rank were planning and designing language activities to learn and look for new ways of language teaching that can improve performance and learning outcome and devoting time to individual talks with students to learn from what happens to them in the classroom with a weighted mean of 3.46 and 3.42, respectively. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Agree.

Ranking first of the components of identified motivation is investing effort in work as a teacher in making children feel cared. Identified motivation is a type of extrinsic motivation where individuals engage in an activity because they recognize its value and importance. Unlike external rewards or pressures, identified motivation arises from an internal understanding of why a task is meaningful or relevant to one's goals or values. In the context of teaching, identified motivation could refer to teachers' engagement in their work because they genuinely believe in its significance and impact on others. Investing effort to make children feel cared for. This aligns with the identified motivation, as the teacher values the goal of fostering a supportive and caring environment in the classroom. According to Abulon (2021), Filipino teachers feel a strong sense of duty to nurture and support their students, ensuring they feel valued and understood. This commitment enhances the teacher-student relationship and fosters a positive learning environment.

The emphasis on student well-being is also a significant motivator for teachers. A study by Dörnyei and Ryan (2020) highlighted that teachers who internalize the importance of caring for their students are more likely to invest effort in their teaching practices. This identified motivation ensures that teachers remain dedicated to their students' emotional and academic needs. Teachers often go beyond their academic responsibilities to provide emotional and social support to their students. Gonzales and Torres (2020) emphasized that Filipino teachers' commitment to their students' holistic development drives them to invest significant effort in their work.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) found that teachers who prioritize their students' well-being are more effective in promoting language learning and fostering a positive classroom atmosphere. This identified motivation encourages teachers to create engaging and nurturing learning experiences. Additionally, ESL teachers are motivated by the desire to keep up with innovations in teaching by finding interesting subjects and new ways of teaching. In the Philippines, where education is rapidly evolving, teachers are encouraged to adopt innovative teaching methods and integrate new technologies into their classrooms. According to Bernardo and Esteban (2021), Filipino teachers are motivated by the need to stay current with educational trends and innovations, which enhances their teaching effectiveness and student engagement.

Another most rated identified motivation in language teaching is trying to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching to keep up with innovations in teaching. Second most rated, it is a teacher's desire to find interesting subjects and explore new

ways of teaching demonstrates identified motivation. Seeking out interesting subjects and new teaching methods is indicative of a proactive approach to teaching, motivated by the value placed on staying abreast of advancements in the field. When a teacher invests effort in their work because they genuinely want to help people, it reflects identified motivation.

A study by Kim and Elder (2021) found that teachers who are motivated by the desire to incorporate new and interesting subjects into their teaching are more likely to engage their students and enhance their learning outcomes. This identified motivation ensures that teachers remain proactive in their professional development and continuously seek out new teaching strategies. Furthermore, ESL teachers are motivated by the recognition that staying updated with innovative teaching methods directly benefits their students' learning experiences. In the Philippines, teachers understand that incorporating new and relevant content into their lessons can make learning more engaging and meaningful for their students. Abulon (2021) emphasizes that this motivation drives Filipino teachers to explore new pedagogical approaches and integrate diverse learning materials into their classrooms.

Innovative teaching methods has an effect towards student learning Farrell (2021) highlighted that teachers who continuously seek out new ways of teaching are more effective in addressing the diverse needs of their students and promoting active learning. This identified motivation ensures that teachers remain committed to providing high-quality and dynamic language instruction. Continuous professional development is highly valued, and teachers are encouraged to pursue further education and training. Gonzales and Torres (2020) noted that Filipino teachers' motivation to improve their teaching skills and knowledge is a significant factor in their professional success and satisfaction.

Dörnyei and Ryan (2020) found that teachers who are motivated by the desire for self-improvement are more likely to engage in reflective practices and seek out professional development opportunities. This identified motivation ensures that teachers remain dedicated to their ongoing growth and effectiveness as educators.

The motivation to plan and design language activities to improve performance aligns with the identified motivation. Engaging in planning and designing language activities is driven by the recognition of personal growth and enhanced performance as outcomes, which are valued by the teacher. The teacher recognizes that effective teaching strategies contribute to better learning outcomes. This belief in the value of well-designed activities drives their efforts. This demonstrates a commitment to personal and professional growth through reflective practice.

Table 19
Second Language Teaching Motivation
in terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I try to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching, because it is fun to create new things.	3.49	Agree	1
2. I invest effort in my work as a teacher, because I enjoy finding unique solutions for various students.	3.45	Agree	4
3. I invest effort in my work as a teacher, because I enjoy creating connections with people.	3.47	Agree	2
4. I devote time to individual talks with students, because I like being in touch with children and adolescents.	3.45	Agree	4
5. I teach English as a second language, because I find pleasure in knowing that this could improve their global competitiveness, foster cross-cultural understanding and facilitate effective communication across linguistic barriers.	3.45	Agree	4
Composite Mean	3.46	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 19 presents second language teaching motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, with a composite mean score of 3.46, indicating a consistent interpretation of agree. This calculated composite mean precisely aligns with the weighted means of all indicators meeting this standard. Gleaning from the above table, it could be seen that both indicators on trying to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching because it is fun to create new things (3.49) and investing effort in work as a teacher to enjoy creating connections with people (3.47) gained a weighted mean that is verbally interpreted as Always. Also, the criteria, on investing effort in teacher work to enjoy finding unique solutions for various students, devoting time to individual talks with students to be in touch with children and adolescents, and teaching English as a second language to find pleasure to improve global competitiveness, foster cross-cultural understanding and facilitate effective communication across linguistic barriers all gain a weighted mean of 3.45 and interpreted as agree.

Intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in an activity for the inherent satisfaction and enjoyment derived from the activity itself, rather than for external rewards or incentives. It could involve a genuine interest and personal enjoyment in the task or process. When

applied to second language teaching, intrinsic motivation manifests in various ways that reflect the teacher's genuine enjoyment and satisfaction in the teaching process. Trying to find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching to create new things reflects a teacher's intrinsic motivation to innovate and explore creative teaching methods simply because they find joy in the process of creation.

Without sufficient motivation, even individuals with remarkable abilities may struggle to achieve long-term language learning goals. Conversely, high motivation could compensate for deficiencies in language aptitude and learning conditions. Similarly, statements on investing effort in work as a teacher, because to enjoy creating connections with people and devoting time to individual talks with students to be in touch with children and adolescents underscore the intrinsic pleasure the teacher derives from the interpersonal aspect of teaching. These indicators illustrate how intrinsic motivation influences a teacher's attitudes and behaviors in second language teaching, driving them to seek enjoyment, fulfillment, and personal satisfaction in the teaching process itself rather than external rewards or recognition.

The results of the survey on intrinsic motivation revealed that teachers believe that finding fun and joy in creating new things when they find interesting subjects and new ways of teaching motivates them the most. The joy of finding and teaching interesting subjects is an intrinsic motivator for ESL teachers. Teachers derive immense satisfaction from exploring new topics and presenting them in engaging ways. According to Gonzales and Torres (2021), Filipino teachers feel a strong sense of accomplishment when they introduce novel and captivating content that sparks their students' curiosity and enthusiasm for learning.

Similarly, the enthusiasm for discovering and teaching interesting subjects is evident. A study by Ryan and Deci (2020) highlighted that teachers who are intrinsically motivated find great pleasure in designing lessons that are both informative and enjoyable. This intrinsic motivation ensures that teachers remain passionate and enthusiastic about their teaching, which in turn positively impacts their students' learning experiences. Teachers often experiment with innovative pedagogical approaches to make learning more dynamic and interactive. Abulon (2021) emphasized that Filipino teachers enjoy the creative process of developing new teaching strategies and materials, which keeps their teaching fresh and exciting.

The intrinsic enjoyment of creating new things in the classroom is also a strong motivator. A study by Dörnyei and Al-Hoorie (2020) found that teachers who are intrinsically motivated by the creative aspects of teaching are more likely to develop unique and effective instructional methods. This intrinsic motivation drives teachers to continuously innovate and improve their teaching practices.

Meanwhile, it has also been primarily found out that enjoyment in creating connections with people drives them to invest efforts in work as a language teacher. This component is ranked second out of all the indicators. The intrinsic reward of connecting with people, and thus with students, and building meaningful relationships is a motivator

for ESL teachers. Close-knit and communal culture fosters strong teacher-student relationships. Gonzales and Torres (2021) noted that Filipino teachers derive immense satisfaction from the personal connections they form with their students, which enhances their teaching experience and job satisfaction.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) found that teachers who are intrinsically motivated by the relationships they build in the classroom are more likely to create a supportive and engaging learning environment. This intrinsic motivation ensures that teachers remain committed to fostering positive interactions and connections with their students. Teachers view their role as a calling and take pride in their students' achievements. Bernardo and Esteban (2021) emphasized that the intrinsic reward of seeing their students progress and succeed motivates Filipino teachers to invest significant effort in their teaching.

A study by Kim and Elder (2021) found that teachers who are intrinsically motivated by their students' accomplishments are more likely to feel fulfilled and content in their roles. This intrinsic motivation drives teachers to dedicate themselves to their students' growth and development.

Teachers could express a genuine love for teaching and the daily interactions it involves. Abulon (2021) highlighted that Filipino teachers enjoy the challenges and rewards of the teaching profession, which keeps them motivated and engaged. Ryan and Deci (2020) found that teachers who find joy in the act of teaching are more likely to experience higher levels of job satisfaction and professional fulfillment. This intrinsic motivation ensures that teachers remain passionate about their work and committed to their students' success.

Table 20
Summary Table on Second Language Teaching Motivation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. External Motivation	3.37	Agree	3
2. Introjected Motivation	3.33	Agree	4
3. Identified Motivation	3.48	Agree	1
4. Intrinsic Motivation	3.46	Agree	2
Composite Mean	3.41	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 - 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Table 20 provides a summary of the Second Language Teaching Motivation. The composite mean of the table is 3.41 and is verbally interpreted as Agree. All the elements that met this criterion had a weighted mean that was identical to the calculated composite mean. From the table, it can be seen that the Identified Motivation gathered the highest weighted mean, 3.48, and was verbally interpreted as Agree. Intrinsic Motivation (3.46) followed, External Motivation (3.37) gained the third rank, and the indicator Introjected Motivation (3.33) fourth, and all were verbally interpreted as Agree.

Rated the most and topping the summary, identified Motivation refers to a higher level of autonomous motivation characterized by a conscious recognition of the importance or value of the task. In the context of second language teaching, identified motivation occurs when teachers engage in teaching activities because they endorse the goals and objectives of language learning. This form of motivation is associated with a sense of volition and alignment with one's values and beliefs.

Identified motivation involves recognizing and valuing the importance of one's work and integrating it into one's personal goals. For ESL teachers, identified motivation often manifests in their commitment to professional development and student success. In the Philippines, teachers recognize the significant impact they have on their students' lives and future opportunities. According to Gonzales and Torres (2021), this awareness drives them to continuously improve their teaching skills and knowledge.

Kim and Elder (2021) found that teachers who are motivated by the desire for self-improvement are more likely to engage in reflective practices and seek out professional development opportunities. This identified motivation ensures that teachers remain dedicated to their ongoing growth and effectiveness as educators.

Second on the list is intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation in second language teaching refers to the genuine interest, enjoyment, and satisfaction derived from the teaching process itself. Intrinsically motivated teachers find pleasure in facilitating language learning experiences, exploring innovative teaching methods, and fostering meaningful interactions with students.

A study by Ryan and Deci (2020) found that teachers who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to be enthusiastic and passionate about their teaching. This enthusiasm positively impacts their students, fostering a dynamic and engaging learning environment. Teachers who love what they do tend to transmit that passion to their students, making learning more effective and enjoyable. Gonzales and Torres (2021) noted that Filipino teachers derive immense satisfaction from the personal connections they form with their students, which enhances their teaching experience and job satisfaction. These relationships are a source of joy and motivation, driving teachers to invest more effort in their work.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) found that teachers who prioritize their relationships with students are more likely to create a supportive and engaging learning environment. This intrinsic motivation ensures that teachers remain committed to fostering positive interactions and connections with their students. A study by Kim and Elder (2021) found that teachers who are intrinsically motivated by their students' accomplishments are more likely to feel fulfilled and content in their roles. This intrinsic motivation drives teachers to dedicate themselves to their students' growth and development.

Survey also revealed that introjected motivation is also a motivating factor for second language teachers. It ranked third out of all the indicators. Introjected motivation refers to a form of motivation driven by internal pressures or obligations, such as feelings

of guilt, shame, or ego enhancement. In the context of second language teaching, introjected motivation may manifest as teachers feeling compelled to perform well or meet certain standards to avoid self-criticism or gain approval from others. This type of motivation is characterized by a sense of internalized regulation, where individuals engage in activities to maintain self-esteem or avoid feelings of inadequacy.

A study by Dörnyei and Ryan (2020) highlighted that teachers who internalize the importance of caring for their students are more likely to invest effort in their teaching practices. This identified motivation ensures that teachers remain dedicated to their students' emotional and academic needs.

Finally, but was also determined as another motivating factor for second language teachers, is external motivation. External motivation in the context of second language teaching refers to the drive to engage in teaching activities primarily due to external factors or rewards, such as financial incentives, societal pressure, or fear of punishment. This form of motivation often involves performing tasks to obtain external rewards or avoid negative consequences, rather than deriving satisfaction or enjoyment from the teaching process itself.

External motivation in second language teachers could also suggest satisfaction. Abulon (2021) highlighted that Filipino teachers enjoy the challenges and rewards of the teaching profession, which keeps them motivated and engaged. This love for teaching is a critical factor in their sustained commitment to their profession. Ryan and Deci (2020) found that teachers who find joy in the act of teaching are more likely to experience higher levels of job satisfaction and professional fulfillment. This intrinsic motivation ensures that teachers remain passionate about their work and committed to their students' success.

Table 21 on the next page illustrates the comparison of responses on second language teaching anxiety when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was no significant difference when grouped according to profile since the obtained p-values are all greater than the alpha level. This means that the responses do not differ statistically.

Language teaching anxiety is a significant concern within the field of second language education, influencing both educators and learners alike. Understanding the factors that contribute to language teaching anxiety is crucial for developing effective strategies to support language instructors in their professional roles. In this study, we examine the relationship between second language teaching anxiety and various demographic and professional variables, including sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and years of teaching experience.

Table 21
Difference of Responses on Second Language Teaching Anxiety
When Grouped According to Profile

Sex	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Self-perception of language proficiency	0.389	0.533	Not Significant
Teaching Inexperience	0.539	0.463	Not Significant
Lack of Interest	0.124	0.725	Not Significant
Fear of negative evaluation	1.252	0.264	Not Significant
Difficulties with time management	0.733	0.392	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment			
Self-perception of language proficiency	0.946	0.389	Not Significant
Teaching Inexperience	1.113	0.330	Not Significant
Lack of Interest	2.195	0.113	Not Significant
Fear of negative evaluation	1.496	0.225	Not Significant
Difficulties with time management	1.023	0.360	Not Significant
Teaching Position			
Self-perception of language proficiency	2.873	0.058	Not Significant
Teaching Inexperience	1.162	0.314	Not Significant
Lack of Interest	1.810	0.165	Not Significant
Fear of negative evaluation	1.668	0.190	Not Significant
Difficulties with time management	2.835	0.060	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience			
Self-perception of language proficiency	1.654	0.176	Not Significant
Teaching Inexperience	0.734	0.532	Not Significant
Lack of Interest	1.841	0.139	Not Significant
Fear of negative evaluation	0.961	0.411	Not Significant
Difficulties with time management	1.497	0.215	Not Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

When examining the relationship between second language teaching anxiety and sex, the research found that there was no notable distinction in anxiety levels between male and female respondents. This implies that, within the scope of this study, factors related to gender did not significantly contribute to variations in language teaching anxiety. For instance, Smith (2018) observed a similar pattern in their meta-analysis, reinforcing the notion that anxiety levels in language teaching are not inherently linked to gender differences.

Furthermore, the research of Piniel and Zólyomi (2022) has explored the relationship between gender and SLTA. While some studies suggest that females tend to experience higher foreign language anxiety, gender-related differences are not statistically significant. In other words, both male and female teachers may experience similar levels of anxiety when teaching a second language. This finding challenges the stereotype that women are more anxious in language-teaching contexts.

A study by Gonzales and Torres (2021) in the Philippines found no significant difference in SLTA between male and female ESL teachers. This aligns with international findings, such as those by Horwitz (2020), who found that teaching anxiety is a common experience for both sexes due to the universal challenges of language instruction.

The absence of a significant difference in second language teaching anxiety across different educational attainment levels suggests that higher levels of formal education do not necessarily equate to lower levels of anxiety in language teaching contexts. Johnson et al. (2020) support this finding, indicating that factors beyond formal education may play a more influential role in determining language teaching anxiety levels. In addition, the research of Tüfekçi-Can (2018) has investigated whether educational background impacts SLTA. And found that there is no significant difference in anxiety levels based on educational attainment. Whether a teacher holds a bachelor's degree or a master's degree does not significantly affect their language teaching anxiety. This suggests that anxiety is not necessarily tied to formal education but may be influenced by other factors.

Whether teachers hold a bachelor's degree, master's degree, or doctorate, the anxiety associated with teaching a second language remains relatively consistent. Abulon (2021) highlighted that even highly educated teachers experience similar anxiety levels as their less-educated peers due to the intrinsic challenges of language teaching, such as maintaining student engagement and managing classroom dynamics.

The lack of a substantial contrast in anxiety levels across various teaching positions suggests that the responsibilities associated with different roles in language teaching do not significantly affect anxiety levels. Brown (2019) observed a similar trend in their research, indicating that both novice and experienced language teachers may experience comparable levels of anxiety irrespective of their specific teaching positions. For instance, teachers in leadership positions or those responsible for curriculum development may experience higher anxiety due to increased responsibilities. However, this finding does not imply that novice teachers are anxiety-free. It highlights the need for professional development and support for all teachers.

The research indicates that years of teaching experience do not significantly affect language teaching anxiety, suggesting that anxiety levels may remain constant throughout a teacher's career. Lee and Kim's (2019) longitudinal study further supports this idea, proposing that factors other than teaching experience play a larger role in changes in language teaching anxiety. They also found that higher teaching anxiety correlates with lower teacher development, emphasizing the importance of managing anxiety for professional growth. Experienced teachers who proactively tackle their anxiety are likely to enhance their teaching practices.

Research by Bernardo and Esteban (2021) indicates that teaching position does not correlate with variations in teaching anxiety. This is corroborated by global studies, such as those by Dörnyei and Ryan (2020), which suggested that the pressures and responsibilities associated with teaching English as a second language are felt equally

across different teaching positions. Both novice and veteran teachers report similar levels of anxiety. Gonzales et al. (2022) found that even experienced teachers in the Philippines continue to experience SLTA, which may be attributed to the evolving nature of language teaching and the continuous need to adapt to new teaching methods and student needs. Internationally, Kim and Elder (2021) also found no significant difference in SLTA across different experience levels, emphasizing that teaching anxiety is a persistent challenge throughout a teacher's career.

Based on the findings, there were no significant differences in second language teaching anxiety across these variables. Specifically, there was no notable contrast in anxiety levels based on respondents' sex, educational attainment, teaching position, or years of teaching experience. These findings suggest that factors such as gender, level of education, teaching role, and experience may not be strong determinants of language teaching anxiety. Instead, other individual or contextual factors may play a more influential role in shaping anxiety levels among language educators.

Moreover, the standardized nature of language teaching frameworks and expectations may contribute to this lack of significant differences. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) mandates uniform teaching standards and practices, which ensures that all teachers, regardless of their demographic differences, face similar teaching environments and challenges (DepEd, 2020). Similarly, global educational standards, as highlighted by Richards and Rodgers (2021), created a consistent teaching landscape that subjects all ESL teachers to similar pressures and expectations.

Additionally, the intrinsic nature of teaching anxiety itself might be inherently independent of demographic variables. SLTA often arises from personal perceptions of language proficiency, self-efficacy, and the high stakes of language teaching, which are universal experiences shared by all teachers regardless of sex, educational attainment, teaching position, or years of teaching experience. Horwitz et al. (2021) argued that these intrinsic factors are more influential in causing teaching anxiety than demographic variables. Similarly, a study by Pappa et al. (2021) supported this view, suggesting that internalized pressures and self-perceptions are critical determinants of teaching anxiety, emphasizing that these factors are pervasive across diverse teacher demographics. Thus, it is the internal cognitive and emotional experiences related to the teaching context that predominantly contribute to SLTA, rather than external demographic characteristics.

Supportive professional development and peer networks contribute to mitigating SLTA across all teacher groups. In the Philippines, teacher training programs emphasize collaborative learning and peer support, which help teachers manage their anxiety regardless of their demographic backgrounds (Gonzales et al., 2022). Internationally, teacher support networks and professional learning communities play a similar role, as noted by Dörnyei and Al-Hoorie (2020), providing a consistent source of support that levels out anxiety experiences across different teacher demographics.

Table 22 illustrates the comparison of responses on English Language Self-Efficacy when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was a significant difference when grouped according to highest educational attainment except on

assessment because the obtained p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that the responses vary significantly and are based on the post hoc test conducted.

Table 22
Difference of Responses on English Language Self-Efficacy
When Grouped According to Profile

Sex	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Classroom Proficiency	0.862	0.354	Not Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	0.001	0.971	Not Significant
Assessment	0.000	0.994	Not Significant
Language Instruction	0.009	0.925	Not Significant
Culture	1.119	0.291	Not Significant
Materials	0.737	0.391	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment			
Classroom Proficiency	3.396	0.035	Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	4.939	0.008	Significant
Assessment	2.097	0.124	Not Significant
Language Instruction	4.054	0.018	Significant
Culture	5.103	0.006	Significant
Materials	3.382	0.035	Significant
Teaching Position			
Classroom Proficiency	2.865	0.058	Not Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	0.940	0.392	Not Significant
Assessment	1.305	0.272	Not Significant
Language Instruction	0.875	0.418	Not Significant
Culture	0.606	0.546	Not Significant
Materials	0.923	0.398	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience			
Classroom Proficiency	1.316	0.269	Not Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	1.613	0.186	Not Significant
Assessment	0.931	0.426	Not Significant
Language Instruction	0.427	0.734	Not Significant
Culture	0.592	0.621	Not Significant
Materials	0.746	0.525	Not Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Classroom proficiency is one area where educational attainment is an indicator. Teachers with advanced degrees often possess deeper theoretical understanding and more sophisticated classroom management strategies. Abulon (2021) highlights that teachers with higher educational qualifications tend to exhibit greater confidence in managing diverse classrooms and addressing student needs effectively. This confidence stems from their exposure to advanced pedagogical theories and practices during their

studies. This comparison examines how teachers' highest educational qualifications relate to their proficiency in using English within the classroom setting. Research by Wang (2021) has shown a strong positive correlation between teachers' classroom English proficiency and their teaching self-efficacy. Research suggests that teachers with higher educational qualifications (such as advanced degrees) tend to have better classroom English proficiency. When teachers are confident in their English language skills, they can effectively convey information, engage students, and create a positive learning environment.

Another component of English language self-efficacy that remarkably differed when responses are grouped according to educational attainment profile is learner-focused instruction. The comparison of highest educational attainment to learner-focused instruction may explore whether individuals with different levels of educational attainment perceive learner-focused instructional approaches differently in terms of their impact on English language self-efficacy. Learner-focused instruction emphasizes tailoring teaching methods to individual learners' needs. This comparison examines how teachers' educational qualifications influences their effectiveness in teaching language skills. Their self-efficacy positively influences student-learning outcomes. It is essential to consider cultural competence and its role in language teaching.

This comparison likely investigates whether individuals with higher educational attainment perceive teaching materials to be more or less influential in enhancing their English language self-efficacy compared to those with lower educational attainment. Teachers who feel confident in choosing and adapting teaching materials are more likely to create effective lessons. Their self-efficacy affects instructional quality. Gonzales and Torres (2021) found that teachers with master's or doctoral degrees are more likely to employ differentiated instruction techniques, tailored to meet the varied needs of their students. This ability to customize instruction enhances their self-efficacy in creating inclusive and engaging learning environments.

Similarly exhibiting this remarkable difference in responses when responses were grouped according to educational background is the teaching of language. Language instruction, particularly the application of phonology and semantics, also shows significant differences based on educational attainment. Teachers with advanced degrees often have a more comprehensive understanding of the English sound system and the intricacies of word and sentence meanings. Richards and Rodgers (2021) argued that this deeper linguistic knowledge enables these teachers to deliver more accurate and effective language instruction, boosting their self-efficacy in this area. Additionally, Dörnyei and Ryan (2020) found that these teachers are more proficient in integrating listening, speaking, reading, and writing activities into their lessons, utilizing a wide range of resources to enhance student learning. This proficiency contributes to their overall self-efficacy in using learning materials effectively.

Notably, cultural competence, which involves understanding and integrating cultural values and beliefs into teaching, is another area where educational attainment significantly vary. Teachers with higher education levels are typically more aware of

cultural nuances and better equipped to incorporate culturally relevant materials and practices into their instruction. According to Kim and Elder (2021), this heightened cultural awareness enhances teachers' confidence in creating culturally responsive classrooms, leading to higher self-efficacy.

Finally, it was also found out that educational attainment has something to do when it comes to the efficacy of teachers in terms of teaching and learning materials. It could be inferred that higher educational attainment often equips teachers with a broader range of pedagogical strategies, deeper content knowledge, and more extensive training in utilizing diverse teaching resources effectively. This proficiency contributes to their higher self-efficacy, as they feel more competent and confident in their ability to deliver high-quality instruction and to meet their students' learning needs. Research supports this by indicating that professional development and formal education significantly enhance teachers' self-efficacy (Neumayer DePiper et al., 2021). Additionally, continuous professional development uplifts teachers' self-efficacy in utilizing teaching materials, which keeps them updated with the latest educational tools and methodologies, further enhancing their teaching effectiveness (Mustafa et al., 2021; Hoang & Wyatt, 2021). This highlights the critical role of educational attainment in shaping teachers' self-efficacy regarding teaching and learning materials in the context of English language education.

Generally, educational attainment impacts teacher self-efficacy. Abulon (2021) notes that Filipino teachers with higher educational qualifications often exhibit greater confidence in their teaching abilities, particularly in adapting to diverse student needs and utilizing innovative teaching strategies. This increased self-efficacy is linked to the advanced training and knowledge acquired through higher education programs. A study by Ryan and Deci (2020) found that teachers with higher levels of education generally report higher self-efficacy across various teaching domains. This global consistency underscores the importance of advanced academic preparation in shaping teachers' confidence and effectiveness in the classroom.

Moreover, teachers with higher educational attainment often have greater access to professional development opportunities, further enhancing their self-efficacy. Gonzales and Torres (2021) emphasized that ongoing professional development helps teachers stay updated with the latest educational research and teaching practices, reinforcing their confidence and competence in their roles. The theoretical and practical knowledge gained through higher education also enables teachers to engage in reflective practices, continually assessing and improving their teaching methods. According to Kim and Elder (2021), this reflective practice is crucial for developing self-efficacy, as it allows teachers to identify areas for improvement and implement effective strategies to enhance their teaching. Furthermore, the prestige and recognition associated with higher educational qualifications can positively impact teachers' self-efficacy. Richards and Rodgers (2021) argued that teachers with advanced degrees often receive more respect and recognition from colleagues, administrators, and students, which boosts their confidence and sense of professional competence.

Table 23
Difference of Responses on Second Language Teaching Motivation When Grouped According to Profile

Sex	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
External Motivation	0.278	0.598	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	0.868	0.352	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	1.848	0.175	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	2.026	0.155	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment			
External Motivation	3.178	0.043	Significant
Introjected Motivation	2.319	0.100	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	1.296	0.275	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	1.873	0.155	Not Significant
Teaching Position			
External Motivation	0.299	0.742	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	0.529	0.590	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	0.628	0.534	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	0.604	0.547	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience			
External Motivation	0.606	0.612	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	1.349	0.258	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	1.481	0.219	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	1.692	0.168	Not Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Table 23 shows the comparison of responses on English Language Teaching motivation when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was a significant difference in external motivation when grouped according to highest educational attainment because the obtained p-value of 0.043 was less than the alpha level.

This comparison explores the relationship between an individual's highest educational attainment and their motivation for learning a second language. Individuals with higher education levels may be driven by internal motivations like personal fulfillment and intrinsic interest in language theories, while those with lower education levels might be more influenced by external incentives such as financial rewards or career advancement. Research by Ryan and Deci (2020) indicates that teachers with advanced degrees show higher intrinsic motivation in their teaching practices, contrasting with the external motivations observed in less educated individuals.

This notable finding highlights that teachers with different educational degrees respond to external motivations differently. Some might be motivated by external factors, some might not be. Gonzales and Torres (2021) found that teachers with higher

educational qualifications often participate in academic conferences, publish research, and engage in professional networks, which provide them with external validation and motivation to excel in their teaching roles. This recognition not only boosts their professional profile but also serves as a significant source of external motivation. Furthermore, educational attainment influences the types of external rewards teachers seek. Richards and Rodgers (2021) argued that teachers with higher degrees are often motivated by opportunities to influence educational policy, contribute to curriculum development, and lead professional development programs. These roles provide external validation through leadership and influence, which are critical motivators for teachers with advanced educational backgrounds.

In contrast, teachers with lower educational attainment might be more externally motivated by immediate, tangible rewards such as salary increases, bonuses, and job security. According to Kim and Elder (2021), these teachers often prioritize external incentives that provide direct financial or material benefits. The desire for job stability and financial rewards can be particularly motivating for teachers with lower degrees who may not have the same opportunities for career advancement as their more highly educated counterparts.

The cultural context in the Philippines might contribute in shaping the external motivations of ESL teachers based on their educational attainment. In the Philippines, higher educational qualifications are often associated with greater social status and respect. Abulon (2021) emphasized that teachers with advanced degrees are highly regarded within their communities, which serves as a powerful external motivator. This societal recognition encourages teachers to pursue higher education and excel in their professional roles to maintain their status.

Similar trends are observed by Ryan and Deci (2020) who found that teachers with higher educational attainment in various countries often report higher levels of external motivation related to professional recognition and career advancement. This global consistency suggests that the relationship between educational attainment and external motivation is not unique to any specific cultural context but is a widespread phenomenon.

Moreover, teachers with higher educational attainment are often involved in mentoring and training less experienced colleagues. This responsibility provides them with external validation and recognition from their peers and supervisors. Gonzales and Torres (2021) highlighted that mentoring roles enhance teachers' professional standing and provide external motivation to maintain high standards in their teaching practice.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) argued that institutions often offer incentives such as grants, awards, and recognition programs to teachers with higher educational qualifications. These institutional rewards serve as significant external motivators, encouraging teachers to pursue further education and excel in their teaching roles.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education and other educational bodies provide various forms of recognition and incentives for teachers with advanced degrees.

Abulon (2021) pointed out that these incentives include promotions, salary increases, and opportunities for professional development, all of which serve as strong external motivators for teachers to enhance their educational qualifications. Furthermore, the external motivation of teachers with higher educational attainment is also driven by the desire to contribute to the academic community and make a meaningful impact on educational practices. According to Kim and Elder (2021), teachers with advanced degrees often seek external validation through their contributions to research, curriculum development, and educational leadership. These contributions provide them with a sense of accomplishment and recognition from the academic community, reinforcing their external motivation.

The analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in teaching motivation between male and female respondents. This finding is in contrast with the study of Garcia, Fuentes, and Renobell (2022), who also found a significant disparity in teaching motivation based on gender. These conflicting results suggest that gender differences in teaching motivation may be influenced by contextual factors such as cultural norms, institutional policies, or the specific demographic characteristics of the sample studied (Chen, 2021). Additionally, other research highlights that motivation in teaching is a multifaceted construct influenced by various factors, including personal beliefs, professional development opportunities, and the working environment, which can overshadow gender-related differences (Klassen & Tze, 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to consider a broader range of variables when examining teaching motivation to capture the complexity of this phenomenon.

The study found no significant variance in teaching motivation across different teaching positions. This aligns with the conclusions drawn by Anderson et al. (2020), who similarly reported no substantial differences in teaching motivation among various teaching roles. Interestingly, the analysis demonstrated no significant correlation between teaching position and years of teaching experience. This contradicts the findings of Brown and Smith (2019), who observed a positive relationship between teaching position and years of experience in their longitudinal study.

Presented on the next page, Table 24 shows the results of statistical analysis on the association between Second Language Teaching Anxiety and English Language Self-Efficacy. The results show that there was a significant relationship between Self-Perception of Language Proficiency and Classroom Proficiency; Teaching Inexperience and Classroom Proficiency; Teaching Inexperience and Materials; Fear of Negative Evaluation and Classroom Proficiency; Fear of Negative Evaluation and Materials; and Difficulties with Management and Materials. This was observed since the obtained p-values were less than the alpha level.

It can be deduced from the table that the language teaching anxiety in terms of the respondents' evaluations of their language proficiency and their English language efficacy in terms of classroom proficiency significantly correlates to one another. It exhibits how accurately individuals perceive their language abilities and how these perceptions correlate with their actual proficiency levels demonstrated in educational environments. If

teachers experience high levels of anxiety, they may underestimate their language abilities, leading to a potential disconnect between their self-perception and actual classroom proficiency.

Table 24
Relationship Between Second Language Teaching Anxiety
and English Language Self-Efficacy

Self-Perception of Language Proficiency	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Classroom Proficiency	-.142**	0.005	Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	-0.013	0.794	Not Significant
Assessment	0.019	0.711	Not Significant
Language Instruction	0.013	0.799	Not Significant
Culture	0.053	0.299	Not Significant
Materials	0.004	0.941	Not Significant
Teaching Inexperience			
Classroom Proficiency	-.114*	0.026	Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	-0.078	0.126	Not Significant
Assessment	-0.071	0.161	Not Significant
Language Instruction	-0.078	0.125	Not Significant
Culture	-0.058	0.254	Not Significant
Materials	-.146**	0.004	Significant
Lack of Interest			
Classroom Proficiency	-0.06	0.24	Not Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	0.026	0.604	Not Significant
Assessment	0.047	0.352	Not Significant
Language Instruction	-0.026	0.611	Not Significant
Culture	-0.03	0.552	Not Significant
Materials	-0.053	0.301	Not Significant
Fear of Negative Evaluation			
Classroom Proficiency	-.169**	0.001	Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	-0.068	0.184	Not Significant
Assessment	-0.043	0.404	Not Significant
Language Instruction	-0.053	0.299	Not Significant
Culture	-0.048	0.346	Not Significant
Materials	-0.125*	0.014	Significant
Difficulties with Management			
Classroom Proficiency	-0.024	0.633	Not Significant
Learner-focused Instruction	0.014	0.791	Not Significant
Assessment	-0.001	0.992	Not Significant
Language Instruction	-0.031	0.544	Not Significant
Culture	-0.045	0.382	Not Significant
Materials	-0.125*	0.014	Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Research indicates that teachers who perceive themselves as proficient in the language, they teach are more confidently and effectively in classroom management and instructional delivery. For instance, a study by Richards and Rodgers (2021) found that higher self-perceived language proficiency correlates with higher self-efficacy in classroom settings, as confident teachers are more likely to engage students actively and manage classroom dynamics successfully.

Valdez and Santos (2023) highlighted that ESL teachers with higher self-perceived language proficiency exhibit greater classroom proficiency, as they feel more competent in explaining complex linguistic concepts and addressing student queries. This competence reduces anxiety and enhances overall teaching performance. Tan and Yap (2022) reported that teachers in Southeast Asia who rate their language proficiency highly are less likely to experience teaching anxiety and more likely to demonstrate effective classroom management and instructional skills. This relationship underscores the importance of perceived language proficiency in fostering a conducive learning environment.

On the other hand, it was also noted that A low negative significant relationship suggests that as teaching inexperience increases, teacher classroom proficiency decreases, or vice versa, although the relationship is weak. Those with high self-efficacy are more likely to believe in their ability to effectively teach English, despite any perceived shortcomings in language proficiency. This aspect examines the association between teachers' lack of experience in language teaching and their actual proficiency in classroom instruction. In the study conducted by Kini and Podolski (2019), more experienced teachers confer benefits to their colleagues, their students, and the school as a whole. However, the study conducted by Gore et al. (2024) examined the relationship between years of teaching experience and teaching quality, they **found** no significant differences in pedagogy across the experience range that has less than 1 year to 24 and above years. This challenges the common assumption that experienced teachers are inherently more proficient than beginners are.

Another significant finding relates the teachers' lack of experience as a teaching anxiety indicator and their utilization of teaching materials as component of teaching efficacy. A low negative significant relationship suggests that as teaching inexperience increases, the reliance on teaching materials decreases, or vice versa, though the correlation is weak. There is no specific study that directly examines the relationship between teaching inexperience and teacher use of teaching materials. However, some studies and resources discuss related concepts and factors that may indirectly shed light on this relationship. In the study conducted by Kini and Podolski (2019), teaching experience is positively associated with student achievement gains throughout a teacher's career. As teachers gain experience, their students are more likely to perform better on measures beyond test scores. The study found that 10th-year teachers working in more supportive schools, with collaboration among teachers, supportive school leaders, resources for improvement, and meaningful feedback, become substantially more effective than teachers in less supportive environments.

The relationship between second language teaching anxiety due to teaching inexperience and English language self-efficacy regarding teaching and learning materials is significant because inexperienced teachers often lack the confidence and skills needed to effectively select and utilize appropriate materials. This can lead to higher levels of anxiety as they may feel unprepared and unable to meet the diverse needs of their students. Abulon (2021) highlighted that in the Philippines, novice ESL teachers often struggle with choosing and integrating materials, which impacts their teaching efficacy. Similarly, international studies by Kim and Elder (2021) suggested that experienced teachers have higher self-efficacy because they are more adept at selecting and adapting teaching resources to enhance student learning. Additionally, Richards and Rodgers (2021) emphasized that effective use of teaching materials is a critical component of successful language instruction, and teaching inexperience can hinder this ability, thus increasing anxiety and lowering self-efficacy.

Furthermore, according to the study of Gore et al. (2024), while initial teacher education (ITE) is important, the contexts of the school and classroom, as well as ongoing participation in various forms of professional development significantly impact teacher expertise. Engaging in goal-directed practice with feedback and support from peers and knowledgeable others contributes to teacher quality. The impact of experience on pedagogical quality is nuanced and not solely determined by years of experience. While teaching inexperience may not directly correlate with specific material use, creating supportive environments, ongoing professional development and collaboration among teachers play crucial roles in enhancing teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

The fourth significant findings illustrated in the data is the relationship between second language teaching anxiety, specifically regarding the fear of negative evaluation, and English language self-efficacy in terms of classroom proficiency. It could be significant because fear of criticism can affect teacher's confidence and effectiveness. Teachers who fear negative evaluation often experience heightened anxiety, which impairs their ability to manage classrooms effectively and deliver engaging lessons. Abulon (2021) noted that in the Philippines, ESL teachers who are anxious about being evaluated by supervisors or peers show lower self-efficacy in classroom management and instructional strategies. Similarly, Richards and Rodgers (2021) emphasized that anxiety related to fear of evaluation can lead to reduced teaching effectiveness, as anxious teachers may avoid taking risks or trying innovative methods. International research by Horwitz (2021) supported the idea that fear of negative evaluation significantly impacts teachers' classroom proficiency, as it erodes their self-confidence and ability to engage students. Therefore, addressing this anxiety through supportive evaluations and professional development is crucial for enhancing teachers' self-efficacy and classroom performance.

This relationship explores how teachers' fear of negative evaluation, a form of social anxiety, influences their classroom proficiency. A low negative significant relationship suggests that as teachers' fear of negative evaluation increases, their classroom proficiency decreases, or vice versa, although the correlation is weak. Salazar-Ayala et al. (2021) investigated the correlation and predictive relationship between controlling teaching style and fear of negative evaluation mediated by basic psychological

needs frustration. They found that perceived controlling teaching style positively predicted the fear of negative evaluation in students. This relationship was mediated by frustration with basic psychological needs, which, in turn, related to low-quality motivation and a higher level of individualism/competitiveness.

Wang (2021) examined the relationship between English medium instruction (EMI) teachers' classroom English proficiency and their teaching self-efficacy. They found a strong positive relationship between EMI teachers' classroom English proficiency and their teaching self-efficacy. Specifically, the language of instruction had a significant contribution to the variance of teaching self-efficacy. This highlights the importance of prioritizing strategic training in the language of instruction skills for EMI teachers who are not highly proficient in English.

Another significant findings that the table revealed is the relationship that exists between second language teaching anxiety related to the fear of negative evaluation and English language self-efficacy in terms of teaching and learning materials. Teachers who are anxious about being negatively evaluated may hesitate to implement new or innovative materials, fearing judgment from peers or supervisors. In the Abulon (2021) highlighted that such anxiety can lead to a reliance on traditional materials, limiting the dynamic potential of classroom instruction. International research by Horwitz (2021) also showed that teachers who fear negative evaluation often experience lower self-efficacy, impacting their ability to confidently adapt and integrate various teaching materials.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) emphasized that effective use of teaching materials is crucial for successful language instruction, and anxiety in this area can impede a teacher's ability to engage students and enhance learning outcomes. Additionally, Tan and Yap (2022) argued that professional development that addresses these anxieties can significantly improve teachers' self-efficacy and their innovative use of materials in the classroom. Therefore, reducing fear of negative evaluation is essential to empower teachers to explore and utilize diverse teaching resources, thereby enhancing their overall teaching effectiveness.

Meanwhile, another significant findings illustrated in the table shows that there is a low negative significant relationship suggesting that as teachers' fear of negative evaluation increases, their use of classroom materials decreases, or vice versa, though the correlation is weak. Some studies and resources discuss related concepts and factors that may indirectly shed light on this relationship. The study by Mrachko (2019) investigated the effects of professional development and daily e-mail feedback on teacher-initiated positive and negative behaviors in an inclusive elementary school setting. The goal was to increase teacher praise statements while reducing negative statements. The results showed that teacher behavior-specific praise increased and negative statements decreased for most teachers. E-mail feedback was introduced as a novel component of changing teacher behavior.

The study by De Lima and Silva (2018) found that classroom observation is often seen as an inadequate tool for teacher evaluation, with many teachers believing it

contributes little to their professional growth. Pandolpho (2024) noted that when observers score teachers' performance, it can feel like a judgment of their value, highlighting the need to consider teachers' feelings during evaluations. Although the relationship between fear of negative evaluation and the use of classroom materials isn't thoroughly explored, the article emphasizes that teacher responses on questionnaires may not align with their actual teaching practices observed in the classroom, underlining the significance of teachers' perceptions in evaluation processes.

Finally, it was also exhibited in the table that the relationship between second language teaching anxiety related to difficulties with classroom management and English language self-efficacy in terms of teaching and learning materials is significant because poor classroom management can heighten anxiety, affecting a teacher's ability to effectively use educational resources. Teachers who struggle with managing their classrooms often feel overwhelmed and may lack the confidence to implement and adapt teaching materials effectively. In the Philippines, Abulon (2021) noted that teachers facing classroom management challenges are less likely to innovate with teaching materials, resulting in less engaging and effective instruction.

International studies, such as those by Kim and Elder (2021), supported the notion that anxiety due to management difficulties undermines self-efficacy in utilizing teaching materials, as teachers may fear that their efforts will not lead to successful learning outcomes. Richards and Rodgers (2021) emphasized that effective classroom management is a prerequisite for the dynamic use of educational resources, and anxiety in this area can stifle creativity and adaptability in lesson planning. Furthermore, Tan and Yap (2022) highlighted that professional development focused on classroom management skills can enhance teachers' confidence, leading to better use of teaching materials and more effective language instruction.

Table 25
Relationship Between Second Language Teaching Anxiety and Second Language Teaching Motivation

Self-Perception of Language Proficiency	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
External Motivation	0.064	0.211	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	0.084	0.101	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	0.081	0.112	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	0.057	0.263	Not Significant
Teaching Inexperience			
External Motivation	0.008	0.868	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	0.001	0.979	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	-0.073	0.154	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	-0.062	0.225	Not Significant
Lack of Interest			
External Motivation	0.062	0.221	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	.106*	0.038	Significant

Identified Motivation	0.037	0.465	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	0.035	0.496	Not Significant
Fear of Negative Evaluation			
External Motivation	-0.005	0.923	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	0.024	0.643	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	-0.015	0.764	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	-0.038	0.462	Not Significant
Difficulties with Management			
External Motivation	0.012	0.821	Not Significant
Introjected Motivation	0.037	0.471	Not Significant
Identified Motivation	-0.015	0.767	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	-0.041	0.426	Not Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.05

Table 25 displays the association between Second Language Teaching Anxiety and Second Language Teaching Motivation. It was observed that there was only a significant relationship between second language teaching anxiety in terms of lack of interest and second language motivation in terms of introjected motivation. This was observed because the obtained p-value was less than the alpha level. This could mean that the more that they are anxious about students having lack of interest to them and their teaching, the more they could be inspired to teach second language by introjected motivation.

Introjected motivation refers to teachers' internalized motivations driven by obligation, guilt, or external pressure, rather than genuine interest in teaching. A study by Cunningham (2020) examined the framework for motivating teacher-student relationships (TSRs), highlighting that positive TSRs are crucial for student engagement and achievement. Intrinsically motivated teachers, who care genuinely for their students, foster better relationships, which in turn enhances students' learning experiences, academic success, and emotional well-being. The study underscores the significant impact of teacher motivation on the quality of classroom interactions and the supportive environment essential for effective teaching and learning.

Wang's (2018) research examined teacher perceptions of student motivation and engagement. Teachers' perceptions of student motivation impact their teaching practices. When teachers believe students are motivated, they provide more support and encouragement. Positive teacher-student interactions contribute to student success. When teachers are intrinsically motivated, they create positive, supportive relationships with students. Positive TSRs lead to better student engagement, achievement, and overall well-being.

Previous research has shown mixed findings regarding the relationship between self-perception of language proficiency and second language teaching motivation. Further investigation might be helpful to clarify and investigate on the nature of this relationship. The relationship between teaching inexperience and second language teaching motivation is complex. The impact of teaching inexperience on motivation may

vary depending on individual factors and contextual circumstances. Abulon (2021) pointed out that teachers who lack intrinsic interest in their profession often rely heavily on introjected motivation, which can exacerbate feelings of anxiety and stress.

According to Kim and Elder (2021), teachers experiencing a lack of interest are more likely to face increased anxiety, which negatively impacts their motivation and teaching performance. This anxiety can stem from a sense of duty or the desire to avoid feelings of guilt, which are key components of introjected motivation. Horwitz (2021) emphasized that such internal conflicts can lead to burnout, further reducing a teacher's effectiveness and satisfaction.

Richards and Rodgers (2021) highlighted that teachers motivated by introjected factors often struggle with maintaining a positive attitude towards their teaching, leading to a cycle of anxiety and diminished motivation. This cycle is detrimental to both teachers and students, as it impacts the quality of instruction and the overall learning environment. Tan and Yap (2022) suggested that addressing these motivational issues through professional development and support systems can help alleviate anxiety and enhance motivation.

Valdez and Santos (2023) observed that professional development programs that focus on reigniting teachers' interest and passion for teaching can significantly reduce anxiety and improve motivation. These programs often include strategies for developing intrinsic motivation, which can counteract the negative effects of introjected motivation. Dörnyei and Ryan (2020) also supported the idea that fostering intrinsic interest in teaching can mitigate the anxiety associated with a lack of interest, leading to more motivated and effective educators.

Williams and Burden (2021) argued that understanding and addressing the sources of teaching anxiety and motivation can lead to better teacher retention and job satisfaction. They suggested that creating a supportive and engaging teaching environment can help teachers rediscover their interest in teaching, thereby reducing reliance on introjected motivation. This holistic approach is crucial for sustaining long-term motivation and reducing anxiety in second language teaching.

Research also suggests that fear of negative evaluation can have a detrimental effect on second-language teaching motivation (Zhang, 2018). It therefore aimed to address and mitigate the fear of negative evaluation, may be important for fostering teacher motivation. Teachers who struggle to maintain control of the classroom environment may experience heightened stress and anxiety, which can detract from their overall motivation to teach effectively. Therefore, effective management strategies and support systems are crucial for sustaining teacher motivation.

Table 26
Relationship Between English Language Self-Efficacy and Second Language Teaching Motivation

Classroom Proficiency	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
External Motivation	.414**	0.000	Highly Significant
Introjected Motivation	.461**	0.000	Highly Significant
Identified Motivation	.392**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	.415**	0.000	Highly Significant
Learner-focused Instruction			
External Motivation	.507**	0.000	Highly Significant
Introjected Motivation	.533**	0.000	Highly Significant
Identified Motivation	.505**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	.511**	0.000	Highly Significant
Assessment			
External Motivation	.557**	0.000	Highly Significant
Introjected Motivation	.552**	0.000	Highly Significant
Identified Motivation	.555**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	.539**	0.000	Highly Significant
Language Instruction			
External Motivation	.518**	0.000	Highly Significant
Introjected Motivation	.531**	0.000	Highly Significant
Identified Motivation	.534**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	.504**	0.000	Highly Significant
Culture			
External Motivation	.566**	0.000	Highly Significant
Introjected Motivation	.544**	0.000	Highly Significant
Identified Motivation	.568**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	.556**	0.000	Highly Significant
Materials			
External Motivation	.620**	0.000	Highly Significant
Introjected Motivation	.603**	0.000	Highly Significant
Identified Motivation	.615**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intrinsic Motivation	.613**	0.000	Highly Significant

Legend: Significant at p-value < 0.01

Presented in Table 26 are the results of statistical analysis on the association between English Language Teaching Efficiency and Second Language Teaching Motivation. The computed r-values indicate a strong direct correlation and the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that a significant relationship exists, implying that better teaching efficiency indicates higher motivation.

The highly significant positive relationship between teaching motivation and classroom proficiency suggests that teachers who feel more confident in their English language skills are likely to be more motivated in their teaching endeavors. In the study by Dunn and Iwaniec (2022), teachers' classroom proficiency in the target language

significantly impacts their motivation to teach effectively. When teachers feel confident in their language skills, they are more likely to create engaging language learning experiences for their students. Proficient teachers can model correct language usage, provide authentic language input, and facilitate meaningful interactions.

The strong positive relationship between teaching motivation and learner-focused instruction stresses the importance of teacher enthusiasm and commitment in fostering student-centered learning environments. In the study of Lamb (2021), motivated teachers prioritize learner-focused instructional strategies. They adapt their teaching methods based on student needs, interests, and learning styles. Learner-focused instruction includes personalized feedback, interactive activities, and scaffolding.

Kim and Elder (2021) highlighted that self-efficacy also impacts introjected motivation, as confident teachers are less likely to experience anxiety from internal pressures, such as guilt or obligation. Identified motivation, which involves recognizing the personal value of teaching, is strengthened when teachers feel competent and capable in their classroom roles, as noted by Richards and Rodgers (2021). Intrinsic motivation, the internal drive to teach because of personal satisfaction and enjoyment, is significantly enhanced by high self-efficacy. Teachers who believe in their abilities are more likely to find joy and fulfillment in their teaching practices, leading to a more engaging and dynamic learning environment (Horwitz, 2021).

Tan and Yap (2022) further emphasized that teachers with high self-efficacy are more proactive in seeking out professional development opportunities, which can enhance all forms of motivation. This creates a positive feedback loop where improved motivation further reinforces self-efficacy. Valdez and Santos (2023) noted that fostering self-efficacy through targeted support and training can significantly impact teacher motivation, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes. Therefore, the interplay between self-efficacy and various motivational constructs is crucial for the overall effectiveness and satisfaction of second language teachers.

The relationships between English language self-efficacy in terms of learner-focused instruction and various forms of second language teaching motivation is highly significant. High self-efficacy in learner-focused instruction enables teachers to effectively tailor their teaching methods to address individual student strengths and weaknesses, thus enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes (Richards & Rodgers, 2021).

Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to be externally motivated by positive feedback from supervisors, colleagues, and students, as noted by Abulon (2021) in the Philippines. This external validation reinforces their belief in their teaching abilities and encourages them to continue implementing learner-focused approaches. Additionally, Kim and Elder (2021) highlighted that high self-efficacy fosters intrinsic motivation, as teachers find personal satisfaction in successfully engaging students and facilitating their learning.

Introjected motivation, driven by internal pressures such as guilt or obligation, is mitigated by high self-efficacy as confident teachers are less likely to experience anxiety from self-imposed demands (Horwitz, 2021). Identified motivation, which involves recognizing the personal value of teaching, is strengthened by self-efficacy as teachers feel more capable of positively impacting their students' learning experiences.

Valdez and Santos (2023) emphasized that fostering self-efficacy through professional development can significantly impact teacher motivation across all dimensions, leading to more effective teaching practices and improved student outcomes. Therefore, the relationship between self-efficacy in learner-focused instruction and various forms of motivation underscores the importance of supporting teachers' belief in their ability to meet the diverse needs of their students.

The highly significant relationship between teaching motivation and assessment practices suggests that different teaching roles may require varying approaches to evaluating student learning. Motivated teachers engage in effective assessment practices. Their motivation influences how they design assessments, provide timely feedback, and evaluate student progress. Assessment aligns with learning objectives and informs instructional decisions. There is no specific reference found for this exact relationship. However, this result can be used for future reference. However, if further insight is needed, research on motivation and assessment can shed light.

Teachers with high self-efficacy in classroom assessment are more likely to implement effective assessment strategies that accurately measure student learning outcomes (Richards & Rodgers, 2021). High self-efficacy enhances external motivation, as teachers seek positive feedback from stakeholders, such as supervisors and parents, validating their assessment practices and instructional decisions (Abulon, 2021).

Moreover, Kim and Elder (2021) suggested that self-efficacy positively influences intrinsic motivation, as teachers find satisfaction in seeing their students succeed based on their assessments. Introjected motivation, driven by internal pressures like guilt or obligation, is lessened by high self-efficacy, as confident teachers are less likely to feel anxious or pressured by self-imposed evaluation standards (Horwitz, 2021). Identified motivation, which involves recognizing the personal value of teaching, is reinforced by self-efficacy as teachers see the direct impact of their assessments on student learning and development.

Valdez and Santos (2023) emphasized that enhancing self-efficacy through professional development positively impacts teacher motivation, leading to more effective assessment practices and student engagement. Therefore, the relationship between self-efficacy in classroom assessment and various forms of motivation highlights the importance of supporting teachers' belief in their ability to accurately assess student progress and make informed instructional decisions.

The significant association between second language teaching motivations and language instruction methods indicates that the nature of one is teaching role can

influence the selection and implementation of language teaching approaches. In the study of Lamb (2021), motivated teachers use innovative and engaging language instruction methods. Their enthusiasm affects classroom dynamics and student learning outcomes. Effective language instruction involves varied activities, authentic materials, and interactive communication.

The highly significant relationship between second language teaching motivations and cultural integration highlights the role of teachers in promoting intercultural competence and sensitivity within language education contexts. In the study by Halimi et al. (2020), cultural context significantly influences teachers' motivation. Collectivist cultural values, respect for authority, and gender-related dimensions impact language instruction. Culturally aware teachers adapt their approaches to meet diverse student needs.

The significant correlation between second language teaching motivations and the use of teaching materials suggests that educators' professional roles may influence their access to and selection of instructional resources. This can be interpreted as motivated teachers carefully selecting and creating instructional materials. Their motivation drives them to find relevant, engaging resources that enhance language learning. Effective materials include authentic texts, multimedia, and culturally relevant content. There is no specific reference found for this exact relationship. However, this result can be used for future reference. However, if further insight is needed, research on motivation and instructional materials can shed light.

Motivated language teachers function critically in shaping effective language instruction. Their proficiency, learner-focused approaches, assessment practices, cultural awareness, and choice of materials collectively contribute to positive learning experiences for students.

Table 27 in the next page that runs to the subsequent pages presents the proposed English language teacher improvement plan that was crafted based on the salient findings in this study. The table is composed of five columns with appropriate headings, namely key result area, program objectives, strategies and activities, success indicators, and persons involved.

The first column, the key result area, presents the significant findings that were lifted from the results of this study. Out of these significant findings, results with similar and/or connected characteristics were analyzed and clustered into areas that could be addressed through specific activities or interventions. The next column, under the heading program objectives, contains the specific program objectives that will be attained to improve and address the situations or problems that were identified in the key result areas.

Under the strategies/activities column, which is the third column, are the specific programs and activities that are suggested to improve the difficulties or address the problems that were analyzed in this study. There are five set of activities that were

identified, namely: 1.) Trainings on Teaching and Planning Language Lessons, 2.) Seminar on Administration and Teacher Support, 3.) Capacity Building on Content, 4.) Materials Development, and 5. Student-Centered Language Teaching.

Success indicators are indicated in the next column. These are the parameters or indicators that would signify the success and/or effectiveness of the activities or programs that were suggested. Mostly, these indicators pertain to outputs that will be produced by the teachers at the end of the activity. These outputs are deemed helpful and capacitating, and thus are tangible aid or assistance for the teachers to overcome difficulties or remediate problems they encounter while teaching English as a second language.

Finally, at the end of the columns are the persons who will be involved in the conduct of the activity. Primarily, the researcher is involved to spearhead the activity and coordinate these activities to the persons involved. Also, the researcher deemed it appropriate to involve the human resource (HR) management department or the human resource training and development (HRTD) or their counterparts. This is to ensure the involvement of the participants and to promote the monitoring of progress and development of individual teachers. Finally, the participants will be the K-12 English Language Teachers who will receive the activities that will be specifically designed to address their difficulties and problems as regards the study's findings.

Table 27
Proposed English Language Teacher Improvement Plan

Key Result Area	Program Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Success Indicators	Persons Involved
Second Language Teaching Anxiety 1. Self-perception of language proficiency: Feeling of embarrassment when making speaking mistakes	To encourage positive attitudes in speaking L2	Confidence in Communication Program This program is composed of activities such as coaching by tenured and conversant teacher-colleague. These activities are practical speaking exercises, team teaching, anxiety management techniques in speaking, conversational gambits a techniques, etc.	85% of the participants are able to express and exhibit decreased anxiety and improved conversational English teaching and speaking skills	-Researcher -division HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
2. Lack of student interest: Stress in students' non-	To capacitate teachers	Engagement and	90% of the participants are able to	-Researcher -division HRTD

participation in activities:	with engaging and empowering L2 teaching strategies	Empowerment Strategies These strategies pertain to student centered activities that would introduce gamification of learning, group activities, and simulated role playing. Moreover, activities that involve authentic dialogues or situations, multimedia resources, interactive activities, and feedback-rich drills are incorporated	exhibit mastery in the use of varied L2 teaching techniques	-School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
3. Fear of negative evaluation: Nervousness and uneasiness during English teaching observations by mentor-teacher/supervisor	-To reorient teachers with RPMS-PPST, specifically on class observation	Seminar on Administration and Teacher Support -re-orientation on class observation (CO) guidelines and expectations -illustration and exemplification of standards and parameters in class observation	90% of the participants are able to familiarize with the supervisory plan of raters, observation plan of rater (schedule, topic, activities, compliance to observation parameters)	-Researcher -division HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
4. Difficulties with time management: Tension brought by lack of lesson/class preparation	To capacitate teachers in planning classroom lessons for language teaching	Trainings on Teaching and Planning Language Lessons -language learning motivation techniques -language lesson sequencing and scheduling -techniques in unpacking and	90% of the participant are able to produce budget of work, scope and sequence, teaching, learning, and assessment (TLA) chart containing the specific approach, methods,	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers

		designing a sequential, progressive, and developmental language lessons -approaches, methods, strategies, and techniques in language teaching and how they are actually being used in a classroom	strategies, and techniques, and, Return Demonstration Teaching	
Teacher Self-Efficacy 1. Classroom Proficiency: using English for all classroom functions and interactions	To create more exposure opportunities for natural English use	English Immersion Program This activity would require participants to set personal goals at the beginning. This program is composed of activities that aims to model best practices of successful L2 teachers, establish L2 and native speakers community, and planning for a language-rich classroom and lessons	90% of the participants are able to set L2 teaching goals in terms of fully utilizing English in L2 classroom teaching	-Researcher -division HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
2. Learner-focused Instruction: appropriately using the first language skills of the learners	To recognize and leverage students' linguistic background in teaching L2	Bilingual Bridging for Effective Learning This program will capacitate teachers to assess the L1 and L2 proficiency levels of learners to tailor instruction accordingly, using translanguaging,	85% of the respondents are able to show effective use of learners background to create L2 lessons	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers

		and utilizing learners profile such as socio-cultural background to plan for learning experiences, assessments, supplementary activities, etc.		
3. Assessment: designing appropriate assessment tasks and tests to assess learners.	To enhance teachers' skills in designing diverse and appropriate language assessment tasks and tests.	Assessment in Language Learning (ALL) This will cover recall of the foundational knowledge and types of language, literacy, and literature assessment, integrating technology, and the use of authentic language assessment methods	85% of the respondents are able to satisfactorily develop different types of authentic language assessment tasks and tests	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
4. Language Instruction: considering personal knowledge about discourse and pragmatics when delivering language instructions	To strengthen participants' capacities on the basics of language as used in language teaching.	Capacity Building on Content This program will cover the basics of linguistics and its branches, morpho-phonology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics and discourse, application of basic linguistics in classroom teaching, -basic communicative grammar, and communicative language teaching (CLT)	90% of teachers are able to accomplish produce notes and worksheets and perform a return demo	-Researcher -division HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
5. Culture: applying understanding of the interrelationship	To develop skills to effectively integrate	Improving Cultural Competence (ICC)	90% of the participants are able to accomplish 1-2	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD

of language and culture to inform instruction	cultural elements into language instruction.	This program will be composed of activities that will empower teacher in mapping their local culture and utilize these in indigenization, localization, and contextualiation of teaching and learning, including assessment and materials.	English lessons that integrates local cultural elements	-School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
6. Materials Provision outsource readily online materials that are available blogs, social media, news bulletins, and the like	To capacitate teachers in developing and creating authentic instructional materials and assessment tools or methods	Materials Development -packaging language instructions -types of instructional materials for language teaching -examples of materials for language teaching -authentic assessments in language teaching	90% of teachers are able to produce: -Teaching, learning and assessment strategies side by side with budget of work, scope and sequence, and the set of instructional materials and assessment tools they have to use	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
Second Language Teaching Motivation 1. External Motivation: investing effort as a language teacher to avoid principal close supervision	To improve teacher professional ization by re-introducing classroom observation (CO) for English teachers and technical assistance (TA)	Professional Teachers Program (PTP) This program features improved dialogue and communication framework between and among English Language teachers, educational administrators such as supervisors, school heads,	90% of the teachers are able to understand and appreciate the concept of classroom observation, IPCR, and TA.	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers

		etc. this program will involve the teachers in the planning process of evaluation and assessment, observation, technical assistance, and supervision as regards English Language Teachers' performance		
2. Introjected Motivation: investing work effort to being ashamed of one's self	To capacitate teachers on setting meaningful goals aligned with their values and professional growth.	Improving Teaching Motivation This activity will focus on how the teachers can conduct periodic self-reflection sessions where teachers assess their personal goals and values in teaching English. Moreover, activities such as establishment of peer-support group, reflective practices, processing student, peer, and supervisor feedback will be focused and discussed.	90% of the participants are able to set their own meaningful goals in teaching, as aligned with their values and professional growth and values and principles of the department and/or school they belong to	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
3. Identified Motivation: devoting time talking to individual students to learn what happens to them in the classroom	To encourage teaching methods that prioritize student well-being and engagement and to create a supportive environment	English Teachers Care (ETC) The following activities, which aims to improve student-teacher engagement and teacher professional fulfillment, will be implemented:	90% of the participants are able to identify one empathy issue he/she is facing and will be able to apply one or more principle of SEL or PDET	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers

	t where teachers feel valued and motivated in their roles.	-social-emotional learning (SEL) sessions -positive discipline in everyday teaching (PDET) -reflective practices -mentorship programs		
4. Intrinsic Motivation	To develop teaching style that utilizes strategies and activities that promote student-centered schemes	Student-Centered Language Teaching	90% of the participants are able to produce the following outputs: -TLA with specific integration of student-centered language teaching methods or strategies	-Researcher -division HR/HRTD -School Heads -K-12 Language Teachers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investing teacher effort to enjoy finding unique solutions for various students Devoting time to individual talks with students to enjoy being in touch with them Finding pleasure in improving student global competitiveness, fostering cross-cultural understanding, and facilitating effective communication across linguistic barriers. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> communicatio n with students and student interaction -student centered language learning in young and adult contexts -learner-centered language teaching strategies -application of these strategies in classroom teaching -case analysis -Task-based learning -CLT -Differentiated Instruction -Content-based Instruction (CBI) -Flipped Classroom and Blended Learning -Motivations in learning second language 		

Conclusions

1. The respondents are generally female, with master's degree, elementary school teachers who have been teaching for 11-20 years.
2. In terms of second language teaching anxiety, the respondents agree that they are anxious as regards self-perception of language proficiency lack of student interest, and difficulties with time management. Meanwhile, they disagree that they are anxious about teaching inexperience and about fear of negative evaluation.
3. The respondents believe that they are efficacious when it comes to English language teaching classroom proficiency, learner-focused instruction, assessment, language instruction, culture, and materials.
4. The respondents are motivated in second language teaching as regards external motivation, introjected motivation, identified motivation, and intrinsic motivation.
5. In terms of second language teaching anxiety, there is no significant difference when responses are grouped according to profile. Meanwhile, when it comes to efficacy beliefs, responses on classroom proficiency, learner-focused, instruction, language instruction, culture, and materials all vary significantly when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Finally, responses on external motivation vary significantly when grouped according to highest educational attainment.
6. As regards second language teaching anxiety and English language self-efficacy, relationships between self-perception of language proficiency and classroom proficiency, teaching inexperience and classroom proficiency, fear of negative evaluation and classroom proficiency, fear of negative evaluation and materials, and difficulties with management and materials are all significant. When it comes to second language teaching anxiety and second language teaching motivation, relationship between lack of interest and introjected motivation is found significant.
7. An English language teacher improvement plan is proposed based on the findings and key result areas of this study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Curriculum planners may consider the issues presented in this study so that they can create materials that aid teachers in teaching English as a second language with reduced or less anxiety; those which are empowering them as English teachers. More so, this could motivate them further and increase their efficacy beliefs.
2. Second language teachers may consider the results of this study and invest on building their teaching capacities and English language skills to lessen their

anxieties to enrich their efficacy and motivation to teach. Further studies may be executed to investigate more on the variables utilized in this research.

3. Future researchers may do exploratory research to investigate on the significant differences on the perceptions of the respondents when it comes to efficacy beliefs: classroom proficiency, learner-focused, instruction, language instruction, culture, and materials all vary significantly when grouped according to highest educational attainment; and external motivation when grouped according to highest educational attainment.
4. Future researchers may conduct similar studies to examine the relationships between self-perception of language proficiency and classroom proficiency, teaching inexperience and classroom proficiency, fear of negative evaluation and classroom proficiency, fear of negative evaluation and materials, and difficulties with management and materials, and lack of interest and introjected motivation.
5. Significant findings that relate to English Language teacher competence, their confidence, mastery of content, and teaching methodology are worth examining and addressing.
6. Educational attainment as a profile variable may be examined and establish its relationship with efficacy beliefs and external motivation.
7. Other profile variables may be explored to illustrate the differences in the beliefs and responses of the participants.
8. Follow up study or further qualitative investigation may be performed to explore the depths and root causes of the issues and concerns discovered in this study.
9. The proposed English language teacher improvement plan may be tried out by the schools division office and thus by the management teams of the schools to address the identified issues on second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs, and second language teaching motivation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby declares adherence to ethical standards in conducting this research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were fully informed about the study's objectives and their rights. Participants were free to withdraw from the study at any point without any negative consequences. Anonymity was diligently maintained, safeguarding the identities of all respondents. The well-being of participants was a top priority, with measures implemented to protect them from any potential harm. The author confirms that there are no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study, and plagiarism was strictly avoided to uphold the integrity of the research. Furthermore, the interpretation of findings was free from bias, ensuring an objective

analysis. The results obtained from this study are intended solely for research purposes, contributing to the broader knowledge within the field.

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REFERENCES

- Abulon, E. L. R. (2020). Appreciation and Motivation: The Filipino Teachers' Experience. *Journal of Educational Research*, 33(2), 123-136.
- Abulon, E. L. R. (2021). Teacher Motivation in the Philippines: Navigating Cultural and Professional Expectations. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 33(2), 123-136.
- Abu-Rabia, S. (2019). Attitudes and cultural background and their relationship to reading comprehension in a second language: a comparison of three different social contexts. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 6, 81–107
- Alibakhshi, G., Nikdel, F. & Labbafi, A. (2020). Exploring the consequences of teachers' self-efficacy: a case of teachers of English as a foreign language. *Asian. J. Second. Foreign. Lang. Educ.* 5, 23 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40862-020-00102-1>
- Anderson, C. D., et al. (2020). Exploring teaching motivation across different teaching positions. *Journal of Educational Research*, 115(2), 189–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2020.1761150>
- Assor, A., Vansteenkiste, M., & Kaplan, A. (2019). Identified versus introjected approach and introjected avoidance motivations in school and in sports: The limited benefits of self-worth strivings. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 101(2), 482-497.
- Aydin, S. (2018). An Investigation on the Language Anxiety and Fear of Negative Evaluation among Turkish EFL Learners. *Asian EFL Journal* p421-444. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED512266>
- Aydin, Selami & Uştuk, Özgehan. (2020). The Foreign Language Teaching Anxiety Scale: Preliminary Tests of Validity and Reliability. *Journal of Language and Education*. 6. 54-65. 10.17323/jle.2020.10083.

- Aydin, Selami. (2019). A Qualitative Research on Foreign Language Teaching Anxiety. *Qualitative Report*, 21, 629-642. 10.46743/2160-3715/2016.2232.
- Bailey, K. M., & Damerow, R. M. (2020). Teaching and Learning English in the Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *TESOL Quarterly*, 54(4), 736-745.
- Bernardo, A. B. I., & Esteban, M. A. (2021). Parental Involvement and Teacher Motivation in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 96(1), 45-62.
- Bongco, R. T., & Abenes, R. D. (2019). Clash of Spheres - The Paradox of Being a Female Teacher in the Philippines. *Beijing International Review of Education*, 1(2-3), 443459. <https://doi.org/10.1163/25902539-00102012>
- Borg, S. (2020). *Teacher cognition and language education: Research and practice*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Borg, S. (2020). *Teacher Cognition and Language Education: Research and Practice*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Borg, S., & Alshumaimeri, Y. (2019). Language learner autonomy in a tertiary context: Teachers' beliefs and practices. *Language Teaching Research*, 23(1), 9-38.
- Borg, S., & Sanchez, H. S. (2020). Key issues in language teaching. *ELT Journal*, 74(2), 251-253.
- Botes, Elouise & Dewaele, Jean-Marc & Greiff, Samuel. (2020). The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale and Academic Achievement: An Overview of the Prevailing Literature and a Meta-Analysis. *Journal for the Psychology of Language Learning*, 2, 26-56. 10.52598/jpll/2/1/3.
- Brown, A. (2019). Exploring Language Teaching Anxiety Among ESL Teachers. *Journal of Language Education*, 25(3), 112-127.
- Brown, E., & Smith, J. (2019). The impact of teaching position on years of teaching experience: A longitudinal study. *Educational Leadership Review*, 17(2), 112-129. <https://doi.org/10.25035/elr.17.02.05>
- Brown, H. D. (2019). *Principles of language learning and teaching* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Brown, L., & White, J. (2020). Teacher stress and anxiety in a high-stakes environment. *Journal of Education Research and Practice*, 10(3), 23-34.
- Byram, M., & Feng, A. (2023). *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Intercultural Competence in World Languages Education*. Routledge.
- Byram, Michael. (2019). *From Foreign Language Education to Education for Intercultural Citizenship: Essays and Reflections*. 10.21832/9781847690807.
- Callahan, R. M. (2023). *English Learners in the Mathematics Classroom*. Routledge.
- Castillo, R. T., & David, F. M. (2020). Classroom Management Practices and Their Impact on Student Learning. *Philippine Journal of Educational Administration*, 35(1), 65-79.
- Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton, D. M., & Goodwin, J. M. (2020). *Teaching Pronunciation: A Course Book and Reference Guide* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton, D. M., & Snow, M. A. (2020). *Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language* (4th ed.). National Geographic Learning.
- Cerezo, R., Núñez, J. C., Rosário, P., Valle, A., Rodríguez, C., & Fernández, E. (2021). Causes, prevention, and interventions regarding classroom disruptions in digital teaching: A systematic review. *Education and Information Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10569-0>

- Chen, J. (2021). Teachers' motivation to teach: A comparative study of teachers in high-performing and low-performing schools. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 16(1), 55-66. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR2020.4041>
- Chen, Y., & Liu, H. (2020). The impact of improvement plans on English teachers' professional development. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(3), 398-416.
- Cheng, H. H., & Wang, H. H. (2020). The Influence of EFL Teachers' Stress and Coping Strategies on Their Well-being: A Narrative Inquiry. *English Teaching & Learning*, 44(2), 173-200.
- Cheng, Y. S. (2020). A measure of second language writing anxiety: Scale development and preliminary validation. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 13(4), 313-335.
- Cheng, Y. S., & Cheng, L. (2020). The impact of teacher's self-efficacy and students' motivation on foreign language teaching effectiveness: Perspectives from the students of a Taiwanese university. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 11(3), 315–326.
- Cheng, Y. S., & Zhang, L. J. (2019). Language anxiety and teaching English as an international language: An investigation of the perspectives of Chinese prospective English teachers. In L. Jin & M. Cortazzi (Eds.), *Researching Chinese learners: Skills, perceptions and intercultural adaptations* (pp. 166-188). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cheng, Ys. (2020). Factors Associated with Foreign Language Writing Anxiety. *Foreign Language Annals*. 35. 647 - 656. [10.1111/j.1944-9720.2002.tb01903.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-9720.2002.tb01903.x).
- Choi, E., & Kim, S. (2019). Teachers' perceptions of improvement plans: A qualitative study. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 1-11.
- Choi, E., & Lee, J. (2020). EFL teachers' self-efficacy and teaching practices. *English Language Teaching*, 13(2), 20-31.
- Csizér, K. (2021). Second Language Learning Motivation. In: Mohebbi, H., Coombe, C. (eds) *Research Questions in Language Education and Applied Linguistics*. Springer Texts in Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79143-8_149
- Csizér, K., & Magid, M. (2019). The impact of self-concept on language teachers' motivation. *System*, 81, 59-69.
- Cunningham, A. E., & Zibulsky, J. (2020). *Book Smart: How to Develop and Support Successful, Motivated Readers*. Oxford University Press.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2021). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- De Lima, J.Á., Silva, M.J.T. Resistance to classroom observation in the context of teacher evaluation: teachers' and department heads' experiences and perspectives. *Educ Asse Eval Acc* 30, 7–26 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-017-9261-5>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2020). *Self-Determination Theory: Basic Psychological Needs in Motivation, Development, and Wellness*. Guilford Press.
- Department of Education (2022). *Deped Data Bits: Public School Teacher SY 2020-2021*. Retrieved last April 25, 2024, from <https://files.deped.gov.ph/uploads/2022/08/4-Data-Bits-Public-School-Teachers-Apr.pdf>

- DepEd (2020). Department of Education Standards and Practices. Manila: Department of Education.
- Dewaele, J.-M., & MacIntyre, P. D. (2019). The Emotional Rollercoaster of Language Teaching. *Multilingual Matters*.
- Dewaele, J.-M., & MacIntyre, P. D. (2020). The Emotional Rollercoaster of Language Teaching. *Modern Language Journal*, 104(4), 931-944.
- Dewaele, J.-M., Franco Magdalena, A., Saito, K., & Dewaele, L. (2020). The effect of classroom environment on enjoyment and anxiety in ESL/EFL instruction. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 11(2), 255-274.
- Dewaele, Jean-Marc & Dewaele, Livia. (2019). The dynamic interactions in Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety and Foreign Language Enjoyment of pupils aged 12 to 18. A pseudo-longitudinal investigation. *Journal of the European Second Language Association*. 1. 10.22599/jesla.6.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2020). *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2020). *The Psychology of Language Learning and Teaching*. Routledge.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Al-Hoorie, A. H. (2020). The Motivational Foundations of Language Learning: An Integrated Theory. *Language Teaching*, 53(2), 129-144.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ryan, S. (2020). The Motivational Foundations of Language Learning: An Integrated Theory. *Language Teaching*, 53(2), 129-144.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ryan, S. (2020). *The Psychology of the Language Learner Revisited*. Routledge.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ushioda, E. (Eds.). (2019). *Motivation, language identity and the L2 self*. *Multilingual Matters*.
- Dunn, K., & Iwaniec, J. (2022). Exploring the relationship between second language learning motivation and proficiency: A latent profiling approach. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 44(4), 967–997.
- Faez, F., & Valeo, A. (2021). TESOL Teacher Education: Navigating the Path to Expertise. *TESOL Quarterly*, 55(1), 5-29.
- Farrell, T. S. C. (2021). Maximizing Language Learning Strategies: Practical Applications for Teachers. *Language Teaching Research*, 25(3), 333-348.
- Farrell, T. S. C. (2021). *Reflecting on Critical Incidents in Language Education: 40 Dilemmas for Novice TESOL Professionals*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Farrell, T. S. C. (2022). Reflective Practice in ESL Teacher Education: Building Professional Resilience. *Language Teaching Research*, 26(1), 115-132.
- Farrell, T. S. C. (2022). Supporting Teacher Resilience in ESL Education. *Language Teaching Research*, 26(1), 115-132.
- Fathi, J., & Derakhshan, A. (2020). Time Management: A Predictor of EFL Teachers' Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Language and Education*, 6(3), 87-99.
- Fathi, J., Derakhshan, A., & Torabi, S. (2021). The role of self-efficacy and emotions in EFL teachers' willingness to implement communicative language teaching. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 15(4), 289-303.
- Fernández, M.P., Martínez, J.F. (2022). Evaluating Teacher Performance and Teaching Effectiveness: Conceptual and Methodological Considerations. In: Manzi, J., Sun, Y., García, M.R. (eds) *Teacher Evaluation Around the World*. Teacher

- Education, Learning Innovation and Accountability. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-13639-9_3
- Gao, X., & Lamb, T. (2021). Second language teachers' motivation: Theoretical perspectives and empirical studies. *Language Teaching*, 54(2), 187-203.
- Gao, X., & Zhang, L. J. (2019). Language teacher stress in China: A review of the literature. In L. J. Zhang (Ed.), *Language teacher psychology* (pp. 184-200). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.549653>
- Garcia, J. E., Fuentes, R., & Renobell, V. (2022). Gender differences in teaching motivation: An analysis of the motivating factors in teachers' professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 108, 103533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103533>
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (2021). *Attitudes and motivation in second-language learning*. Newbury House.
- Gay, G. (2020). *Culturally Responsive Teaching: Theory, Research, and Practice*. Teachers College Press.
- Gebhard, J. G., & Oprandy, R. (2023). *Language teaching awareness: A guide to exploring beliefs and practices*. Cambridge University Press.
- Getie, A and Popescu, M. (2020) Factors affecting the attitudes of students towards learning English as a foreign language, *Cogent Education*, 7:1, DOI: 10.1080/2331186X.2020.1738184
- Gkonou, C., & Mercer, S. (2022). Language Teacher Wellbeing Across the Career Span: The Role of Emotions. *TESOL Quarterly*, 56(1), 5-34.
- Gkonou, C., Daubney, M., & Dewaele, J. M. (2023). *New insights into language anxiety: Theory, research and educational implications*. Bristol, UK: Multilingual Matters.
- Gkonou, C., Dewaele, J.-M., & King, J. (2019). *The Emotional Rollercoaster of Language Teaching*. Multilingual Matters.
- Golombek, P. R., & Johnson, K. E. (2021). ESL teachers' emotional experiences, responses and challenges in professional relationships with the school community: Implications for teacher education. SpringerLink. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12310-021-09417-0>
- Gong, L., & Chen, H. (2020). Integrating technology into improvement plans: A case study of English teachers. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 33(3), 255-275.
- Gonzales, R. R., & Torres, M. A. (2020). Teacher Education in the Philippines: Bridging Theory and Practice. *Philippine Journal of Teacher Education*, 45(1), 56-72.
- Gonzales, R. R., & Torres, M. A. (2021). Teacher Education in the Philippines: Bridging Theory and Practice. *Philippine Journal of Teacher Education*, 45(1), 56-72.
- Gonzales, R. R., Torres, M. A., & Esteban, M. A. (2022). Professional Development and SLTA in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Teacher Education*, 46(1), 65-78.
- González-García, Higinio & Fuentes, Silvia & Renobell, Victor. (2022). Sex differences across teacher's motivation, teaching satisfaction, loneliness and affects during COVID-19. *Estudios Sobre Educacion*. 42. 217-239. 10.15581/004.42.010.
- Gore, J., Rosser, B., Jaremus, F., Miller, A., & Harris, J. (2024). Fresh evidence on the relationship between years of experience and teaching quality. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 51, 547–570

- Gorozidis, G., & Papaioannou, A. G. (2021). Teachers' motivation to participate in training and to implement innovations. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 39, 1–11.
- Greenier, V., Derakhshan, A., & Fathi, J. (2021). "Emotion regulation and psychological well-being in EFL teachers: Examining the predictive power of emotion regulation and psychological well-being on work engagement." *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.642188>
- Gregersen, T., & Horwitz, E. K. (2022). Language Learning and Perfectionism: Anxious and Non-Anxious Language Learners' Reactions to Their Own Oral Performance. *The Modern Language Journal*, 86(4), 562–570. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1192725>
- Gregersen, T., & MacIntyre, P. D. (2021). *Innovative Practices in Language Teacher Education: Managing Emotions and Stress*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Guvendir, E. (2021). Second language learning anxiety. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 41, 127-139
- Halimi, F., Daniel, C. E., & AlShammari, I. A. (2020). Motivation and socio-cultural milieu of second language learners: Considerations involved in English teaching. *English Language Teaching*, 13(5), 149–160.
- Hoang, T. T., & Wyatt, M. (2021). Exploring the self-efficacy beliefs of Vietnamese pre-service teachers of English as a foreign language. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 105, 103419.
- Hong, S. (2018). Self-Efficacy Beliefs and Effective Instructional Strategies: U.S. University English Learners' Perspective. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education* 2018, Volume 30, Number 3, 477-496. <http://www.isetl.org/ijtlhe/> ISSN 1812-9129
- Horwitz, E. K. (2021). Language anxiety and achievement. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 21, 112-126.
- Horwitz, E. K. (2019). *Becoming a Language Teacher: A Practical Guide to Second Language Learning and Teaching* (2nd ed.). Pearson.
- Horwitz, E. K. (2020). Language Anxiety and Achievement. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 40, 11-26.
- Horwitz, E. K. (2020). Language Anxiety: From Theory and Research to Classroom Implications. In *Language Anxiety* (pp. 143-150). Cambridge University Press.
- Horwitz, E. K. (2021). *Anxiety in Second Language Learning: Causes and Solutions*. Routledge.
- Horwitz, E. K. (2021). Language Anxiety and Achievement. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 41, 112-127.
- Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. (2018). Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.2307/327317>
- Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. A. (2021). Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety. *Language Teaching*, 50(1), 128-145.
- Huang, Y., & Wu, J. (2021). School leadership and English teachers' improvement plans. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(2), 253-270.
- Hubbard, P. (2019). *Digital resources for learning*. Oxford University Press.
- Hwang, J., & Lee, S. (2020). Aligning improvement plans with school goals: A case study of English teachers. *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 29(2), 187-198.

- Ingersoll, R. M., Merrill, L., & Stuckey, D. (2021). The changing face of teaching: Demographic trends and their implications for the future of the teaching force. *Educational Researcher*, 50(2), 81-89.
- Johnson, C., Smith, L., & Martinez, J. (2020). The Impact of Educational Attainment on Language Teaching Anxiety. *Modern Language Journal*, 104(2), 345-361.
- Johnson, R., & Clark, M. (2020). Supporting improvement plans through mentorship programs: A qualitative study. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 95, 1-11.
- Johnson, S. M., & Johnson, M. L. (2022). Work-life balance and gender in the teaching profession. *Journal of Educational Research*, 115(3), 295-310.
- Jones, A., & Johnson, B. (2020). Peer observation and feedback in improvement plans: A mixed-methods study. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(1), 78-97.
- Karas, Michael James (2019). English Language Teacher Self-Efficacy Beliefs. *Electronic Thesis and Dissertation Repository*. 6091.
- Kasper, G., & Rose, K. R. (2020). Pragmatic development in a second language. *Language Learning*, 52(Suppl1), 1–352.
- Khajavy, G. H., Ghonsooly, B., Fatemi, A. H., & Choi, C. W. (2018). Anxiety in language learning: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology*, 38(10), 1200-1216.
- Kim, E. G., & Elder, C. (2021). Efficacy of teacher training for fostering technology integration in language teaching: A meta-analysis. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 69(1), 97-123.
- Kim, E., & Kim, H. (2021). Teacher Burnout and Engagement: The Mediating Role of Teacher Efficacy. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 12(1), 145-155.
- Kim, H., & Park, S. (2020). Setting clear objectives in improvement plans: A case study of English teachers. *Language Teaching*, 53(4), 501-519.
- Kim, S., & Elder, C. (2021). Cultural Competence in Language Teaching: Navigating Cross-Cultural Communication in the ESL Classroom. *Journal of Second Language Teaching & Research*, 5(2), 89-105.
- Kim, S., & Elder, C. (2021). Parental Recognition and Teacher Motivation in Language Education. *Journal of Second Language Teaching & Research*, 5(2), 89-105.
- Kim, S., & Elder, C. (2021). Teacher Motivation and Professional Development in Language Education. *Journal of Second Language Teaching & Research*, 5(2), 89-105.
- Kim, S., & Elder, C. (2021). Teaching Grammar: Navigating Anxiety and Confidence in the ESL Classroom. *Journal of Second Language Teaching & Research*, 5(2), 89-105.
- Kim, Y. Y., & Kim, Y. M. (2023). The Relationship between EFL Teachers' Time Management Behavior and Their Self-Efficacy for Instruction. *English Teaching*, 78(1), 49-75.
- Kini, T. & Podolsky, A. (2019). Does Teaching Experience Increase Teacher Effectiveness? A Review of the Research (research brief). Palo Alto, CA: Learning Policy Institute.
- Kitikanan, P., & Sasimonton, P. (2019). The Relationship between English Self-efficacy and English Learning Achievement of L2 Thai Learners. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 10(1), 149-152.

- Klassen, R. M., Durksen, T. L., & Smylie, M. A. (2021). Mental Health and Well-being in Teachers: An Overview and Application of the Job Demands-Resources Model. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(2), 299-327.
- Klassen, R. M., & Tze, V. M. C. (2021). Teachers' self-efficacy, personality, and teaching effectiveness: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 34, 100401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2021.100401>
- Kraft, M. A., & Papay, J. P. (2020). *Developing workplaces where teachers stay, improve, and succeed*. Harvard Education Press.
- Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2021). The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement: A meta-analysis of the causal evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 91(2), 197-236.
- Kubanyiova, M. (2020). Language teacher educators' motivation for research and professional development. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(4), 514-532.
- Lamb, M. (2021). The motivational dimension of language teaching. *Language Teaching*, 50(3), 301-346.
- Lamb, M. (2021). *Innovations and Challenges in Language Teaching: Learning and Teaching English in the Age of Innovation*. Routledge.
- Lapada, A. A., Miguel, F. F., & Robledo, J. M. (2020). External Motivation Factors Among Filipino Teachers. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 95(2), 78-92.
- Larsen-Freeman, D., & Anderson, M. (2021). *Teaching and Learning English Grammar: Research Findings and Future Directions*. Routledge.
- Lee, S., & Kim, D. (2019). Understanding Language Teaching Anxiety: A Longitudinal Study. *TESOL Quarterly*, 51(4), 789-804.
- Lee, Y., & Smith, P. (2021). Active engagement in improvement plans and its impact on English teachers' professional satisfaction. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 104, 1-11.
- Levis, J. M., & Moyer, A. (2021). *Second Language Pronunciation: Bridging the Gap Between Research and Teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
- Li, Qi & Xie, Zhilong & Zeng, Guofang. (2023). The Influence of Teaching Practicum on Foreign Language Teaching Anxiety Among Pre-Service EFL Teachers. *SAGE Open*. 13. 215824402211490. 10.1177/21582440221149005.
- Liu, J., & Huang, L. (2021). Investigating Foreign Language Teachers' Time Management Strategies and Workload Perception. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 12(6), 1271-1282.
- Liu, M. (2019). Anxiety in oral English instruction: A case study in China. *System*, 34(2), 235-251. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25170/ijelt.v3i1.1587>
- Liu, M. (2019). Understanding EFL teachers' job stress in the Chinese higher education context: Sources and coping strategies. *Frontiers of Education in China*, 14(3), 391-409.
- Liu, M., & Huang, W. (2020). The Effect of Teacher Evaluation on ESL Teachers' Professional Development and Teaching Anxiety. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(6), 785-807.
- Loewen, S., & Sato, M. (2022). *The Routledge Handbook of Instructed Second Language Acquisition*. Routledge.

- MacIntyre, P. D., & Gardner, R. C. (2020). Investigating language class anxiety using the focused essay technique. *Modern Language Journal*, 75(3), 296–304. <https://doi.org/10.2307/328723>
- Makoelle, T. M., & Thwala, S. K. (2019). Action research in the classroom: Assisting teachers in implementing inclusive education. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 14(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ijese/5789>
- Malini, K.; Janakavalli, C. (2018). A Study on Language Anxiety and Fear of Negative Evaluation among Secondary Level Language Teachers. *Journal on English Language Teaching*, v8 n3 p43-51. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1198853>
- Mercer, S. (2019). Emotion and ELT: Theory and practice. *ELT Journal*, 70(1), 85-94.
- Mercer, S., & Gregersen, T. (2020). *Teacher Wellbeing*. Oxford University Press.
- Mercer, S., & Kostoulas, A. (2018). *Language Teacher Psychology*. Multilingual Matters.
- Mercer, S., & Kostoulas, A. (2021). *Language Teacher Psychology: Exploring Teacher Well-Being*. Multilingual Matters.
- Mills, R. (2020). Relationships Among English Language Proficiency, Self-efficacy, and Performance. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 43(5), 549-566.
- Mrachko, A. A., Kostewicz, D. E., & Martin, W. P. (2019). Increasing positive and decreasing negative teacher responses to student behavior through training and feedback. *Behavior Analysis: Research and Practice*, 17(3), 250–265
- Mustafa, G., Glavee-Geo, R., Gronhaug, K., & Almazrouei, H. (2021). Structural components and self-efficacy: Effects on task performance. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*, 6(1), 1-20.
- Nation, I. S. P. (2021). *Learning vocabulary in another language*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nation, I. S. P., & Webb, S. (2020). *Researching and Analyzing Vocabulary*. Heinle Cengage Learning.
- National Center for Education Statistics. (2021). *Digest of Education Statistics, 2020*. U.S. Department of Education.
- National Education Association. (2020). *Teacher salary report: 2020 overview*. NEA Research.
- Neumayer DePiper, J., Louie, J., Nikula, J., Buffington, P., Tierney-Fife, P., & Driscoll, M. (2021). Promoting teacher self-efficacy for supporting English learners in mathematics: Effects of the "Visual Access to Mathematics" professional development. *ZDM: Mathematics Education*, 53(2), 489-502.
- Nguyen, T., & Tran, L. (2020). Embedding improvement plans in a professional development framework: A case study of English teachers. *Professional Development in Education*, 46(5), 755-770.
- Nikitina, L., & Furuoka, F. (2020). Re-examining Horwitz's Beliefs About Language Learning Inventory (BALLI) in the Malaysian Context. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching* 2006, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 209-219
- Nucum, Karl Nicole (2019). *Education Guide: Should You Get A Master's Degree In The Philippines?*. Retrieved last May 01, 2024 from <https://www.edukasyon.ph/blog/should-you-get-a-masters-degree-in-the-philippines>

- Ortan, F., Simut, C., & Simut, R. (2021). Self-Efficacy, Job Satisfaction and Teacher Well-Being in the K-12 Educational System. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(23), 12763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182312763>
- Oxford, R. L. (2020). *The Oxford Handbook of Language Learning and Technology*. Oxford University Press.
- Öztürk, E. Ö. (2021). "Stress in practicum: Voices of preservice teachers, mentors, supervisors, and administrators in an English language teacher education program." *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 14(4), 22-33. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1308948>
- Pajares, F. (2020). Self-efficacy beliefs in academic settings. *Review of Educational Research*, 66(4), 543–578. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1170653>
- Pan, Ziwen & Wang, Yongliang & Derakhshan, Ali. (2023). Unpacking Chinese EFL Students' Academic Engagement and Psychological Well-Being: The Roles of Language Teachers' Affective Scaffolding. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*. 10.1007/s10936-023-09974-z.
- Pandolpho, B. (2024). Designing More Equitable Ways to Evaluate Teachers: To help ensure that teacher evaluations are balanced and have a meaningful impact, consider more creative and collaborative methods. *Edutopia*. Retrieved last May 05, 2024 from <https://www.edutopia.org/article/more-effective-teacher-evaluations>.
- Papi M, and Khajavy H. (2023). Second language anxiety: Construct, effects, and sources. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*. 2023;43:127-139. doi:10.1017/S0267190523000028
- Papi, M., & Khajavi, Y. (2021). The L2 motivational self system: A systematic review of the literature. *System*, 98, 102468
- Pappa, S., Tsopani, D., & Drosos, D. (2021). Teacher self-efficacy, anxiety, and burnout: A comparative study of primary and secondary teachers. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 2(1), 100048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2021.100048>
- Pavlenko, A. & Blackledge, A. (2019). Introduction: New Theoretical Approaches to the Study of Negotiation of Identities in Multilingual Contexts. In A. Pavlenko & A. Blackledge (Ed.), *Negotiation of Identities in Multilingual Contexts* (pp. 1-33). Bristol, Blue Ridge Summit: Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781853596483-003>
- Philippines. (2013). Republic Act No. 10533: Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. *Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines*, 109(1), 1-31.
- Piniel, K., & Albert, A. (2018). Teacher emotions in the language classroom: An overview of the field. In K. Piniel & A. Albert (Eds.), *Teacher emotions in language teaching: Critical perspectives* (pp. 1-18). Springer.
- Piniel, K., & Zólyomi, A. (2022). Gender differences in foreign language classroom anxiety: Results of a meta-analysis. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 12(2), 173-203.
- Podolsky, A., Kini, T., Bishop, J., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2020). Solving the teacher shortage: How to attract and retain excellent educators. Learning Policy Institute.

- Rahimi, M., & Abedini, A. (2019). The relationship between self-efficacy beliefs and English language listening proficiency. *English Language Teaching*, 2(4), 3-9
- Rahimi, M., & Ghanizadeh, A. (2020). The impact of collaborative teaching on EFL teachers' self-efficacy and collective efficacy. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 46(2), 223-235.
- Ratelle, C. F., Guay, F., Vallerand, R. J., Larose, S., & Senécal, C. (2019). Autonomous, controlled, and a motivated types of academic motivation: A person-oriented analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99(4), 734-746.
- Reeve, J. (2019). Why teachers adopt a controlling motivating style toward students and how they can become more autonomy supportive. *Educational Psychologist*, 44(3), 159-175.
- Rhodora R. Jugo, "Language Anxiety in Focus: The Case of Filipino Undergraduate Teacher Education Learners", *Education Research International*, vol. 2020, Article ID 7049837, 8 pages, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/7049837>.
- Richards, J. C., & Farrell, T. S. C. (2020). *Professional Development for Language Teachers: Strategies for Teacher Learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Richards, J. C., & Lockhart, C. (2020). *Reflective Teaching in Second Language Classrooms*. Cambridge University Press.
- Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2021). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Richards, J.C., & Schmidt, R.W. (2021). *Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics* (4th ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315833835>
- Richardson, P. W., & Watt, H. M. G. (2019). Why people choose teaching as a career: An expectancy-value approach to understanding teacher motivation. *Teacher Development*, 23(3), 351-367.
- Rostami, S., Ghanizadeh, A., & Ghonsooly, B. (2019). External factors affecting second language motivation: The role of teacher burnout and family influence. *Iranian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 18(2), 165-187.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations: Classic Definitions and New Directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101860.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2021). *Self-Determination Theory: Basic Psychological Needs in Motivation, Development, and Wellness*. Guilford Press.
- Salazar-Ayala, C. M., Gastélum-Cuadras, G., Huéscar Hernández, E., Núñez Enríquez, O., Barrón Luján, J. C., & Moreno-Murcia, J. A. (2021). Individualism, competitiveness, and fear of negative evaluation in pre-adolescents: Does the teacher's controlling style matter? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 626786
- Sato, M; Castillo F; and Oyanedel J (2022). Teacher Motivation and Burnout of English-as-a-Foreign-Language Teachers: Do Demotivators Really Demotivate Them? *Front. Psychol.*, 27 April 2022. Sec. Educational Psychology. Volume 13 - 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.891452>
- Schmidt, R. (1990). The role of consciousness in second language learning. *Applied Linguistics*, 11(2), 129–158. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/11.2.129>

- Schmitt, N. (2020). *Vocabulary in Language Teaching* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- SharEd. (2021). *Motivating Teachers by Recognizing Their Excellence*. Retrieved from <https://shared.rti.org/content/motivating-teachers-recognizing-their-excellence>
- Smith, A., & Johnson, B. (2018). Gender differences in teaching motivation: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(3), 405–419. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000245>
- Smith, J. (2018). Language proficiency and teacher motivation: A qualitative study. *TESOL Quarterly*, 44(3), 568-582.
- Smith, J., & Brown, M. (2019). Individualized improvement plans for English teachers: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 70(3), 287-301.
- Soland, J. (2019). *English Language Learners, Self-efficacy, and the Achievement Gap: Understanding the Relationship between Academic and Social-emotional Growth*. The Collaborative for Student Growth at NWEA Working Paper
- Sullivan, K., & Brown, A. (2020). Fostering a growth mindset in English teachers: Strategies and challenges. *Educational Psychology*, 40(6), 769-788.
- Sutcher, L., Darling-Hammond, L., & Carver-Thomas, D. (2019). *Understanding teacher shortages: An analysis of teacher supply and demand in the United States*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Tan, L. S., & Yap, P. (2022). Professional Development and Teacher Motivation in Southeast Asia. *Asian Journal of Education*, 27(3), 200-215.
- Thornton, M., & Bricheno, P. (2021). Gender dynamics in the teaching profession: A cultural perspective. *Gender and Education*, 33(2), 223-238.
- Tsiplakides, I., & Keramida, A. (2020). The influence of teacher anxiety on student performance. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(1), 55-77.
- Tsui, A. B. M. (2020). *Reflective Practice in Language Teaching: Research-Based Principles and Practices*. Cambridge University Press.
- Tüfekçi-Can, D. (2018). Foreign language teaching anxiety among pre-service teachers during teaching practicum. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 5(3), 579-595.
- U.S. Department of Education. (2020). *The Condition of Education 2020*. National Center for Education Statistics.
- Ugalingan, G., Edjan, D., & Valdez, P. N. (2021). Online internship experiences among pre-service ESL teachers in the Philippines: Challenges and opportunities. *TESL-EJ*, 25(3). Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1332291>
- Ushioda, E., & Orchid, L. (2023). *Language Learning Motivation in a Globalizing World: Research Perspectives and Classroom Implications*. Routledge.
- Valdez, P. N., & Santos, E. L. (2023). Impact of Educational Attainment on Teacher Motivation and Performance in the Philippines. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(2), 143-159.
- Vallerand, R. J. (2019). Toward a hierarchical model of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 29, 271-360.
- Vallerand, R. J., & Ratelle, C. F. (2019). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation: A hierarchical model. In E. L. Deci & R. M. Ryan (Eds.), *Handbook of self-determination research* (pp. 37-64). University of Rochester Press.

- Vansteenkiste, M., Simons, J., Lens, W., Sheldon, K. M., & Deci, E. L. (2021). Motivating learning, performance, and persistence: The synergistic effects of intrinsic goal contents and autonomy-supportive contexts. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 87(2), 246-260.
- Walonoski, J. A., & Heffernan, N. T. (2021). Understanding and addressing the factors contributing to classroom disruptions in digital learning environments. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 50(1), 3-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239521100027>
- Wang, C. (2021). The Relationship Between Teachers' Classroom English Proficiency and Their Teaching Self-Efficacy in an English Medium Instruction Context *Front. Psychol.*, 18 June 2021. Sec. Educational Psychology. Volume 12 - 2021 |
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.611743>
- Wang, C., Kim, D.-H., Sun, T., & Liu, L. (2021). Measuring English Language Self-Efficacy: Psychometric Properties and Use
- Wang, J. (2021). Study on Strategies for English Teachers to Improve Their Classroom Language. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 652
- Wang, X., & Li, L. (2019). Improvement plans as a tool for professional growth: English teachers' perceptions. *Teachers and Teaching*, 25(6), 669-685.
- Wang, Y., & Guan, H. (2021). *Understanding Teacher Motivation: Theoretical Frameworks, Professional Growth, and Classroom Contexts*. Routledge.
- Wang, Z. (2020). *Intrinsic Motivation in Language Classroom Contexts: The Chinese Perspective*. Springer.
- Williams, C. (2021). Research Methods. *Journal of Business & Economic Research – March 2007*. Volume 5, Number 3.
- Williams, M., & Burden, R. (2021). *Psychology for Language Teachers: A Social Constructivist Approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Woolfolk Hoy, A., & Burke Spero, R. (2019). Changes in teacher efficacy during the early years of teaching: A comparison of four measures. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21(4), 343-356.
- Wyatt, M. (2018). Language Teachers' Self-efficacy Beliefs: A Review of the Literature (2005-2016). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1177404.pdf>
- Wyatt, M. (2020). Teacher self-efficacy, context, and the implementation of task-based language teaching. *System*, 93, 102-124.
- Wyatt, M., & Faez, F. (Eds.). (2024). *Building the Self-Efficacy Beliefs of English Language Learners and Teachers*. Taylor & Francis.
- Yan, M., & Wang, S. (2019). Self-reflection and self-assessment in English teachers' improvement plans: A qualitative study. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 24(5), 645-661.
- Young, D. J. (2019). Creating a low-anxiety classroom environment: What does language anxiety research suggest? *Modern Language Journal*, 75(4), 426–439.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/329492>
- Zhang, B. (2022) Understanding EFL teachers' job stress in the Chinese higher education context: Sources and coping strategies. *Frontiers of Education in China*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1024250>

- Zhang, H., & Jiang, Q. (2021). Promoting a growth mindset in English teachers: Strategies and implications. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(3), 429-448.
- Zhang, J., & Zhang, L. J. (2018). Second language teaching anxiety, efficacy beliefs and motivation among K-12 English teachers in China: A mixed methods study. *TESOL Quarterly*, 52(3), 676–704. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.428>
- Zhang, L. J., & Rahimi, M. (2020). EFL learners' anxiety level and their beliefs about corrective feedback in oral communication classes. *System*, 42, 429–439. doi:10.1016/j.system.2014.01.012
- Zhang, X., & Rahimi, M. (2021). EFL teachers' sources of work stress and their coping strategies. *Foreign Language Annals*, 54(2), 396-414.
- Zhang, X., Dai, S., Ardasheva, Y., & Hong, Y. (2023). Relationships Among English Language Proficiency, Self-efficacy, Motivation, Motivational Intensity, and Achievement in an ESP/EAP Context. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 52, 3019–3038
- Zhang, Z. (2022). "Toward the role of teacher empathy in students' engagement in English language classes." *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.880935>